

Annotated Checklist of the true bugs (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) of Albania

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ABSTRACT: This checklist presents the Heteropteran species published from Albania, with critical consideration of the available primary literature, the present national territory, and the plausibility of identification. A total of 649 species were considered for validation. The records of thirteen species are now located outside Albania: *Oncochila scapularis* (Fieber, 1844), *Tingis (Tingis) crispata* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838), *Dicyphus (Brachyceroea) annulatus* (Wolff, 1804), *Horistus (Primihoristus) orientalis* (Gmelin, 1790), *Acetropis (Acetropis) carinata* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1841), *Orthocephalus bivittatus* Fieber, 1864, *Campylomma verbasci* (Meyer-Dür, 1843), *Scolopostethus thomsoni* Reuter, 1875, *Peritrechus geniculatus* (Hahn, 1832), *Dicranocephalus marginicollis* (Puton, 1881), *Tritomegas bicolor* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Eurydema (Horvatherydema) fieberi* Schummel, 1837, and *Leprosoma inconspicuum* Baerensprung, 1859. The report of one species, *Heterotoma planicornis* (Pallas, 1772), is based on a citation error. On the other hand, some species which were published a fairly long time ago and overlooked in earlier catalogues, could be added. Because of differing opinions on their taxonomic status, the likelihood of misidentification, or unclear assignment to present-day Albania, we had to place a question mark over 62 of the species recorded.

PËRMBLEDHJE: Ky katalog përmbledh speciet e rendit Heteroptera të raportuara nga Shqipëria, duke shqyrtuar në mënyrë kritike literaturën shkencore primare të disponueshme, përkatësinë ndaj territorit aktual të Shqipërisë dhe saktësinë e identifikimit. Në total, u analizuan 649 specie për verifikim. Trembëdhjetë specie rezultojnë të jenë të regjistruara jashtë territorit të Shqipërisë: *Oncochila scapularis* (Fieber, 1844), *Tingis (Tingis) crispata*

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(Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838), *Dicyphus (Brachyceroea) annulatus* (Wolff, 1804), *Horistus (Primihoristus) orientalis* (Gmelin, 1790), *Acetropis (Acetropis) carinata* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1841), *Orthocephalus bivittatus* Fieber, 1864, *Campylomma verbasci* (Meyer-Dür, 1843), *Scolopostethus thomsoni* Reuter, 1875, *Peritrechus geniculatus* (Hahn, 1832), *Dicranocephalus marginicollis* (Puton, 1881), *Tritomegas bicolor* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Eurydema (Horvatheurydema) fieberi* Schummel, 1837 dhe *Leprosoma inconspicuum* Baerensprung, 1859. Regjistrimi i një specieje, *Heterotoma planicornis* (Pallas, 1772), është rezultat i një gabimi citimi. Nga ana tjetër, disa specie të raportuara prej kohësh, por të anashkaluara në katalogët e mëparshëm, mund të përfshihen. Për shkak të pikëpamjeve të ndryshme mbi statusin e tyre taksonomik, mundësisë së gabimeve në identifikim ose pasigurisë lidhur me përkatësinë e tyre ndaj territorit të sotëm të Shqipërisë, është vënë në dyshim përkatësia e 62 specieve të regjistruara.

KEYWORDS: Critical review of records, Eastern Mediterranean fauna, Balkan Peninsula.

INTRODUCTION AND HISTORY OF THE HETEROPTEROLOGICAL RESEARCH IN ALBANIA

Many of the Heteroptera records from Albania date back to a time when parts of today's neighbouring countries were still included. To ensure accuracy, we have reviewed this data, which has often been uncritically adopted in later catalogues. Dallas (1851, 1852) reports on hemipterous insects housed in the Museum of Natural History in London (BMNH) are considered to include the first documented heteropteran species in Albania. However, the information provided does not go beyond 'Albania, leg. W. Wilson Saunders'. Therefore, it is uncertain whether these records, as well as those of Horváth (1876), are actually located in present-day Albanian territory. The species listed by Walker (1875), Reuter (1891), and Horváth (1906) are few. However, they named the localities more precisely, allowing for a clear assignment to present-day states. Schumacher (1914) published the first comprehensive list of Albanian Heteroptera. He combed through the entomological collection of the Bosnian-Herzegovinian State Museum in Sarajevo (ZMBH). The material studied was collected by Apfelbeck (undated), by Mustajbek Kurbegović from 1897 and 1898, by Latif Buljabašić from 1905, and by Winneguth from 1906 and 1908. It is worth noting that Schumacher identified many of these specimens before Horváth (1916), who had also identified them but had not labelled them and only published his notes two years after Schumacher. As a result, the lists of both authors largely coincide. Shortly thereafter, Royer (1922, 1923, 1924a, and 1924b) reported on his studies of material collected by Rivet and co-workers on the Balkan peninsula between 1916 and 1918. Csiki (1940) also collected material in the north and east of present-day Albania during his travels in the Balkans between 1916 and 1918. The yield, which took more than 20 years to process and publish, ended up in the Hungarian National Museum in Budapest (HNHM). Mancini (1953) supplemented these lists with numerous new species found in the collections of the Natural History Museum in Vienna (NHMW), Austria. The specimens are from collections by Penther in 1914, by Karny who collected in 1917 and 1918, by Capra (undated), and another unnamed expedition. Mancini also integrated Albanian data from 1941, which was made available to him by Tamanini. Josifov (1970) studied the Heteroptera of the Albania expedition, carried out by the German Entomological Institute in Eberswalde (former GDR, today Germany) in 1961. The vast majority of individuals were deposited in the Senckenberg Deutsches Entomologisches Institut in Müncheberg, Germany (SDEI); a few specimens remained in the Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences in Sofia, Bulgaria (ZISB). According to our knowledge, Misja (1970, 1973) was the first Albanian entomologist to study true bugs in his country. The bugs collected by him are housed in the Natural History Museum Tirana, Albania (NMHT). Halimi (2011) and Halimi et al. (2010, 2014, 2018, 2020, 2024) have since published

a doctoral thesis and several articles on the topic. Apart from some smaller works, such as Gkrazntani & Kallenborn (2023) and reports on naturalists' community platforms on the Heteroptera of Albania, the work of Graf et al. (2018) on the aquatic invertebrate fauna of Vijosa is particularly important for nature conservation.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Taxonomy and nomenclature: It is unsurprising that the taxonomy and nomenclature of many species recorded from Albania needed updating, particularly those mentioned in older literature. The Catalogue of the Palaearctic Heteroptera (Aukema & Rieger, 1995–2006; Aukema et al., 2013) was primarily used as a guideline in our work, along with its continuously updated online version edited by B. Aukema. When citing literature, we use the original references in their original language. An exclamation mark '!' in literature citations indicates that the author has personally verified the reference. Our comments are enclosed in square brackets [], where [?] denotes a questionable record that should be verified, [x] denotes a deletion, and [sic] denotes an exact replication, not a spelling error on our part.

Locations: When citing literature, original information is used for locations. As Albania's current borders have only been in effect since 1912 and 1925, we put a question mark on them if older literature citations or collection material with the reference 'Albania' do not contain any more precise information about place or date. This also applies to the distribution data from Stichel (1955–1962), which is only cited if there are no other references to Albania available. Table 1 presents the current names of the record localities in Albania, along with information on the municipality unit (Lnjësi administrative), municipality (Komunë or Bashkia), and county (Qark) according to the 2015 local government reform. This table includes both the indefinite and definite forms of proper names, as both can be found in literature or on maps. Examples are Durrës, Durrësi and Tiranë, Tirana. Apart from that, we use only the indefinite form. Some old or foreign-language place names, such as Italian 'Valona' for Vlorë or 'San Giovanni di Medua' for Shëngjin, presented certain difficulties. The lists of Albanian records created by Friese (1967) and Lack & Barina (2020), as well as the GeoNames geographical database website, have been a welcome help. However, for some locations mentioned in the literature, we were not able to identify them or to do so unambiguously (see Table 2). Table 3 lists those records that currently belong to countries other than Albania.

Collection abbreviations: The following abbreviations refer to depositories and will be used in square brackets throughout the text:

BMNH: Museum of Natural History, London, England.

HNHM: Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest, Hungary.

JBSC: coll. Josef Bryja, Studenec, Czech Republic.

MCRI: Museo Civico, Rovereto, Italy.

MCSN: Museo Civico di Storia Naturale 'Giacomo Doria', Genova, Italy.

MHNG: Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle, Geneva, Switzerland.

HNHM: Magyar Nemzeti Múzeum (Hungarian National Museum), Budapest, Hungary.

MSNV: Museo Civico di Storia Naturale, Verona, Italy.

NHMT: Natural History Museum Tirana, Albania.

NHMW: Naturhistorisches Museum Wien, Vienna, Austria.

OLML: Oberösterreichisches Landesmuseum, Linz, Austria.

PCEH: Private collection E. Heiss, Innsbruck, Austria.

PCMG: Private collection M. Gkrazntani, Friedrichsthal, Germany.

RMW: Römermuseum Wien (Vindobona), Vienna, Austria.

SDEI: Senckenberg Deutsches Entomologisches Institut, Müncheberg, Germany.

ZISB: Zoological Institute, Academy of Sciences, Sofia, Bulgaria.

ZIUT: Zoological Institute, University of Tirana, Albania.

ZMAS: Zoological Institute, Russian Academy of Sciences, St. Petersburg, Russia.

ZMBH: Zemaljski Muzej Bosne i Hercegovine (National Museum of Bosnia and Herzegovina), Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Online platforms: We only considered reports from online platforms such as iNaturalist or Flickr if they were of particular interest, such as first or rare reports from Albania, and if identification of species was confirmed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The list below presents suprageneric taxa in systematic order as provided by Aukema & Rieger (1995–2006), with genera and subgeneric taxa listed alphabetically. Bold print indicates species and subspecies whose occurrence in Albania is confirmed or highly probable. Any comments we have on the taxon or documented records are found in the 'Note' section. The locations of records are presented in current spelling along with the superordinate administrative structure. Figure 1 depicts the locations of Heteroptera records across the various districts of Albania.

Heteropteran species recorded from Albania

Infraorder: DIPSOCOROMORPHA Miyamoto, 1961

DIPSOCORIDAE Dohrn, 1853

[?] *Alpagut castaneovitream* (Linnavuori, 1951)

Location of record: ?

Reference: [?] Kerzhner, 1995: Albania. [?] Fent et al., 2011: Albania.

Note: Josifov (1986, as *Cryptostemma (Harpago) castaneovitream*) and Heiss & Péricart (2007, as *Harpago castaneovitream*) classify this species as part of the Pontic and Eastern Mediterranean fauna, without mentioning Albania.

Cryptostemma (Cryptostemma) alienum Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835

Location of record: Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Mancini, 1953 (as *Cryptostemma alienus* [sic] H. S.): Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

Infraorder: NEPOMORPHA Popov, 1968

Superfamily: NEPOIDEA Latreille, 1802

NEPIDAE Latreille, 1802: NEPINAE Latreille, 1802

Nepa cinerea Linnaeus, 1758

Locations of records: Martanesh (Bulqizë, Qark Dibër); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck); Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Oroshi, Velipoja. Mancini, 1953: Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Misja, 1970 (as *Nepa rubra* L.): Martanesh (10.VII.1965).

Ranatra (Ranatra) linearis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Figure 1. Locations of Heteroptera records in Albania, indicated by numbered squares or rhombuses within each county. Further explanations in Table 1.

Location of record: Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).

References: Mancini, 1953: Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Misja, 1970: Shkodër (28.X.1958).

BELOSTOMATIDAE Leach, 1815

***Lethocerus patruelis* (Stål, 1854)**

Locations of records: Durrës (Qark Durrës); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1917 (as *Belostoma (Lethocerus) cordofanum* Mayr): Durazzo, Skutari [Shkodër] [ZMBH]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Belostoma cardofanum* Mayr): Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1970 (as *Belostoma [sic] cordophanum* M.): Elbasan (IV.1964). [?] Perez Goodwyn, 2006: Albania, 1 ♀ (undated; St. Petersburg Museum collection, Russia) [ZMAS]. Halimi, 2011 (as *Belostoma cordophanum* Montandon, 1898): Farkë (13.VII.2009).

Superfamily: CORIXOIDEA Leach, 1815

[?] MICRONECTIDAE Jaczewski, 1924 [Corixidae Leach, 1815: Micronectinae Jaczewski, 1924]

[?] *Micronecta (Dichaetonecta) scholtzi* (Fieber, 1860)

Location of record: [?] Berat (Qark Berat).

Reference: Jansson, 1986: [?] Berat.

Note: No original record of this species on Albanian territory has been found. However, the distribution map No. 2 by Jansson (1986) indicates a museum specimen from the vicinity of the city of Berat, which he checked (black circle) but did not specify.

[?] *Micronecta (Micronecta) griseola* Horváth, 1899

Location of record: [?] Kutë, Vjosë (Mallakastër, Qark Fier).

References: [?] Graf et al., 2017: Vjosa river (2014–2017).

Note: Graf et al. (2018) did not document this species, despite working with the same material. The determination of this specimen is considered questionable, according to W. Rabitsch (pers. comm.).

[?] CORIXIDAE Leach, 1815: CYMATIAINAE Walton, 1940

[?] *Cymatia coleoprata* (Fabricius, 1777)

Locations of records: [?] Durrës (Qark Durrës); [?] Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

Reference: [?] Schumacher, 1914 (as *Notonecta glauca* L. var. *marginata* Muell.): Durazzo (leg. Apfelbeck); Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH].

Note: Kirkaldy (1897) synonymised *Notonecta marginata* Müller, 1776 with *Notonecta obliqua* Thunberg, 1787. Kerzhner (1994) considered it identical with *Cymatia coleoprata* (Fabricius, 1777). For further information, see Polhemus, 1995.

CORIXIDAE Leach, 1815: CORIXINAE Leach, 1815

***Corixa affinis* Leach, 1817**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Kutë, Vjosë (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Librazhd (Qark Elbasan); Prroj Dunavec (Korçë, Qark Korçë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë)

References: Schumacher, 1914: Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898); Durazzo (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Durazzo, Velipoja, Valona. Royer,

1924a: Dunavec (IX, 2 ♀). Mancini, 1953: Berati, Libraz, Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Graf et al., 2018: Kutë, Fluss Vjosa (IV.2017).

***Corixa punctata* (Illiger, 1807)**

Locations of records: Korçë (Qark Korçë); Maliq (Qark Korçë); Prroj Dunavec (Korçë, Qark Korçë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Corixa geoffroyi* Leach, 1817): Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Corixa Geoffroyi* [sic] Leach, 1817): Velipoja. Royer, 1924a (as *Corixa Geoffroyi* [sic] Leach, 1817): environs de Koritza [Korçë] (VIII, 1 ♂); Dunavec (IX, 1♀). Mancini, 1953: Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Misja, 1973: Maliq (30.VII.1970) [NHMT].

***Hesperocorixa moesta* (Fieber, 1848)**

Locations of records: Prroj Dunavec (Korçë, Qark Korçë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Arctocorixa moesta* Fieb.): Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Arctocorixa moesta* Fieb.): Velipoja. Royer, 1924a (as *Arctocorixa moesta* Fieb.): Dunavec (IX, 1 ♂, 1 ♀).

***Hesperocorixa parallela* (Fieber, 1860)**

Locations of records: Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Arctocorixa parallela* Fieb.): Valona. Josifov, 1970 (as *Corixa (Hesperocorixa) parallela* (Fieber, 1860)): Luria östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Hesperocorixa sahlbergi* (Fieber, 1848)**

Locations of records: Durrës (Qark Durrës); Librazhd (Qark Elbasan); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Arctocorixa sahlbergi* Fieb.): Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898); Durazzo (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Arctocorixa sahlbergi* Fieb.): Durazzo, Velipoja. Mancini, 1953 (as *Sigara sahlbergi* Fieb.): Libraz, Petrela, Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

[?] *Sigara (Halicorixa) mayri* (Fieber, 1860)

Location of record: [?] Sarandë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Jansson, 1986: [?] Sarandë; Jansson, 1995: Albania.

Note: No original record of this species on Albanian territory has been found. However, according to distribution map No. 34 by Jansson (1986), a museum specimen from the vicinity of the city of Sarandë exists (black circle).

***Sigara (Pseudovermicorixa) nigrolineata nigrolineata* (Fieber, 1848)**

Locations of records: Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Librazhd (Qark Elbasan); Lushnjë (Qark Fier); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Prroj Dunavec (Korçë, Qark Korçë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Arctocorixa nigrolineata* Fieb.): Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Arctocorixa nigrolineata* Fieb.): Velipoja. Royer, 1924a (as *Arctocorixa Fabricii* [sic] Fieb.): Dunavec (1 ♂, 1 ♀). Mancini, 1953 (as *Sigara nigrolineata* Fieb.): Lusnia, Libraz, Petrela, Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Sigara (Pseudovermicorixa) nigrolineata* (Fieber, 1848)): Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1973 (as *Sigara nigrolineata* Fieb.): Korçë (27.VIII.1970) [NHMT].

[?] *Sigara (Sigara) dorsalis* (Leach, 1817)

Note: This species possibly occurs in Albania. A record by Grupče (1961) from Lake Scutari (Liqen i Shkodrës) could refer to either Albania or Montenegro.

Sigara (Sigara) striata (Linnaeus, 1758)

Locations of records: Prroj Dunavec (Korçë, Qark Korçë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Arctocorisa striata* L.): Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Arctocorisa striata* L.): Velipoja. Royer, 1924a (as *Arctocorisa striata* L.): Dunavec (IX, 3 ♂).

Note: Schumacher (1914) mentions the locality 'Janina', which is now known as Ioannina (Albanian Janinë, Janina) and is part of Greece.

Sigara (Vermicorixa) lateralis (Leach, 1817)

Locations of records: Lushnjë (Qark Fier); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Arctocorisa hieroglyphica* Duf.): Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Arctocorisa hieroglyphica* Duf.): Velipoja, Valona. Mancini, 1953 (as *Sigara hieroglyphica* Duf.): Lusnia (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

Sigara (Vermicorixa) scripta (Rambur, 1840)

Location of record: Lushnjë (Qark Fier).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Lusnia (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

NAUCORIDAE Leach, 1815: NAUCORINAE Leach, 1815

Ilyocoris cimicoides cimicoides (Linnaeus, 1758)

Locations of records: Buçimas (Pogradec, Qark Korçë); Prroj Dunavec (Korçë, Qark Korçë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Naucoris cimicoides* L.): Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Naucoris cimicoides* L.): Velipoja. Royer, 1924a (as *Naucoris cimicoides* L.): Dunavec près Koritza [Korçë] (IX, 1 sp.); marais de Starova [Buçimas] (IX, 1 sp.).

APHELOCHEIRIDAE Fieber, 1851

Aphelocheirus (Aphelocheirus) aestivalis (Fabricius, 1794)

Location of record: Kutë, Vjosë (Mallakastër, Qark Fier).

Reference: Graf et al., 2018: Kutë, Fluss Vjosa (IV.2017).

NOTONECTIDAE Latreille, 1802: ANISOPINAE Hutchinson, 1929

Anisops sardeus sardeus Herrich-Schaeffer, 1849

Locations of records: Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Anisops producta* [sic] Fieb.): Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Anisops producta* [sic] Fieb.): Velipoja. Mancini, 1953 (*Anisops sardeus* H. S.): Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

NOTONECTIDAE Latreille, 1802: NOTONECTINAE Latreille, 1802

Notonecta (Notonecta) glauca glauca Linnaeus, 1758

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Fushë

Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Notonecta glauca* L.): Korab, Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1973: Bizë (16.VII.1961) [NHMT]. Halimi, 2011 (*Notonecta glauca* Linnaeus, 1758): Farkë (13.VII.2009).

Notonecta (Notonecta) maculata Fabricius, 1794

Locations of records: Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër)

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Notonecta marmorea* F.): Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Velipoja. Mancini, 1953: Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

Notonecta (Notonecta) meridionalis Poisson, 1926

Locations of records: Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Notonecta glauca* var. *hybrida* Poiss.): Korab (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Notonecta glauca hybrida* Poisson, 1953): Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI].

Notonecta (Notonecta) obliqua Thunberg, 1787

Locations of records: Durrës (Qark Durrës); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Roskovec (Qark Fier); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Notonecta furcata* Fabr.): Durazzo, Velipoja. Royer, 1924a (as *Notonecta glauca* L. var. *furcata* Fabr.): environs de Koritza [Korçë] (VIII, 2 sp.). Misja, 1970 (as *Notonecta oblique* [sic] Gall.): Ibë (06.VI.1968). Halimi et al., 2018 (as *Notonecta obliqua* Fallen [sic], 1787): Roskovec (V.–IX.2015–2017).

Note: See note on *Cymatia coleoprata* (Fabricius, 1777).

Notonecta (Notonecta) viridis Delcourt, 1909

Locations of records: Divjakë (Qark Fier); Kutë, Vjosë (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).

References: Mancini, 1953: Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Graf et al., 2018: Kutë, Fluss Vjosa (IV.2017). Halimi, 2011: Divjakë (22.IX.2008).

Superfamily: PLEOIDEA Fieber, 1851

PLEIDAE Fieber, 1851

Plea minutissima minutissima Leach, 1817

Location of record: Buçimas (Pogradec, Qark Korçë).

Reference: Royer, 1924a (as *Plea atomaria* Pallas): marais de Starova [Buçimas], (IX, 3 sp.).

Infraorder: GERROMORPHA Popov, 1971

Superfamily: MESOVELIOIDEA Douglas & Scott, 1867

MESOVELIIDAE Douglas & Scott, 1867: MESOVELIINAE Douglas & Scott, 1867

Mesovelia vittigera Horváth, 1895

Location of record: Elbasan (Qark Elbasan).

Reference: Horváth, 1924: Elbasan (leg. Mader) [HNHM].

Superfamily: HEBROIDEA Amyot & Serville, 1843

HEBRIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: HEBRINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843

Hebrus (Hebrus) montanus Kolenati, 1857

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi, Flußtal des Luma (250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI].

Hebrus (Hebrus) pusillus pusillus Fallén, 1807

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Sherishtë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Hebrus pusillus* Fabr. [sic]): Kishbarda [Sherishtë]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Hebrus pusillus* Fallén, 1807): Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi, Flußtal des Luma (250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI].

Hebrus (Hebrusella) ruficeps Thomson, 1871

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Velipoja. Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (05.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Josifov, 1970: Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi, Flußtal des Luma (250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI].

Superfamily: HYDROMETROIDEA Billberg, 1820

HYDROMETRIDAE Billberg, 1820: HYDROMETRINAE Billberg, 1820

Hydrometra stagnorum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Locations of records: Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Krumë (Has, Qark Kukës); Kutë, Vjosë (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Orikum (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Tomorr-Tyrbja e Abaz Aliut (Skrapar, Qark Berat); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Oroshi, Pashaliman [Orikum]. Mancini, 1953: Kruma, Elbassan, Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970: Poliçan westlich Tomor (Kulturland, 500 m, 12.VI.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi, Flußtal des Luma (250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (20.V.1969). Graf et al., 2018: Kutë, Fluss Vjosa (IV.2017).

Superfamily: Gerroidea Leach, 1815

VELIIDAE Brullé, 1836: MICROVELIINAE China & Usinger, 1949: MICROVELIINI China & Usinger, 1949

Microvelia (Picaultia) pygmaea (Dufour, 1833)

Location of record: Elbasan (Qark Elbasan).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Elbassan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

VELIIDAE Brullé, 1836: VELIINAE Brullé, 1836

Velia (Plesiovelia) affinis fillippii Tamanini, 1947

Locations of records: Markaj (Tropojë, Qark Kukës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Tomorr-Tyrbja e Abaz Aliut (Skrapar, Qark Berat).

References: Tamanini, 1947: Petrela, M. Tomori [loc. typ.]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Velia fillippii* Tam.): Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941); M. Tomori (coll. Mancini). Misja, 1973 (as *Velia affinis* Kol.): Markaj (B. Curr) (27.VIII.1971) [NHMT].

[?] *Velia (Plesiovelia) currens* (Fabricius, 1794)

Locations of records: [?] Mirditë (Qark Lezhë); [?] Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë).

References: [?] Schumacher, 1914: Oroshi (leg. Apfelbeck); Merdita (leg. Adolph Winneguth, 1906, 1908) [ZMBH]. [?] Horváth, 1916: Merdita, Oroshi.

Note: Andersen (1995) suggests that most records of *Velia currens* prior to Tamanini's work published in 1947 refer to other *Velia* species. Therefore, the data provided above should be viewed with caution.

Velia (Plesiovelia) mancinii mancinii Tamanini, 1947

Location of record: Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan).

Reference: Mancini, 1953 (as *Velia mancinii* Tam.): Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

Velia (Plesiovelia) pelagonensis Hoberlandt, 1941

Locations of records: Krumë (Has, Qark Kukës); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Tamanini, 1947 (as *Velia balcanica* sp. n): Petrela (1941) [MCRI]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Velia pelagonensis* var. *balcanica* Tam.): Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941); Kruma (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970: Kulla e Lumës bei Kukësi, Flußtal des Luma (250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI].

[?] *Velia (Velia) rivulorum* (Fabricius, 1775)

Locations of records: [?] Durrës (Qark Durrës); [?] Orikum (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); [?] Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: [?] Schumacher, 1914: Durazzo (leg. Apfelbeck); Valona (leg. Apfelbeck); Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. [?] Horváth, 1916: Durazzo, Pashaliman [Orikum], Valona.

Note: Records of this western Mediterranean species are most likely based on misidentifications.

GERRIDAE Leach, 1815: GERRINAE Leach, 1815: GERRINI Leach, 1815

Aquarius najas (De Geer, 1773)

Locations of records: Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Gerris najas* Geer [sic]): Oroshi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (*Gerris najas* Deg.): Oroshi. Mancini, 1953 (as *Gerris najas* De G.): Elbasan (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

Aquarius paludum paludum (Fabricius, 1794)

Locations of records: Durrës (Qark Durrës); Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kutë, Vjosë (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Gerris paludum* F.): Durazzo (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Gerris paludum* Fabr.): Durazzo. Misja, 1970 (as *Gerris (A) paludum* F.): Tiranë (16.IV.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Gerris paludum* Fabricius, 1794): Farkë (13.VII.2009). Graf et al., 2018: Kutë, Fluss Vjosa (IV.2017).

Gerris (Gerris) argentatus Schummel, 1832

Locations of records: Byshek (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë);

Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Gerris argentata* [sic] Schumm.): Valona. Misja, 1970 (as *Gerris argentatus* Schumn. [sic]): Tiranë (26.IV.1969). Halimi, 2011: Farkë (13.VII.2009); Byshek (18.VII.2009).

***Gerris (Gerris) costae fieberi* Stichel, 1938**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Gerris costae* H.–S.): Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Gerris (Gerris) costai* [sic] *fieberi* Stichel, 1938): Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1973 (as *Gerris costai* [sic] H. S.): Bizë (03.VIII.1971) [NHMT].

[?] *Gerris (Gerris) gibbifer* Schummel, 1832

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Divjakë (Qark Fier); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Shëngjin (Qark Lezhë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: [?] Schumacher, 1914: Durazzo (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. [?] Horváth, 1916: Durazzo, Valona. [?] Mancini, 1953: Berati (leg. Tamanini, 1941). [?] Misja, 1970 (*Gerris gibbifer* Schumn. [sic]): Shëngjin (15.IV.1968). [?] Halimi, 2011: Divjakë (22.IX.2008).

Note: Josifov (1970) and Andersen (1995) consider that earlier records of *Gerris gibbifer* Schummel, 1832 from south-eastern Europe probably refer to *Gerris (Gerris) maculatus* Tamanini, 1946.

***Gerris (Gerris) lacustris* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Location of record: Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Misja, 1970: Vorë (04.VI.1969).

***Gerris (Gerris) maculatus* Tamanini, 1946**

Locations of records: Kutë, Vjosë (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); [?] Berat (Qark Berat); [?] Durrës (Qark Durrës); [?] Shëngjin (Qark Lezhë); [?] Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Graf et al., 2018: Kutë, Fluss Vjosa (IV.2017). [?] Schumacher, 1914 (as *Gerris gibbifer* Schumm.): Durazzo (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. [?] Horváth, 1916 (as *Gerris gibbifer* Schumm.): Durazzo, Valona. [?] Mancini, 1953 (as *Gerris gibbifer* Schumm.): Berati (leg. Tamanini, 1941). [?] Misja, 1970 (as *Gerris gibbifer* Schumn. [sic]): Shëngjin (15.IV.1968).

Note: Josifov (1970) and Andersen (1995) suggest that earlier records of *Gerris gibbifer* from south-eastern Europe refer to this species.

***Gerris (Gerris) thoracicus* Schummel, 1832**

Location of record: Tragjas (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Misja, 1970 (as *Gerris thoracicus* Schumn. [sic]): Tragjas (22.V.1969).

[?] *Gerris (Gerriselloides) lateralis* Schummel, 1832

Locations of records: Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Tragjas (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

References: Misja, 1970 (as *Gerris lateralis* Schumn. [sic]): Tragjas (22.V.1969). Halimi, 2011: Farkë (13.VII.2009).

Note: The records of this boreo-montane species have to be confirmed. They may refer to *Gerris (Gerriselloides) asper* Fieber, 1860 (B. Aukema, personal communication).

Infraorder: LEPTOPODOMORPHA Popov, 1971

Superfamily: SALDOIDEA Amyot & Serville, 1843

[?] SALDIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: CHILOXANTHINAE Cobben, 1959

[?] *Chiloxanthus stellatus suturalis* (Jakovlev, 1889)

Locations of records: [?] Lushnjë (Qark Fier); [?] Peqin (Qark Elbasan).

References: [?] Misja, 1973 (as *Chiloxanthus stellatus* Curt.): Lushnjë (03.VIII.1971) [NHMT]. [?] Halimi, 2011 (as *Chiloxanthus stellatus* Curtis, 1835): Peqin (10.VIII.2008).

Note: Aukema et al. (2013) have raised concerns about the records from Albania. The geographical range extends further east, from eastern Siberia to Inner Mongolia.

SALDIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: SALDINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: SALDOIDINI Reuter, 1912

***Chartoscirta cincta cincta* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1841)**

Locations of records: Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Chartoscirta cincta* H. Sch.): Skutari [Shkodër] (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905); Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Chartoscirta cincta* H.–Sch.): Velipoja.

***Chartoscirta cocksii* (Curtis, 1835)**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Chartoscirta cocksii* Curt.): Skutari [Shkodër] (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905); Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Chartoscirta Cocksii* [sic] Curt.): Skutari [Shkodër], Oroshi. Csiki, 1940 (as *Chartoscirta Cocksii* [sic] Curt.): Kula Ljums (05.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Josifov, 1970: Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Chartoscirta elegantula elegantula* (Fallén, 1807)**

Location of record: Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan).

Reference: Mancini, 1953 (*Chartoscirta elegantula* var. *flori* Dhrn): Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

[?] *Chartoscirta elegantula longicornis* (Jakovlev, 1882)

Note: Lindskog (1995) includes Albania in the combined distribution data of the two subspecies of *Chartoscirta elegantula*. However, *Chartoscirta elegantula longicornis* (Jakovlev, 1882) has not been reported from Albania.

[?] *Halosalda lateralis* (Fallén, 1807)

Location of record: ?

References: [?] Cobben, 1960: Albanien. [?] Josifov, 1970, 1986: Albanien [quoting from Cobben, 1960].

***Macrosaldula scotica* (Curtis, 1835)**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Saldula scotica* Curt.): Kula Ljums (08.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Saldula scotica* Curt.): Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Halimi, 2011 (as *Saldula scotica* Curtis, 1835): Ndroq (06.V.2007).

***Macrosaldula variabilis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Acanthia variabilis* H. Sch.): Orosi (leg.

Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Acanthia variabilis* H.–Sch.): Oroshi. Csiki, 1940 (as *Saldula connectens* Horv.): Kula Ljums (08.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Saldula variabilis* H. S.): Berat (leg. Tamanini, 1941). [?] Cobben, 1960: Albania. [?] Péricart, 1990: Albanie!

Note: Horváth (1916) also mentions an Albanian record from ‘Shar Dagħ (Ljuboten)’. This refers to the mountain range Šar Panina-Ljuboten between Kosovo and North Macedonia.

***Saldula amplicollis* (Reuter, 1891)**

Location of record: Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI, ZISB].

***Saldula arenicola arenicola* (Scholtz, 1847)**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Saldula arenicola* Schltz.): Kula Ljums (08.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Saldula arenicola* Schltz., *Saldula arenicola* var. *connectens* Reut. and *Saldula arenicola* var. *simulator* Reut.: Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Saldula arenicola* (Scholtz, 1847)): Kulla e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Saldula melanoscela* (Fieber, 1859)**

Locations of records: Kolonjë (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër).

References: Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (05.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Josifov, 1970: Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961) [SDEI]. Halimi, 2011: Kolonjë (24.IX.2008). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

[?] *Saldula nitidula* (Puton, 1880)

Location of record: ?

Reference: [?] Péricart, 1990: Albanie!. Lindskog, 1995: Albania (referring to Péricart, 1990).

***Saldula opacula* (Zetterstedt, 1838)**

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Horváth, 1916 (as *Acanthia opacula* Zett. var. *albipennis* Reut.: Valona.

***Saldula orthochila* (Fieber, 1859)**

Location of record: Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Korab (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

***Saldula pallipes* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

***Saldula saltatoria* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Csiki, 1940: Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (20.VIII.1917, 1200 m); Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m) [HNHM]. Josifov, 1970: Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Mis-

ja, 1970: Vorë (22.VI.1969). Halimi, 2011: Ndroq (06.V.2007).

***Saldula xanthochila* (Fieber, 1859)**

Locations of records: Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Saldula xanthochila* var. *limbosa* H. S.): Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

Saldidae Amyot & Serville, 1843: Saldinae Amyot & Serville, 1843: Saldini Amyot & Serville, 1843

***Salda littoralis* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Location of record: Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër).

Reference: Csiki, 1940 (*Salda littoralis* [sic] L.): Montes Korab (22.VII.1918, 1000–1700 m) [HNHM].

Superfamily: LEPTOPODOIDEA Brullé, 1836

LEPTOPODIDAE Brullé, 1836: LEPTOPODINAE Brullé, 1836: LEPTOPODINI Brullé, 1836

***Erianotus lanosus* (Dufour, 1834)**

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

***Leptopus marmoratus* (Goeze, 1778)**

Location of record: Kodrat Shurit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953; Shurija (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1973: Tiranë (21.IX.1971) [NHMT].

Infraorder: CIMICOMORPHA Leston, Pendergrast & Southwood, 1954

Superfamily: TINGOIDEA Laporte, 1832

TINGIDAE Laporte, 1832: TINGINAE Laporte, 1832

***Acalypta gracilis gracilis* (Fieber, 1844)**

Location of record: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Josifov, 1970 (as *Acalypta gracilis* (Fieber, 1844)): Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI].

Note: It appears that Josifov's (1970, 1986) record from Albania was not considered by Péricart (1983) and Péricart & Golub (1996).

***Agramma (Agramma) atricapillum* (Spinola, 1837)**

Locations of records: Durrës (Qark Durrës); Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Reuter, 1891 (as *Serenthia atricapilla* Spin.): Avlona (1884–1885, leg. E. von Oertzen). Horváth, 1916 (as *Serenthia atricapilla* Spin.): Valona. Mancini, 1953 (as *Serenthia atricapilla* Spin.): Durrec (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Halimi, 2011 (as *Agramma atricapilla* [sic] Spinola, 1837): Golem (19.VII.2009). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

[?] *Agramma (Agramma) confusum* (Puton, 1879)

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark

Tiranë); Sauk (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Tropojë (Qark Kukës); Ura Lapaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Serentia confusa* Put.): Valona. Csiki, 1940 (as *Serentia confusa* Put. ab. *antennata* Horv.): Tropoja (01.VIII.1917); Lušna: Ura i Lopez [Ura Lapaj] (21.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Serentia intermedia* Wagn.): Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Agramma* (s.str.) *confusa* [sic] (Puton, 1879) and *Agramma* (s.str.) *intermedia* (Wagner, 1940)): Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Fluštal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1973 (as *Agramma confusa* [sic] Put.): Sauk (27.IV.1970) [NHMT].

Note: Josifov (1986) considers this species synonymous with *Agramma laetum* (Fallén, 1807) and includes it in his inventory for Albania. Péricart & Golub (1996), on the other hand, put a question mark over Albania.

[?] *Agramma* (*Agramma*) *laetum* (Fallén, 1807)

Note: Albania is included in the list of Josifov (1986). Péricart & Golub (1996), on the other hand, put a question mark over Albania and assume that most of the records from southern European localities refer to *Agramma confusum* (Puton, 1879).

***Campylosteira ciliata* Fieber, 1844**

Location of record: ?

Reference: Protić, 2004a: Albania [quoting from Protić, 2004b]. Aukema et al. (2013): Albania [quoting from Protić, 2004a]

***Campylosteira orientalis* Horváth, 1881**

Location of record: Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër)

References: Horváth, 1906 (as *Campylosteira orientalis* var. *miridita* Horv.: Velipoja (Mus. Hungarici) [HNHM?]. [?] Schumacher, 1914 (as *Campylostira* [sic] *orientalis* var. *miridita* Horv. and *Campylostira* [sic] *verna* Fall.): Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Campylostira* [sic] *orientalis* var. *miridita* Horv.): Velipoja. Péricart, 1983: Albanie (lectotype!, M. Bu (Természettudományi Múzeum Allatára. Budapest, Hongrie) [HNHM?].

***Catoplatus anticus* (Reuter, 1880)**

Locations of records: Bardhor (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916: Valona. Misja, 1973: Ibë (05.VII.1969) [NHMT]. Halimi, 2011: Bardhore (08.VI.2009).

***Catoplatus carthusianus* (Goeze, 1778)**

Locations of records: Hamallaj (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Ploshtan (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Shtiçen (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Csiki, 1940: Stiçen (in radices Montibus Djalica Ljums, 09.VII.1918); Ploštan (29.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Misja, 1970 (as *Catoplatus Carthusianus* [sic] Gz.): Vlorë (20.V.1969); Korçë (05.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Hamallaj (14.VIII.2008). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

***Catoplatus fabricii* (Stål, 1868)**

Locations of records: Peqin (Qark Elbasan); Seman (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Misja, 1970: Tiranë (16.IV.1969). Halimi, 2011: Peqin (10.VIII.2005). Halimi et al., 2018: Seman (V.–IX.2015–2017).

Copium brevicorne* (Jakovlev, 1879)*Location of record:** Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).**Reference:** Misja, 1970: Vlorë (23.V.1969).***Copium clavicorne clavicorne* (Linnaeus, 1758)****Locations of records:** Korçë (Qark Korçë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mirditë (Qark Lezhë).**References:** Schumacher, 1914 (as *Copium cornutum* Thbg.): Merdita (leg. Adolph Winneguth, 1906, 1908) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Copium cornutum* Thbg.): Merdita. Josifov, 1970 (as *Copium clavicorne* (Linnaeus, 1758)): Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1973 (*Copium clavicorne* L.): Korçë (05.VIII.19) [NHMT].***Copium teucris teucris* (Host, 1788)****Location of record:** Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier).**Reference:** Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).***Corythucha arcuata* (Say, 1832)****Location of record:** ?**Reference:** Csóka et al., 2019: Albania.***Derephysia (Derephysia) foliacea foliacea* (Fallén, 1807)****Locations of records:** Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).**References:** Csiki, 1940 (as *Derephysia lugens* Horv.): Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (19.VIII.1917, 2300–2500 m) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Derephysia foliacea* Fall. and *Derephysia lugens* Horv.): Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Misja, 1970 (*Derephysia foliacea* Fall.): Vlorë (18.V.1969).***Dictyla echii* (Schrank, 1782)****Locations of records:** Ardenica (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Kaninë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastrë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).**References:** Schumacher, 1914 (as *Monanthia echii* Schrk.): Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Monanthia Echii* [sic] Schrk.): Oroshi, Valona, Kanina. Csiki, 1940 (as *Monanthia echii* Schrnk.): Kulla Ljums (05.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (Fluštal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Dictula* [sic] *echii* Schrk.): Vlorë (27.V.1969); Vorë (02.V.1968); Ndroq (25.IV.1968). Halimi, 2011: Petrelë (12.VI.2009). Halimi et al., 2018 (as *Dictula* [sic] *echii* Schrank, 1782): Ardenica (V.–IX.2015–2017). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).***Dictyla humuli* (Fabricius, 1794)****Locations of records:** Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).**References:** Misja, 1973: Vlorë (23.V.1969) [NHMT]. Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).***Dictyla nassata nassata* (Puton, 1874)****Locations of records:** Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).**Reference:** Mancini, 1953 (*Monanthia nassata* Put.): Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

Dictyla rotundata* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)*Location of record:** ?**Reference:** Protić, 2004a: Albania [quoting from Protić, 2004b]. Aukema et al., 2013: Albania [quoting from Protić, 2004a].***Dictyonota strichnocera* (Fieber, 1844)****Locations of records:** Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë)**References:** Josifov, 1970 (as *Dictyonota (Dictyonota) strichnocera* (Fieber, 1844)): Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (19.–26.V.1969). Péricart, 1983: Albanie [quoting from Golub, 1975].[?] *Galeatus affinis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**Location of record:** ?**Reference:** Péricart & Golub, 1996: Albania [?].***Kalama tricornis* (Schränk, 1801)****Locations of records:** Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Gostilë (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Poçëm (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Sarandë (Qark Vlorë); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).**References:** Schumacher, 1914 (as *Dictyonota tricornis* Schrk.): Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Dictyonota tricornis* Schrk.): Valona. Csiki, 1940 (as *Dictyonota tricornis* Schrnk): Kösztil [Gostilë] (30.VII.1918); Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (19.VIII.1917, 1900–2300 m) [HNHM]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Dictyonota (Alcletha) tricornis* (Schränk, 1801)): Borshi südlich Vlorë (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlorë (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1973 (as *Dictyonota (A) tricornis* Schrk.): Sarandë (29.X.1970) [NHMT]. Rabitsch, 2018: Poçëm (24.–29.IV.2017).***Monosteira unicostata* (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)****Locations of records:** Poçëm (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Sherishtë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).**References:** Horváth, 1916 (as *Monostira* [sic] *unicostata* M. R.): Kishbarda [Sherishtë], Valona. Rabitsch, 2018: Poçëm (24.–29.IV.2017).[A] *Oncochila scapularis* (Fieber, 1844)**Note:** Aukema et al. (2013) cite Misja (1973) as a source, who in this case refers to Csiki (1940). However, there it reads 'Kosovo Polje: Mitrovica (1917, V.31)'. This place is located in present-day Kosovo.[?] *Physatocheila confinis* Horváth, 1905**Location of record:** ?**Reference:** [?] Péricart, 1983: Albania.**Note:** Péricart (1983) considers *Physatocheila confinis* Horváth, 1905 and *Physatocheila dumetorum* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838) as phenotypes of a systematic complex, which can be well distinguished morphologically only in the eastern part of the range.***Physatocheila dumetorum* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838)****Locations of records:** Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Shën Thanas (Voskopojë, Qark Korçë).**References:** Schumacher, 1914: Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Physatocheila dumetorum* H.Sch.): Oroshi, Shen Thanas. Protić, 2004a: Albania

[quoting from Protić, 2004b].

[?] *Stephanitis (Stephanitis) oberti* (Kolenati, 1857)

Location of record: ?

References: [?] Stichel, 1938: Albanien. [?] Péricart & Golub, 1996: Albania.

Note: This is a boreal species whose occurrence in Albania is very doubtful (Péricart, 1983). It is also missing from the list of Josifov (1986). However, without further data for Albania, it is mentioned by Péricart & Golub (1996), possibly with reference to Stichel (1938).

***Stephanitis (Stephanitis) pyri* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Locations of records: Lushnjë (Qark Fier); Shkozet (Rrogzhiinë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Stephanitis Pyri* [sic] Fabr.): Velipoja. Misja, 1973: Tiranë (10.VIII.1970); Lushnje (03.VIII.1971) [NHMT]. Halimi, 2011: Shkozet (03.VIII.2008).

[?] *Tingis (Neolasiotropis) pauperata* (Puton, 1879)

Location of record: ?

Reference: [?] Horváth, 1906 (as *Tingis pauperata* Put.): Albania! (Mus. Vindob [RMW]).

Note: Péricart (1983) and Josifov (1986) list Albania, presumably referring to Horváth (1906), the only original source known to us. At that time, however, parts of present-day Serbia, Kosovo, Montenegro and Greece were part of the Albanian territory.

***Tingis (Tingis) angustata* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Reuter, 1891 (as *Phyllontochila angustata* H. S.): Avlona (1884–1885, leg. E. von Oertzen). [?] Horváth, 1906: Albania. Horváth, 1916: Valona. Josifov, 1970: Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Tingis (Tingis) auriculata* (A. Costa, 1847)**

Locations of records: Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916: Valona. Mancini, 1953: Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

***Tingis (Tingis) cardui* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier).

References: Mancini, 1953: Elbassan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

[8] *Tingis (Tingis) crispata* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838)

Note: Aukema et al. (2013) cite Misja (1973), who in turn refers to Csiki (1940). However, there it reads 'İpek (in fauce Plavensi, 1917, v.31)'. The place 'İpek' (Turkish) is now called Pejë, Peja (Albanian) or Peć (Serbo-Croatian) and is located in present-day Kosovo.

***Tingis (Tingis) grisea* Germar, 1835**

Location of record: Kaninë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Horváth, 1916 (as *Tingis rotundicollis* Jak.): Kanina.

Note: Whether or not *Tingis rotundicollis* (Jakovlev, 1883) is a valid species is still controversial (see Péricart, 1981 and 1983; Péricart & Golub, 1996).

Tingis (Tropidocheila) geniculata (Fieber, 1844)

Locations of records: Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Shëngjin (Qark Lezhë).

References: Péricart, 1983: S. Giov. Di Medua [San Giovanni di Medua, Shëngjin] (leg. Mader, M. Bu!) [HNHM]. Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

[?] *Tingis (Tropidocheila) griseola* (Puton, 1879)

Location of record: ?

References: [?] Péricart, 1983: Albanie! [?] Josifov, 1986: Albanien.

Note: Péricart (1983) could not specify the locality and date of the specimen he examined. Presumably, Josifov (1986) refers to this literature passage.

Tingis (Tropidocheila) reticulata Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835

Location of record: Mirditë (Qark Lezhë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Merdita (leg. Adolph Winneguth, 1906, 1908) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Merdita.

Note: Schumacher (1914) also mentions an Albanian record from 'Poljana'. This may refer to a location in either Montenegro, Kosovo or North Macedonia.

Superfamily: MIROIDEA Hahn, 1833

MICROPHYSIDAE Dohrn, 1859: MICROPHYSINAE Dohrn, 1859

Loricula (Myrmericula) bedeli (Montandon, 1887)

Location of record: Kaninë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Horváth, 1916 (as *Microphysa Bedeli* [sic] Montd.): Kanina.

MIRIDAE Hahn, 1833: CYLAPINAE Kirkaldy, 1903

Fulvius oxycarenoides (Reuter, 1878)

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Berat, Petrela (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

MIRIDAE Hahn, 1833: BRYOCORINAE Baerensprung, 1860: DICYPHINI Reuter, 1883

Dicyphus (Brachyceroea) albonasutus Wagner, 1951

Locations of records: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Gërmenj (Barmash, Kolonjë, Qark Korçë).

References: Josifov, 1970: Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti (Westhang, 1100 m, 29.VI.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Dhellemmes, 2021c: District de Kolonjë, Albanie (01.X.2021; N 40.225383 E 20.659195 and N 40.225385 E 20.659182 [Gërmenj]).

[8] *Dicyphus (Brachyceroea) annulatus* (Wolff, 1804)

Note: Aukema et al. (2013) cite Misja (1973), who in turn refers to Csiki (1940). However, there it reads 'Ipek (in fauce Plavensi, 1917, v.31)'. The place 'Ipek' (Turkish) is now called Pejë, Peja (Albanian) or Peć (Serbo-Croatian) and is located in present-day Kosovo.

Dicyphus (Brachyceroea) geniculatus (Fieber, 1858)

Location of record: Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 30.VI.1961) [SDEI].

Dicyphus (Brachyceroea) globulifer (Fallén, 1829)

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër).

References: Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (02.VII.1918); Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

[?] *Dicyphus (Dicyphus) cerastii* Wagner, 1951

Location of record: ?

Reference: [?] Kerzhner & Josifov, 1999: Albania.

Dicyphus (Dicyphus) errans (Wolff, 1804)

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Dicyphus errans* Wlff. and *Dicyphus errans* var. *longicollis* Fall.): Biza (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, lux, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI].

Dicyphus (Dicyphus) stachydis wagneri Tamanini, 1956

Location of record: Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Mancini, 1953 (as *Dicyphus stachydis* Reut. [see Protić, 2002]): Pashtrikë (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

Macrolophus costalis Fieber, 1858

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Kepi i Rodonit (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastrë).

References: Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961) [SDEI]. Halimi, 2011: K. Rodonit (21.V.2007). Halimi et al., 2020: Spille.

Macrolophus pygmaeus (Rambur, 1839)

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Kodrat e Krujës (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Roskovec (Qark Fier); Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Uznovë (Berat, Qark Berat); Zharrëz (Patos, Qark Fier).

References: Josifov, 1970 (*Macrolophus insignis* Josifov, 1968): Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, lux, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Macrolophus nubilus* H.–S.): Tiranë (27.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Macrolophus (nubilus) pygmaeus* Herrich-Schäffer [sic], 1835 (Rambur, 1839) [sic]): K. Krujës (12.V.2008). Halimi et al., 2018 (as *Macrolophus nubilus* H.–S.): Zharëza, Roskovec (V.–IX.2015–2017). Halimi et al., 2020 (as *Macrolophus pygmaeus* Herrich-Schäffer [sic], 1835): Spille. Halimi et al., 2024: Uznov (15.VIII.2019) [NHMT].

MIRIDAE Hahn, 1833: DERAEOCORINAE Douglas & Scott, 1865: DERAEOCORINI Douglas & Scott, 1865

Deraeocoris (Camptobrochis) punctulatus (Fallén, 1807)

Location of record: Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Camptobrochis punctulatus* Fall.): Oroshi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Camptobrochis punctulatus* Fall.): Oroshi.

Deraeocoris (Camptobrochis) serenus (Douglas & Scott, 1868)

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Golem

(Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Campobrochis serenus* Dgl. Sc.): Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941); Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra). Josifov, 1970: Tirana (09.–12.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlorë (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 500 m, 30.VI.1961); Kulla e Lumës bei Kukësi (Luzernefeld, 300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës, Wiese (1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vorë (29.IV.1968); Berat (31.X.1968); Tiranë (03.V.1969). Halimi, 2011: Ibë (26.VII.2008). Halimi et al., 2020: Golem.

Deraeocoris (Deraeocoris) flavilinea (A. Costa, 1862)

Location of record: Durrës (Qark Durrës).

Reference: Kerzhner & Josifov, 1999: Albania (Durrës, 22.VI.2000, collected by B. Aukema [pers. communication]).

Deraeocoris (Deraeocoris) ruber (Linnaeus, 1758)

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Fushë-Krujë (Krujë, Durrës); Krumë (Has, Qark Kukës); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës); Peshtan (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Zall-Bastar (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck); Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Deraeocoris ruber* L. var. *danicus* Fabr. and *Deraeocoris ruber* L. var. *seguinus* Müll): Oroshi, Valona. Csiki, 1940 (as *Deraeocoris ruber* ab. *gothicus* Scop. and *Deraeocoris ruber* ab. *danicus* F.): Kulla e Lumës (03.V.1918, 05.VII.1918); Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (20.V.1918, 1200 m). Mancini, 1953 (as *Deraeocoris ruber* var. *gothicus* Scop., *Deraeocoris ruber* var. *danicus* F. and *Deraeocoris ruber* var. *seguinus* Müll.): Elbasan, Pashtrik, Kulla e Lumës, Kruma (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlorë (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961 [ZISB]; Uji Ftohtë südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Dajti, Shkallë Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Kulla e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Fushë-Krujë (14.VI.1964). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Poliçan (17.VI.2022); Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022) [PCMG]. Halimi et al., 2024: Peshtan (17.VI.2020) [NHMT].

Deraeocoris (Deraeocoris) rutilus (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838)

Locations of records: Kodrat e Krastës (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Ploshtan (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Sauk (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shtiçen (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Zvërnec (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

References: Csiki, 1940: Stiçen (in radices Montibus Djalica Ljums, 09.VII.1918); Ploştan (29.VII.1918). Misja, 1973: Sauk (14.VI.1970) [NHMT]. Halimi, 2011: K. Krastës (24.VI.2008). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zvërnec (14.VI.2022) [PCMG].

Deraeocoris (Deraeocoris) schach (Fabricius, 1781)

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Papër (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Peshtan (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Poliçan (Qark Berat);

Porto Palermo (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Shijon (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastrë); Vodicë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Vorë (Qark Tiranë); [?] Prezë (Vorë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953: Elbassan, Durrec, Bresh [Prezë?], Shingjonas [Shijon] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Porto Palermo südlich Vlora (21.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor, *Arbutus-Phillyrea-Macchie*, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961) [SDEI, ZISB]. Misja, 1970: Vorë (25.VI.1969). Halimi, 2011: Ndroq (06.V.2007); Papër (09.VIII.2008). Halimi et al., 2020: Spille, Mali i Robit. Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Poliçan (17.VI.2022) [PCMG]. Halimi et al., 2024: Peshtan (10.VIII.2019); Vodic (17.V.2020) [NHMT].

Note: Mancini's (1953) record from the locality of 'Bresh' possibly refers to the village of Prezë, Preza (formerly also known as Bresa, Breša).

[?] *Deraeocoris (Deraeocoris) scutellaris* (Fabricius, 1794)

Location of record: [?] Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës)

Reference: [?] Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918)

Note: See note on *Deraeocoris (Deraeocoris) ventralis ventralis* Reuter, 1904.

[?] *Deraeocoris (Deraeocoris) ventralis ventralis* Reuter, 1904

Location of record: [?] Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës)

References: [?] Csiki, 1940 (*Deraeocoris scutellaris* F.): Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918)

Note: Josifov (1970) reinterprets the species *Deraeocoris scutellaris* F. mentioned by Csiki (1940) as *Deraeocoris (Deraeocoris) ventralis* Reuter, 1904. Aukema et al. (2013) also referred to this species, citing Misja (1973), who in turn quoted Csiki (1940).

***Deraeocoris (Knightocapsus) lutescens* (Schilling, 1837)**

Locations of records: Divjakë (Qark Fier); Dukat (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Malësi e Madha (Qark Skodër); Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë)

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Camptobrochis lutescens* Schill.): Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck); Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubasić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Camptobrochis lutescens* Schill.): Oroshi, Dukati. Csiki, 1940 (as *Camptobrochis lutescens* Schill.): Malçija [Malësi e Madha] (29.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953 (as *Camptobrochis lutescens* Schill.): Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918). Josifov, 1970: Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi, Flußtal des Luma (250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Halimi, 2011: Divjakë (22.IX.2008). Halimi et al., 2020: Spille, Mali i Robit, Golem.

MIRIDAE Hahn, 1833: MIRINAE Hahn, 1833: MIRINI Hahn, 1833

***Adelphocoris josifovi* (Wagner, 1968)**

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Adelphocoris lineolatus* (Goeze, 1778)**

Locations of records: Ardenica (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Çermë e Poshtme (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Hoçisht (Devoll, Qark Korçë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lezhë (Qark Lezhë); Lybeshë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark

Tiranë); Mali me Gropë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Uznovë (Berat, Qark Berat); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vodice (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Zharrëz (Patos, Qark Fier).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck); Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Cukali, Oroshi. Royer, 1924b (as *Adelphocoris lineolatus* Goeze var. *binotatus* Hahn): env. de Koritza [Korçë] (VI–VII, 1 ♂, 1 ♀). Csiki, 1940 (as *Adelphocoris lineolatus* Goeze var. *binotatus* Hahn): Kula Ljums (02.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953 (as *Adelphocoris lineolatus* var. *binotatus* Hhn): Scutari [Shkodër], Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Petrela, Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vloza (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkallë Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Mali me Gropë (Rotbuchenbestand mit angrenzender Wiese, 1200 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshti, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Luzernfeld, 300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Unterwuchs in Apfelplantage, 350 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Thethi, Nordalbanische Alpen (01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Lezhë (06.VII.1968); Velipojë (16.VIII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Dajt (25.VI.2008); Spille (27.IX.2007); Golem (19.VII.2009); Çermë (17.IX.2008). Halimi et al., 2018: Zharëza, Ardenica (V.–IX.2015–2017). Halimi et al., 2020: Spille, Golem. Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Hoçisht (07.IX.2022) [PCMG]. Halimi et al., 2024: Uznov (20.VII.2019); Vodice (27.VII.2019); Lybesh (03.IX.2019) [NHMT].

***Adelphocoris seticornis* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Locations of records: Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lezhë (Qark Lezhë); Papaj Ballaban (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (05.VII.1918). Josifov, 1970: Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Luzernfeld, 300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Ballabanovë (28.X.1968); Vlorë (19.V.1969); Lezhë (06.VII.1968); Korçë (05.VIII.1969); Velipojë (16.VIII.1969).

***Adelphocoris ticinensis* (Meyer-Dür, 1843)**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lezhë (Qark Lezhë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).

References: Mancini, 1953: Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Lezhë (04.VII.1968).

***Adelphocoris vandalicus* (Rossi, 1790)**

Locations of records: Kodrat e Krujës (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Tropojë (Qark Kukës).

References: Royer, 1924b: env. de Koritza [Korçë] (2 ♀). Csiki, 1940: Tropoja (01.VIII.1917); Kula Ljums (02.VII.1918, 05.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953: Pashtrik, Korab (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Dajti, Shkallë Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 25.–29.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Luzernfeld, 25.–

29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Tiranë (06.IX.1969). Halimi, 2011: Petrelë (12.VI.2009); K. Krujë (12.V.2008). Halimi et al., 2020: Spille; Mali i Robit.

***Agnocoris reclairei* (Wagner, 1949)**

Location of record: Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier).

Reference: Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

***Agnocoris rubicundus* (Fallén, 1807)**

Location of record: Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

Reference: Horváth, 1916 (as *Lygus rubicundus* Fall.): Velipoja.

***Alloeonotus egregius* Fieber, 1864**

Locations of records: Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës).

References: Csiki, 1940: Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (16.VII.1918, 1300 m); Montes Korab (22.VII.1918, 1000–1700 m, 26.VII.1918, 1800 m). Mancini, 1953: Korab, Pashtrik (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970: Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Aphanosoma italicum* A. Costa, 1842**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Royer, 1924b: env. de Koritza [Korçë] (VI. 1 ♂). Josifov, 1970 (as *Aphanosoma italicum* Costa, 1841 [sic]): Dajti (Westhang, 1100 m, 29.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI, ZISB]. Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Poliçan (17.VI.2022) [PCMG].

***Brachycoleus decolor* Reuter, 1887**

Locations of records: Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Kodrat e Krastës (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Kolonjë (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Mali me Gropë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ploshtan (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Royer, 1924b (as *Brachycoleus scriptus* Fab.): environs de Koritza [Korçë] (VI–VII, 9 ♂, 4 ♀). Csiki, 1940 (as *Brachycoleus scriptus* F.): Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (13.VII.1918, 1800 m, 16.VII.1918, 1300 m). Mancini, 1953 (as *Brachycoleus scriptus* F.): Ploshtan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Mali me Gropë (Dolinengebiet, 1350 m, 06.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Tiranë (06.IX.1969). Halimi, 2011: Petrelë (12.VI.2009); K. Krastës (24.VI.2008); Kolonjë (24.IX.2008).

***Calocoris affinis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

Location of record: Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër)

Reference: Josifov, 1970 (as *Calocoris* (*Calocoris*) *affinis* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1835)): Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Geröllhang in Fagus-Abies-Wald in 1350 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Calocoris roseomaculatus angularis* (Fieber, 1864)**

Locations of records: Bicaç (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër);

Mali me Gropë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Calocoris angularis* Fieb.): Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck); Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Calocoris angularis* Fieb.): Cukali, Oroshi. Csiki, 1940 (as *Calocoris roseomaculatus* Gmel. [sic], *Calocoris roseomaculatus* ab. *fuscognatus* Stich., and *Calocoris roseomaculatus* ab. *nigroinductus* Stich.): Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m). Mancini, 1953 (as *Calocoris angularis* Fieb., *Calocoris roseomaculatus* De G., *Calocoris roseomaculatus* De G. var. *fuscognatus* Stich., and *Calocoris roseomaculatus* De G. var. *nigroinductus* Stich.): Bicaj (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Calocoris (Calocoris) angularis* (Fieber, 1864): Mali me Gropë (Dolinengebiet, 1350 m, 06.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Poliçan (17.VI.2022) [PCMG].

Note: Mancini (1953) also mentions 'Uskub' as a record location. Uskub is the Turkish name for Skopje, the present capital of North Macedonia.

[?] *Calocoris roseomaculatus roseomaculatus* (De Geer, 1773)

Note: All records from the Balkan Peninsula refer to the Pontomediterranean subspecies *Calocoris roseomaculatus angularis* (Fieber, 1864), according to Josifov (1986) and Kerzhner & Josifov (1999).

***Camptozygum aequale* (Villers, 1789)**

Location of record: Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Camptozygum pinastris* Fall.): Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Camptozygum Pinastris* [sic] Fall.): Oroshi.

***Capsodes gothicus gothicus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali me Gropë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Capsodes gothicus* L. and *Capsodes gothicus* ab. *elegans* Reut.): Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m). Mancini, 1953 (as *Capsodes gothicus* L. and *Capsodes gothicus* ab. *elegans* Reut.): Pashtrik (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970 (*Capsodes (Capsodes) gothicus* (Linnaeus, 1758)): Mali me Gropë (Dolinengebiet, 1350 m, 06.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Capsus ater* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Capsus ater* L. var. *tyrannus* Fabr.): Valona. Josifov, 1970: Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

***Capsus wagneri* (Remane, 1950)**

Locations of records: Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Misja, 1973 (as *Capsus Wagneri* [sic] Rem.): Golem (13.V.1970) [NHMT]. Halimi, 2011: Spille (27.IX.2007). Halimi et al., 2020: Spille.

***Charagochilus (Charagochilus) gyllenhalii* (Fallén, 1807)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Josifov, 1970 (as *Charagochilus gyllenhalii* [sic]): Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 30.VI.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–

08.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Calocorchilus gyllenhali* [sic] Fall.): Vlorë (05.X.1969).

***Closterotomus annulus* (Brullé, 1832)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Krumë (Has, Qark Kukës); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lukovë (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Poçëm (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shtiçën (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Calocoris annulus* Brull.): Kula Ljums (02.VII.1918), Stiçen (in radices Montibus Djalica Ljums, 09.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953 (as *Calocoris annulus* Brull.): Elbassan, Durrec, Kula Ljums, Kruma (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Berat (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Calocoris (Closterotomus) annulus* (Brullé, 1832)): Lukova nördlich Saranda (250 m, 24.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea*-Macchie, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961) [SDEI, ZISB]. Rabitsch, 2018: Poçëm (24.–29.IV.2017).

***Closterotomus biclavatus biclavatus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Misja, 1970 (as *Calocoris biclavatus* H.–S.): Vlorë (24.V.1969).

***Closterotomus cinctipes* (A. Costa, 1853)**

Locations of records: Bicaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lukovë (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Calocoris cinctipes* Costa): Kula Ljums (02.VII.1918); Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (13.VII.1918, 1800 m, 16.VII.1918, 1300 m). Mancini, 1953 (as *Calocoris cinctipes* Costa): Bicaj, Kula Ljums, Elbassan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Calocoris (Closterotomus) cinctipes* (Costa, 1852) [sic]): Borshi südlich Vlora (SW-Hang mit *Pistacia* und *Phlomis*, 200–400 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Lukova nördlich Saranda (250 m, 24.V.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Rotbuchenwald, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Closterotomus fulvomaculatus* (De Geer, 1773)**

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Mancini, 1953 (as *Calocoris fulvomaculatus* De G.): Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

***Closterotomus histrio histrio* (Reuter, 1877)**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Lukovë (Himarë, Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Josifov, 1970 (as *Calocoris (Closterotomus) histrio* Reuter, 1877): Borshi südlich Vlora (SW-Hang mit *Pistacia* und *Phlomis*, 200–400 m, 14.–27.V.1961, coll. Zool. Inst. Sofia); Lukova nördlich Saranda (250 m, 24.V.1961) [SDEI, ZISB].

***Closterotomus norvegicus* (Gmelin, 1790)**

Locations of records: Bicaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Pukë (Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Zall-Bastar (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Calocoris norvegicus* [sic] Gmel.): Cukaligebirge

(leg. Apfelbeck); Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Calocoris norvegicus* [sic] Gmel. (*bipunctatus* Fabr. nec L.) and *Calocoris norvegicus* [sic] Gmel. var. *vittiger* Reut.): Valona. Mancini, 1953 (as *Calocoris norvegicus* [sic] Gmel. and *Calocoris norvegicus* Gmel. var. *vittiger* Reut.): Puka (leg. Capra); Bicaj (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1973 (*Calocoris norvegicus* [sic] Gmel.): Vlorë (21.V.1969) [NHMT]. Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022) [PCMG].

***Cyphodema instabilis* (Lucas, 1849)**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ploshtan (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Zall-Bastar (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Cyphodema instabile* [sic] Luc.): Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905); Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Oroshi, Valona. Csiki, 1940 (as *Cyphodema instabile* [sic] Luc.): Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (16.VII.1918, 1300 m); Ploštan (29.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953 (as *Cyphodema instabile* [sic] Luc.): Durrec, Elbassan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Cyphodema instabile* [sic] (Lucas, 1849)): Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022) [PCMG].

***Cyphodema mendosa* Montandon, 1887**

Location of record: Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

Reference: Josifov, 1970 (as *Cyphodema mendosum* [sic] Montandon, 1887): Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI, ZISB].

[?] *Dichroscythus intermedius* Reuter, 1885

Location of record: ?

References: [?] Stichel, 1958: Albanien. [?] Josifov, 1970: Albanien [quoting from Stichel, 1958].

***Dichroscythus valesianus* Fieber, 1861**

Location of record: Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër).

Reference: Josifov, 1970 (as *Dichroscythus bulgaricus* Josifov, 1959): Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI].

[?] *Dionconotus confluens confluens* Hoberlandt, 1945

Note: See note on *Dionconotus neglectus neglectus* (Fabricius, 1798).

[?] *Dionconotus neglectus neglectus* (Fabricius, 1798)

Locations of records: [?] Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); [?] Vermosh (Malësi e Madha, Qark Shkodër).

References: [?] Mancini, 1953 (as *Dionconotus neglectus* F.): Vermosa (leg. Penther, 1914). [?] Josifov, 1970: Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961) [SDEI].

Note: Josifov (1986) accepted the records mentioned above for Albania. Kerzhner & Josifov (1999), on the other hand, listed these records under *Dionconotus confluens*

confluens Hoberlandt, 1945.

Horistus (Horistus) infuscatus (Brullé, 1832)

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Lopus infuscatus* Brullé): Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Lopus infuscatus* Brull.): Berat, Valona. Csiki, 1940 (as *Capsodes infuscatus* Brull.): Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (16.VII.1918, 1800 m, in *Asphodelo alba* Mill.). Mancini, 1953 (as *Capsodes infuscatus* Brull.): Durrec, Pashtrik, Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Capsodes (Horistus) infuscatus* (Brullé, 1832): Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI].

[&] *Horistus (Primihoristus) orientalis* (Gmelin, 1790)

Note: Although Aukema et al. (2013) reference Albania using Misja (1973), the original source for *Capsodes cingulatus* F. is Csiki (1940), who gives 'Kosovo polje: Mitrovica (1917.V.31)' as the locality. Mitrovica is located in present-day Kosovo.

Liocoris tripustulatus (Fabricius, 1781)

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Markaj (Tropojë, Qark Kukës); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Valona. Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (05.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970: Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Fluštal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1973: Markaj (B. Curr) (27.VII.1971) [NHMT].

Lygus gemellatus (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Tomorr-Tyrbja e Abaz Aliut (Skrapar, Qark Berat).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Tomor, Kloster Abbas Ali (1800 m, 08.–10.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI].

Lygus pratensis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Locations of records: Ardenica (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lapardha 1 (Berat, Qark Berat); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Maminas (Shijak, Qark Durrës); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Roskovec (Qark Fier); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Spille (Rrogzhiinë, Qark Tiranë); Sukth (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vodicë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Zharrëz (Patos, Qark Fier).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Cukalgebirge (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905); Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Cukali, Oroshi, Valona. Royer, 1924b: env. de Koritza [Korçë] (VIII.). Josifov, 1970: Durrës (Ödland, 06.IX.1959, leg. Klausnitzer); Borshi südlich Vlora (14.–27.V.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 300 m, 30.VI.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–

08.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Ndroq (15.V.1968); Maminas (14.VI.1968); Velipojë (16.VIII.1969); Tiranë (06.IX.1969); Vlorë (16.V.1969). Halimi, 2011: Spille (27.IX.2007); Sukth (22.VI.2009). Halimi et al., 2018: Zharëza, Ardenica, Roskovec (V.–IX.2015–2017). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017). Halimi et al., 2020: Spille, Mali i Robit. Halimi et al., 2024: Vodice (13.VIII.2019); Lapardha (05.VI.2020) [NHMT].

Note: Horváth (1916) also mentions an Albanian record from ‘Shar Dagħ (Ljuboten)’. This refers to the mountain range Šar Panina-Ljuboten between Kosovo and North Macedonia.

[?] *Lygus punctatus* (Zetterstedt, 1838)

Locations of records: [?] Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); [?] Maliq (Qark Korçë); [?] Mirakë (Librazhd, Qark Elbasan); [?] Peqin (Qark Elbasan); [?] Uznovë (Berat, Qark Berat).

References: [?] Misja, 1970: Maliq (.VIII.1969). [?] Halimi, 2011 (*Lygus punctatus* Zetterstedt, 1839 [sic]): Peqin (10.VIII.2008); Mirakë (29.VII.2009). [?] Halimi et al., 2020: Golem. [?] Halimi et al., 2024: Uznov (07.V.2020) [NHMT].

Note: This species is not included in the lists of Josifov (1986), Kerzhner & Josifov (1999), and Aukema et al. (2013) for Albania. According to Wagner (1970/71), *Lygus punctatus* (Zetterstedt, 1838) is a boreomontane species. It may have been confused with *Lygus wagneri* Remane, 1955.

***Lygus rugulipennis* Poppius, 1911**

Locations of records: Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Kodrat e Krastës (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Lygus pubescens* Reut.: Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Lygus rugulipennis* (Poppius, 1911) [sic]): Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Luzernefeld, 300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Tiranë (26.IV.1969). Halimi, 2011: Dajti (25.VI.2008); K. Krastës (24.VI.2008).

***Lygus wagneri* Remane, 1955**

Locations of records: Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës).

Reference: Csiki, 1940 (as *Lygus pratensis* L. var. *punctatus* Zett. [auct. non Zetterstedt, 1838; see Josifov, 1970]): Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (16.VII.1918, 1650 m); Montes Korab (25.VIII.1917, 1600–1800 m, 26.VII.1918, 1800 m).

***Megacoelum infusum* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1837)**

Location of record: Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

***Miridius quadrvirgatus* (A. Costa, 1853)**

Locations of records: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953: Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961) [SDEI].

***Miris striatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Durrës (Qark Durrës); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mirditë (Qark Lezhë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Pycnopterna striata* L. var. *apfelbecki* nov.): Merdita (leg. Adolph Winneguth, 1906, 1908) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (*Pycnopterna striata* L. var. *Apfelbecki* [sic] Schumach.): Merdita. Mancini, 1953 (as *Pycnopterna striata* L., *Pycnopterna striata* var. *Apfelbecki* Schumach., and *Pycnopterna striata* var. *unipustulatus* Stich.): Kula Ljums, Durrec (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

Note: Horváth (1916) also mentions an Albanian record from ‘Shar Dagħ (Ljuboten)’. This refers to the mountain range of Šar Panina-Ljuboten between Kosovo and North Macedonia.

***Orthops (Montanorthops) forelii* Fieber, 1858**

Location of record: Korçë (Qark Korçë).

Reference: Misja, 1973 (as *Orthops foreli* [sic] Fieb.): Korçë (04.VIII.1969) [NHMT].

***Orthops (Montanorthops) montanus* (Schilling, 1837)**

Locations of records: Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Malësi e Madha (Qark Skodër).

Reference: Csiki, 1940 (as *Lygus montanus* Schill.): Malçija [Malësi e Madha] (27.VII.1918), Montes Korab (23.VII.1918, 1900–2100 m).

***Orthops (Orthops) basalis* (A. Costa, 1853)**

Locations of records: Mali me Gropë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Josifov, 1970 (as *Orthops basalis* (Costa, 1852) [sic]): Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Mali me Gropë (Dolinengebiet, 1350 m, 06.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Orthops (Orthops) campestris* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Lygus campestris* L.): Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Bizë bei Shënnergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Orthops (Orthops) kalmii* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Mirakë (Librazhd, Qark Elbasan); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Lygus kalmi* [sic] L.): Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (16.VII.1918, 1300 m). Mancini, 1953 (as *Lygus kalmi* [sic] L.): Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra). Josifov, 1970 (as *Orthops kalmi* [sic] (Linnaeus, 1758)): Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Bizë bei Shënnergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Apfelplantage, 350 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (*Orthops kalmi* [sic] L.): Korçë (02.VIII.1969); Tiranë (06.IX.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Orthops kalmi* [sic] Linnaeus, 1758): Petrelë (12.VI.2009); Mirakë (29.VII.2009). Halimi et al., 2020: Mali i Robit.

***Phytocoris (Exophytocoris) parvulus* Reuter, 1880**

Location of record: Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Oroshi.

***Phytocoris (Ktenocoris) austriacus* Wagner, 1954**

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Unterwuchs in Apfelplantage, 350 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Phytocoris (Ktenocoris) insignis* Reuter, 1876**

Locations of records: Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Papër (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Josifov, 1970: Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Luzernefeld, 300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Ibë (05.VII.1969); Korçë (05.VIII.1969); Tiranë (23.IX.1969). Halimi, 2011: Papër (09.VIII.2008). Halimi et al., 2020: Golem.

***Phytocoris (Ktenocoris) nowickyi* Fieber, 1870**

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI, ZISB].

***Phytocoris (Ktenocoris) ulmi* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Phytocoris Ulmi* [sic] L.): Oroshi. Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (05.VII.1918). Josifov, 1970: Poliçan westlich Tomor (Kulturland, 500 m, lux, 02.–12.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Phytocoris (Ktenocoris) varipes* Boheman, 1852**

Locations of records: Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Phytocoris varipes* Boh. ab. *leptocerus* Reut.): Kula Ljums (02.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953: Elbassan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

***Phytocoris (Leptophytocoris) ustulatus* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835**

Locations of records: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kodrat e Krastës (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953: Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Misja, 1970: Vorë (25.VI.1969); Ibë (05.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Petrelë (12.VI.2009); K. Krastës (24.VI.2008).

***Phytocoris (Phytocoris) pini* Kirschbaum, 1856**

Locations of records: Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Kodrat e Krastës (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905); Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Phytocoris Pini* [sic] Kirschb.): Oroshi. Halimi, 2011: K. Krastës (24.VI.2008). Halimi et al., 2020: Spille, Golem.

***Phytocoris (Phytocoris) thrax* Josifov, 1969**

Location of record: Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961) [SDEI].

[?] *Phytocoris (Stictophytocoris) meridionalis* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835

Location of record: ?

References: [?] Stichel, 1958: Albanien. [?] Josifov, 1986: Albanien [quoting from Stichel, 1958]. [?] Kerzhner & Josifov, 1999: Albania.

Pinalitus cervinus (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1841)

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Mali me Gropë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Josifov, 1970 (as *Orthops cervinus* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1842) [sic]): Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Mali me Gropë (Dolinengebiet, 1350 m, 06.VII.1961) [SDEI].

Polymerus (Poeciloscytus) cognatus (Fieber, 1858)

Locations of records: Gërmenj (Skrapar, Qark Berat); Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Kodrat e Krastës (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Peqin (Qark Elbasan); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Spille (Rrogzhinë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vodicë (Poliçan, Qark Berat).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Poeciloscytus cognatus* Fieb.): Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra). Misja, 1970: Tiranë (03.V.1969); Vlorë (25.V.1969). Halimi, 2011: Ndroq (06.V.2007); K. Krastës (24.VI.2008); Peqin (10.VIII.2008); Gërmenjë (18.IX.2009). Halimi et al., 2020: Spille, Golem. Halimi et al., 2024: Vodic (27.VII.2019) [NHMT].

Polymerus (Poeciloscytus) unifasciatus (Fabricius, 1794)

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Maja e Madhe (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali me Gropë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Maliq (Qark Korçë); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Poeciloscytus unifasciatus* F.): Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m). Mancini, 1953 (as *Poeciloscytus unifasciatus* F.): Pashtrik (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti (Westhang, 1100 m, 29.VI.1961); Mali me Gropë (Dolinengebiet, 1350 m, 06.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Maja e Madhe (1400–1789 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Geröllhang in Fagus-Abies-Wald in 1350 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1973: Maliq (30.VII.1970) [NHMT].

Polymerus (Poeciloscytus) vulneratus (Panzer, 1806)

Locations of records: Ardenica (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Darëzezë e Re (Qark Fier); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Labinot-Fushë (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Maliq (Qark Korçë); Patos (Qark Fier); Poshnjë (Dimal, Qark Berat); Roskovec (Qark Fier); Seman (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Spille (Rrogzhinë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Zharrëz (Patos, Qark Fier).

References: Josifov, 1970: Kulla e Lumës bei Kukësi (Luzerfeld, 300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Polymerus vulnetatus* [sic] Panz.): Maliq (04.VIII.1969); Tiranë (06.IX.1969). Halimi, 2011: L. Fushë (29.VII.2009). Halimi et al., 2018: Zharëza, Ardenica, Seman, Darëzezë, Patos, Roskovec (V.–IX.2015–2017). Halimi et al., 2020: Spille, Mali i Robit. Halimi et al., 2024: Poshnjë (27.V.2020) [NHMT].

Pseudomegacoelum beckeri* (Fieber, 1870) = *Megacoelum beckeri* (Fieber, 1870)*Location of record:** Gërmenj (Barmash, Kolonjë, Qark Korçë).**Reference:** Dhellemes, 2021h: District de Kolonjë, Albanie (01.X.2021; N 40.224993 E 20.658585 [Gërmenj]).***Rhabdomiris striatellus striatellus* (Fabricius, 1794)****Location of record:** Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastrë).**Reference:** Josifov, 1970 (as *Calocoris* (*Closterotomus*) *quadripunctatus* (Villers, 1789)): Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961) [SDEI].***Stenotus binotatus* (Fabricius, 1794)****Locations of records:** Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastrë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Zall-Bastar (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).**References:** Schumacher, 1914: Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Valona. Csiki, 1940: Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (16.VII.1918, 1300 m). Mancini, 1953: Elbassan, Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Thethi, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (21.V.1969); Ibë (05.VII.1969). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022) [PCMG].***Taylorilygus apicalis* (Fieber, 1861)****Locations of records:** Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).**References:** Mancini, 1953 (as *Lygus apicalis* var. *prasinus* Reut.): Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Misja, 1973: (as *Lygocoris* (*T.*) *pallidulus* Blanch.): Velipojë (16.VIII.1969); Vorë (27.VI.1969) [NHMT].

MIRIDAE Hahn, 1833: MIRINAE Hahn, 1833: STENODEMINI China, 1943

[8] *Acetropis* (*Acetropis*) *carinata* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1841)**Note:** The locality 'Janina' mentioned by Schumacher (1914) refers to the present-day city of Ioannina (Albanian Janinë, Janina), which belongs to Greece.***Acetropis* (*Acetropis*) *sinuata* Wagner, 1951****Locations of records:** Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).**Reference:** Josifov, 1970 (as *Acetropis josifovi* Wagner, 1967): Lurja östlich Kurbneshi (19.–24.VII.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–21.VI.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI].***Leptopterna dolabrata* (Linnaeus, 1758)****Locations of records:** Bicaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Krumë (Has, Qark Kukës); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Mali me Gropë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë).**References:** Schumacher, 1914 (as *Miris dolobratus* [sic] L.): Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Miris dolobratus* [sic] L.): Oroshi. Csiki,

1940 (as *Miris dolobratus* [sic] L. and *Miris dolobratus* [sic] ab. *aurantiacus* Reut.): Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (13.VII.1918, 1800 m, 16.VII.1918, 1300 m); Montes Korab (20.VII.1918, 26.VII.1918, 1800 m). Mancini, 1953 (as *Miris dolobratus* [sic] L.): Bicaj, Kruma (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Leptopterna dolobrata* [sic] (Linnaeus, 1758)): Mali me Gropë (Dolinengebiet, 1350 m, 06.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënnergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Leptopterna ferrugata* (Fallén, 1807)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Mali me Gropë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poliçan (Qark Berat).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Mali me Gropë (Dolinengebiet, 1350 m, 06.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënnergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Poliçan (17.VI.2022) [PCMG].

***Megaloceroea recticornis* (Geoffroy, 1785)**

Locations of records: Bicaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kodrat e Krastës (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Krrabë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kunora e Lunës (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkalla e Priskës (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Royer, 1924b (as *Megaloceroea linearis* Fuessl.): env. de Koritza [Korçë] (VII. 1 ♀). Csiki, 1940 (as *Megaloceroea linearis* Füssly): Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (14.VII.1918, 2000–2500 m, 16.VII.1918, 1200 m, 13.VII.1918, 1800 m). Mancini, 1953 (as *Megaloceroea linearis* Fuessl.): Bicaj (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti (Westhang, 1100 m, 29.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënnergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Knora e Lurës (1400–2000 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Sh. Priskë (30.VI.1961). Halimi, 2011 (*Megaloceroea recticornis* Geoffroy [sic], 1787 [sic]): Krrabë (24.VI.2008); K. Krastës (24.VI.2008).

***Myrmecoris gracilis* (R.F. Sahlberg, 1848)**

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Misja, 1973: Vlorë (23.V.1969) [NHMT].

***Notostira erratica* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Kodrat e Krastës (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Kolonjë (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Parku Kombëtar i Qafshtamës (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Tomorr-Tyrbja e Abaz Aliut (Skrapar, Qark Berat).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Notostira erratica* L. and *Notostira erratica* ab. *ancestralis* Reut.): Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (16.VII.1918, 1300 m); Kula Ljums (02.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953: Pashtrik (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970: Tomor, Kloster Abbas Ali (1800 m, 08.–10.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Tiranë (06.IX.1969); Qafë-Shtamë (04.X.1969). Halimi, 2011: K. Krastës (24.VI.2008); Kolonjë (24.IX.2008).

Note: Horváth (1916) mentions a record from ‘Shar Dagħ (Ljuboten)’. This refers to the mountain range of Šar Panina-Ljuboten between Kosovo and North Macedonia.

Stenodema (Brachytropis) calcarata (Fallén, 1807)

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Divjakë (Qark Fier); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Hamallaj (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kavajë (Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lybeshë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Patos (Qark Fier); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkozet (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër); Uznovë (Berat, Qark Berat).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Stenodema calcaratum* [sic] var. *virescens* Fieb. and *Stenodema calcaratum* [sic] var. *pallescens* Reut.): Qukes, Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Stenodema (Brachytropis) calcaratum* [sic] (Fallén, 1807)): Borshi südlich Vlora (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lura [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma (250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Stenodema calcaratum* [sic] Fall.): Kavajë (14.VIII.1969); Durrës (18.VII.1969); Tiranë (06.IX.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Stenodema calcaratum* [sic] Fallén, 1807): Golem (19.VII.2009); Shkozet (24.IX.2008); Hamallaj (14.VIII.2008), Divjakë (22.IX.2008). Halimi et al., 2018 (as *Stenodema calcaratum* [sic] Fllen [sic], 1809): Patos (V.–IX.2015–2017). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017). Halimi et al., 2024: Uznov (20.VII.2019); Lybesh (03.IX.2019) [NHMT].

Stenodema (Stenodema) holsata (Fabricius, 1787)

Locations of records: Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Stenodema holsatum* [sic] F.): Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m). Mancini, 1953 (as *Stenodema holsatum* [sic] F.): Pashtrik (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918). Halimi, 2011 (as *Stenodema holstatum* [sic] Fabricius, 1787): Dajt (18.IX.2007).

Stenodema (Stenodema) laevigata (Linnaeus, 1758)

Locations of records: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Këlcyrë (Qark Gjirokastër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Parku Kombëtar i Qafshamës (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Prenisht (Pogradec, Qark Korçë); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Royer, 1924b: Prënist (V. 1 ♀). Csiki, 1940 (as *Stenodema laevigatum* [sic] L.): Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (16.VII.1918, 1300 m). Mancini, 1953 (as *Stenodema laevigatum* [sic] L.): Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Stenodema (Stenodema) laevigatum* (Linnaeus, 1758)): Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Stenodema laevigatum* [sic] L.): Këlcyrë (28.X.1968); Qafë-Shtamë (04.X.1969). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Poliçan (17.VI.2022) [PCMG].

Note: Horváth (1916) mentions a record from ‘Shar Dagħ (Ljuboten)’. This refers to the mountain range of Šar Panina-Ljuboten between Kosovo and North Macedonia.

Stenodema (Stenodema) sericans (Fieber, 1861)

Locations of records: Fusha e Rudnicës (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Cukali. Mancini, 1953: Fusa Rudnices (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970: Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961) [SDEI].

[?] *Stenodema (Stenodema) turanica* Reuter, 1904

Location of record: Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Josifov, 1970 (as *Stenodema (Stenodema) virens turanicum* Reuter, 1904): Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961) [SDEI].

Note: This record may have been overlooked or revised by Josifov (1986) and Kerzhner & Josifov (1999).

Stenodema (Stenodema) virens (Linnaeus, 1767)

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Kunora e Lunës (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Ploshtan (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Tomorr-Tyrbja e Abaz Aliut (Skrapar, Qark Berat).

References: Csiki, 1940: Ploštan (29.VII.1918); Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m). Josifov, 1970 (as *Stenodema (Stenodema) virens virens* (Linnaeus, 1767)): Tomor, Kloster Abbas Ali (1800 m, 08.–10.VI.1961); Bizë bei Shëngjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Geröllhang in Fagus-Abies-Wald in 1350 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Knora e Lurës (1400–2000 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI].

Teratocoris antennatus (Boheman, 1852)

Location of record: Shëngjin (Qark Lezhë).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Shen Gjin (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

Trigonotylus caelestialium (Kirkaldy, 1902)

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: van der Heyden, 2017e (as *Trygonotylus* [sic] *caelestialium* (Kirkaldy, 1902)): Vlorë (phot. Aleksander Golemaj, 22.VII.2017).

Trigonotylus pulchellus (Hahn, 1834)

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan).

References: Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918, 05.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953: Qukes, Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Unterwuchs in Apfelplantage, 350 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI].

Trigonotylus ruficornis (Geoffroy, 1785)

Locations of records: Bardhor (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Divjakë (Qark Fier); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kavajë (Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Bizë bei Shëngjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Unterwuchs in Apfelplantage, 350 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei

Kukësi (Luzernefeld, 300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (29.V.1969); Ibë (05.VII.1969); Kavajë (14.VII.1969); Korçë (02.VIII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Bardhore (08.VI.2009); Divjakë (22.IX.2008).

MIRIDAE Hahn, 1833 MIRINAE Hahn, 1833: HERDONINI Distant, 1904

***Camponotidea saundersi* (Puton, 1874)**

Locations of records: Durrës (Qark Durrës); Koplik (Malësi e Madha, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Camponotidea Saundersi* [sic] Put.): Valona. Mancini, 1953: Durrec (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918); Kopliku (leg. Capra).

MIRIDAE Hahn, 1833: ORTHOTYLINAE Van Duzee, 1916: HALTICINI A. Costa, 1853

[?] *Barbarosia punctulata* (Reuter, 1901)

Locations of records: [?] Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); [?] Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); [?] Spille (Rrogzhinë, Qark Tiranë).

References: [?] Misja, 1973 (as *Halticidae* [sic] *punctulata* Reut.): Ibë (05.VII.1969) [NHMT]. [?] Halimi et al., 2020 (as *Halticidae* [sic] *punctulata* Reuter, 1901): Spille, Golem.

Note: This species is only known from the southern European part of Russia and Kazakhstan. Its occurrence in Albania is unlikely (Aukema et al., 2013).

***Euryopicoris nitidus* (Meyer-Dür, 1843)**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës); Zvërnec (Vlorë; Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums, Pashtrik (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zvërnec (14.VI.2022) [PCMG].

***Halticus apterus apterus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

Reference: Josifov, 1970 (as *Halticus apterus* (Linnaeus, 1758)): Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Unterwuchs in Apfelplantage, 350 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI].

***Halticus luteicollis* (Panzer, 1804)**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (05.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953: Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Halticus luteicollis* (Panzer, 1805) [sic]): Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Halticus macrocephalus* Fieber, 1858**

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Horváth, 1916: Valona.

***Halticus pusillus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (04.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953: Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

***Halticus saltator* (Geoffroy, 1785)**

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

References: Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (05.VII.1918). Josifov, 1970: Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI].

[?] *Orthocephalus arnoldii* (V.G. Putshkov, 1961)

Locations of records: [?] Divjakë (Qark Fier); [?] Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); [?] Kavajë (Qark Tiranë); [?] Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); [?] Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë).

References: [?] Misja, 1973 (*Anapomella arnoldi* [sic] Putshk.): Kavajë (26.VI.1970) [NHMT]. [?] Halimi, 2011 (*Anapomella arnoldii* Putshkov, 1961): Golem (19.VII.2009); M. Robit (03.VIII.2008); Divjakë (22.IX.2008). [?] Halimi et al., 2020 (*Anapomella arnoldii* V.G. Putshkov, 1961): Spille, Mali i Robit.

Note: This species is known only from the southern European part of Russia, Ukraine, and Kazakhstan. Its occurrence in Albania is unlikely (Aukema et al., 2013).

[x] *Orthocephalus bivittatus* Fieber, 1864

Note: Aukema et al. (2013) cite Misja (1973), who in turn refers to Csiki (1940). However, there it reads 'İpek'. The place 'İpek' (Turkish) is now called Pejë, Peja (Albanian) or Peć (Serbo-Croatian) and is located in present-day Kosovo.

***Orthocephalus brevis* (Panzer, 1798)**

Locations of records: Krrabë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Halimi, 2011: Kërrabë (24.VI.2008, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂). Halimi et al., 2020: Spille, Mali i Robit.

Note: The distribution of this Euro-Siberian species extends to the Mediterranean region. Its presence in Albania is plausible.

***Orthocephalus proserpinae* (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)**

Locations of records: Durrës (Qark Durrës); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Orthocephalus coracinus* Put.): Durrec (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

[?] *Orthocephalus putshkovi* Namyatova & Konstantinov, 2009

Locations of records: [?] Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); [?] Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); [?] Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); [?] Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); [?] Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: [?] Misja, 1970 (as *Piezocranum medvedevi* Putschk.): Vlorë (25.V.1969); Ibë (05.VII.1969). [?] Halimi, 2011 (as *Piezocranum medvedevi* V.G. Putshkov, 1961): Dajt (18.IX.2007); Petrëllë (12.VI.2009). [?] Halimi et al., 2020 (as *Piezocranum medvedevi* V.G. Putshkov, 1961): Mali i Robit.

Note: The above records seem questionable. This species was previously only known

from Kazakhstan (Aukema et al., 2013).

***Orthocephalus saltator* (Hahn, 1835)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Mali me Gropë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Zall-Bastar (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Orthocephalus saltator* Hahn and *O. Ferrarii* [sic] Reut.): Kula Ljums (02.VII.1918), Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (16.VII.1918, 1300 m). Mancini, 1953 (as *Orthocephalus saltator* Hhn. and *O. ferrarii* Reut.): Durrec, Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Orthocephalus saltator* (Hahn, 1835) and *O. ferrarii* Reuter, 1891): Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Mali me Gropë (Dolinengebiet, 1350 m, 06.VII.1961); Tirana (09.–12.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (Kulturland, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022) [PCMG].

Note: Mancini (1953) also mentions ‘Uskub’ as location of record. Uskub is the Turkish name for Skopje, today's capital of North Macedonia.

***Orthocephalus vittipennis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

***Piezocranum simulans* Horváth, 1877**

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Misja, 1970: Vlorë (24.V.1969).

***Strongylocoris leucocephalus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër).

References: Csiki, 1940: Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m). Josifov, 1970: Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Strongylocoris niger* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

Location of record: Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961) [SDEI].

MIRIDAE Hahn, 1833: ORTHOTYLINAE Van Duzee, 1916: ORTHOTYLINI Van Duzee, 1916

***Globiceps (Globiceps) sphaegiformis* (Rossi, 1790)**

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Globiceps sphaegiformis* [sic] Rossi): Kula Ljums (04.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953 (as *Globiceps sphaegiformis* [sic] Rossi): Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

Globiceps (Kelidocoris) flavomaculatus* (Fabricius, 1794)*Location of record:** Korçë (Qark Korçë).**Reference:** Misja, 1973 (as *Globiceps (P) flavomaculatus* Deg. [sic]): Korçë (03.VIII.1969) [NHMT].***Globiceps (Kelidocoris) fulvicollis* Jakovlev, 1877****Locations of records:** Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).**References:** Mancini, 1953 (as *Globiceps cruciatus* Reut.): Pashtrik (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Globiceps (Paraglobiceps) fulvicollis cruciatus* Reuter, 1879): Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI].***Globiceps (Kelidocoris) juniperi* Reuter, 1902****Location of record:** Zall-Bastar, Mali i Dajtit, Shkalla e Tujanit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).**Reference:** Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022) [PCMG].***Heterocordylus (Heterocordylus) genistae* (Scopoli, 1763)****Location of record:** Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).**Reference:** Josifov, 1970: Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961) [SDEI].***Heterocordylus (Heterocordylus) tumidicornis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)****Location of record:** Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).**Reference:** Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].***Heterotoma merioptera* (Scopoli, 1763)****Locations of records:** Dardhë (Korçë, Qark Korçë); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër).**References:** Schumacher, 1914 (as *Heterotoma meriopterum* [sic] Scop.): Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Cukali. Mancini, 1953 (as *Heterotoma meriopterum* [sic] Scop.): Elbassan, Dardha (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].[8] *Heterotoma planicornis* (Pallas, 1772)**Note:** Aukema et al. (2013) state that the Albanian record should be checked. This record is based on an error. Misja (1973, p. 173) quotes ‘Dr. H. Géza’, p. 141 with ‘*Heterotoma (Capsus) planicorne* Pall.’. This is undoubtedly Horváth (1916), who does not list this species but ‘*Heterotoma meriopterum* Scop.’ from the locality ‘Cukali’ (see above).[?] *Orthotylus (Melanotrichus) palustris* Reuter, 1888**Location of record:** ?**Reference:** [?] Stichel, 1958: Albanien.[?] *Orthotylus (Orthotylus) interpositus* Schmidt, 1938**Location of record:** ?**Reference:** [?] Stichel, 1958: Albanien.***Orthotylus (Orthotylus) marginalis* Reuter, 1883**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Shijon (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan).

References: Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (08.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953: Shingjonas [Shijon] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

***Platycranus (Platycranus) erberi* Fieber, 1870**

Location of record: Elbasan (Qark Elbasan).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Elbasan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

[?] *Reuteria marqueti* Puton, 1875

Location of record: ?

Reference: [?] Stichel, 1958: Albanien.

MIRIDAE Hahn, 1833: PHYLINAE Douglas & Scott, 1865: PILOPHORINI Douglas & Scott, 1865

***Pilophorus cinnamopterus* (Kirschbaum, 1856)**

Locations of records: Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Parku Kombëtar i Qafshamës (Krujë, Qark Durrës).

References: Misja, 1973: Qafë Shamtë (04.X.1969) [NHMT]. Halimi, 2011: Dajt (18.IX.2007).

***Pilophorus confusus* (Kirschbaum, 1856)**

Locations of records: Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Oroshi. Mancini, 1953: Petrela, Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

***Pilophorus perplexus* Douglas & Scott, 1875**

Location of record: Peshkopi (Dibër, Qark Dibër).

Reference: Misja, 1973: Peshkopi (14.IX.1970) [NHMT].

MIRIDAE Hahn, 1833: PHYLINAE Douglas & Scott, 1865: HALODAPINI Van Duzee, 1916

***Cremnocephalus albolineatus* Reuter, 1875**

Location of record: Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë).

Reference: Horváth, 1916: Oroshi.

Note: In 1970, Josifov assumed that all records of this species in the Balkans referred to the species *Cremnocephalus alpestris* Wagner, 1941. However, in later publications (Josifov, 1986; Kerzhner & Josifov, 1999) *Cremnocephalus albolineatus* Reuter, 1875 was listed for Albania.

[?] *Cremnocephalus alpestris* Wagner, 1941

Note: See note on *Cremnocephalus albolineatus* Reuter, 1875.

***Systemonotus triguttatus* (Linnaeus, 1767)**

Locations of records: Bicaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Durrës (Qark Durrës).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Durrec, Bicaj (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

MIRIDAE Hahn, 1833: PHYLINAE Douglas & Scott, 1865: PHYLINI Douglas & Scott, 1865

Adelphophylus balcanicus* (Kormilev, 1939)*Location of record:** Mali me Gropë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).**Reference:** Josifov, 1970: Mali me Gropë (Rotbuchenbestand mit angrenzender Weide, 1200 m, 03.–08.VII.1961) [SDEI].***Amblytylus brevicollis* Fieber, 1858****Location of record:** Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë).**Reference:** Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlorë (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI].***Amblytylus concolor* Jakovlev, 1877****Locations of records:** Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan).**References:** Csiki, 1940 (as *Macrotylus testaceus* Reut.): Kulla Ljums (02.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953 (as *Macrotylus testaceus* Reut.): Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941).***Amblytylus nasutus* (Kirschbaum, 1856)****Location of record:** Bicaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës).**Reference:** Mancini, 1953 (as *Amblytylus nasutus* [sic] Kbn): Bicaj (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].***Camptotylus (Kelidocoris) reuteri* Jakovlev, 1881****Location of record:** Zvërnec, Manasteri i Shën Mërisë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).**Reference:** Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zvërnec (14.VI.2022) [PCMG].[&] *Campylomma verbasci* (Meyer-Dür, 1843)**Note:** Aukema et al. (2013) cite Misja (1973), who in turn refers to Csiki (1940). There, 'Ipek' and 'Banica (propre Ipek)' are mentioned as localities. 'Ipek' (Turkish) is now Pejë, Peja (Albanian) or Peć (Serbo-Croatian). 'Banica' is Banicë, Banica (Albanian) or Banjica (Serbo-Croatian). Both are located in present-day Kosovo.***Chlamydatus (Chlamydatus) saltitans* (Fallén, 1807)****Location of record:** Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës).**Reference:** Csiki, 1940: Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (19.VII.1917, 1900–2300 m, 15.VII.1918, 1650 m).***Conostethus venustus venustus* (Fieber, 1858)****Location of record:** Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier).**Reference:** Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).***Cremnorhinus basalis* Reuter, 1880****Locations of records:** Berat (Qark Berat); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).**References:** Schumacher, 1914 (as *Cremnorhinus* [sic] *basalis* Reut.): Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Cremnorhinus basalis* Fieb. [sic]): Berat, Valona. Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).***Criocoris crassicornis* (Hahn, 1834)****Locations of records:** Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).**Reference:** Josifov, 1970: Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI].

[?] *Criocoris nigripes* Fieber, 1861

Location of record: [?] Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: [?] Josifov, 1970: Dajti (Westhang, 1100 m, 29.VI.1961) [SDEI].

Note: Josifov (1970, 1986) identified the Albanian specimens with reservations, as all the specimens he had were missing extremities.

***Criocoris sulcicornis* (Kirschbaum, 1856)**

Location of record: Maja e Madhe (Dibër, Qark Dibër).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Maja e Madhe (1400–1789 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Europiella alpina* (Reuter, 1875)**

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Csiki, 1940 (as *Plagiognathus alpinus* Reut.): Kula Ljums (05.VII.1918).

***Europiella artemisiae* (Becker, 1864)**

Location of record: Maja e Madhe (Dibër, Qark Dibër).

Reference: Josifov, 1970 (as *Plagiognathus (Poliopterus) gracilis* Wagner, 1956): Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Maja e Madhe (1400–1789 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Harpocera hellenica* Reuter, 1876**

Location of record: Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).

Reference: Horváth, 1916: Skutari [Shkodër].

***Heterocapillus tigrisipes* (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)**

Locations of records: Gërmenj (Skrapar, Qark Berat); Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Lukovë (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Atractotomus tigrisipes* Muls.): Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Lukova nördlich Saranda (250 m, 24.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea*-Macchie, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (23.V.1969); Ibë (01.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Ibë (26.VII.2008); M. Robit (03.VIII.2008); Gërmenjë (18.IX.2009). Halimi et al., 2020: Mali i Robit, Golem.

***Hoplomachus thunbergii* (Fallén, 1807)**

Location of record: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Josifov, 1970 (as *Hoplomachus thunbergi* [sic] (Fallén, 1807)): Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Icodema infusata* (Fieber, 1861)**

Location of record: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Josifov, 1970 (*Icodema infusatum* [sic] (Fieber, 1861)): Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI].

***Lopus decolor* (Fallén, 1807)**

Locations of records: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Papër (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953: Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Misja, 1970: Ibë (05.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Petrelë (12.VI.2009); Ndroq (06.V.2009); Papër (09.VIII.2008). Halimi et al., 2020: Spille, Mali i Robit.

Macrotylus (Alloeonycha) atricapillus (Scott, 1872)

Locations of records: Divjakë (Qark Fier); Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Kavajë (Qark Tiranë); Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Misja, 1973: Kavajë (18.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Golem (03.VIII.2008); Divjakë (22.IX.2008) [NHMT]. Halimi et al., 2020 (as *Macrolophus* [sic; *Macrotylus*] *atricapillus* Scott, 1872): Mali i Robit, Golem.

Macrotylus (Alloeonycha) paykullii (Fallén, 1807)

Locations of records: Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastrë).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Macrotylus interpositus* Wagn.): Elbassan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Macrotylus interpositus* Wagner, 1951): Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961) [SDEI].

Megalocoleus tanaceti (Fallén, 1807)

Locations of records: Korçë (Qark Korçë); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Royer, 1924b (as *Megalocoleus pilosus* Schrk): env. de Koritza [Korçë] (VI. 1♀). Josifov, 1970 (as *Megalocoleus pilosus* (Schrank, 1801)): Mali me Gropë, Livadhët e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961) [SDEI].

Monosynamma bohemanni (Fallén, 1829)

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Csiki, 1940 (as *Microsynamma Bohemani* [sic] Fall. and *Microsynamma nigrifulva* Zett.): Kula Ljums (05.VII.1918, 08.VII.1918).

Oncotylus (Cylindromelus) setulosus (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1837)

Locations of records: Labinot-Fushë (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Maliq (Qark Korçë).

References: Misja, 1970: Maliq (04.VIII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Labinot (29.VII.2009).

Oncotylus (Oncotylus) punctipes Reuter, 1875

Locations of records: Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë); Sukth (Durrës, Qark Durrës).

References: Misja, 1973: Vorë (27.VI.1969) [NHMT]. Halimi, 2011: Farkë (13.VII.2009); Sukth (22.VI.2009).

Oncotylus (Oncotylus) viridiflavus viridiflavus (Goeze, 1778)

Location of record: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Misja, 1970 (as *Oncotylus viridiflavus* Gz.): Ibë (05.VII.1969).

[?] *Opisthotaenia (Opisthotaenia) fulvipes* Reuter, 1901

Location of record: [?] Korçë (Qark Korçë).

Reference: [?] Kment et al., 2005: Koriç env. (13.VI.1994, 1 ♂, O. Hovorka lgt., J. Bryja det., JBSC).

Note: We could not find a place named 'Koriç' in Albania (Kment et al., 2005). Perhaps Korçë is meant.

Orthonotus cylindricollis (A. Costa, 1853)

Location of record: Mirditë (Qark Lezhë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Byrsoptera cylindricollis* Costa): Merdita (leg. Adolph Winneguth, 1906, 1908) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Byrsoptera cylindricollis*

Costa): Merdita.

***Pachyxyphus lineellus* (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)**

Locations of records: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Josifov, 1970: Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea*-Macchie, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (Kulturland, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (23.–27.V.1969).

***Phoenicocoris modestus* (Meyer-Dür, 1843)**

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Misja, 1973: Vlorë (23.[?].1969) [NHMT].

***Phylus (Phylus) coryli* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Krumë (Has, Qark Kukës); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Kruma, Kula Ljums, Pashtrik (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

Notes: The locality ‘Janina’ mentioned by Schumacher (1914) refers to the present-day city of Ioannina (Albanian: Janinë, Janina) in Greece. Horváth (1916) mentions a record from ‘Shar Dagħ (Ljuboten)’. This refers to the mountain range of Šar Panina-Ljuboten between Kosovo and North Macedonia.

***Plagiognathus arbustorum arbustorum* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Plagiognathus arbustorum* var. *hortensis* Mey. D.): Kula Ljums (05.VII.1918); Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (13.VII.1918, 1000–1600 m, 1800 m). Josifov, 1970 (*Plagiognathus* (as *Plagiognathus*) *arbustorum* (Fabricius, 1794)): Bizë bei Shënjergji (Rotbuchenwald, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI].

***Plagiognathus bipunctatus bipunctatus* Reuter, 1883**

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Josifov, 1970 (as *Plagiognathus (Plagiognathus) bipunctatus* Reuter, 1883): Kulla e Lumës bei Kukësi (Luzernefeld, 300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Plagiognathus chrysanthemi* Wolff, 1804**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Plagiognathus chrysanthemi* Fieb. [sic] and *P. cunctator* Horv.): Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (16.VII.1918, 1300 m); Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m). Josifov, 1970 (*Plagiognathus (Plagiognathus) chrysanthemi* (Wolff, 1804) [sic] and *P. cunctator* Horváth, 1887): Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Halimi, 2011 (as *Plagiognathus cunctator* Horváth, 1887): Dajt (18.IX.2007).

***Plagiognathus fulvipennis* Kirschbaum, 1856**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kodrat e Krastës (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Zall-Bastar (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Plagiognathus fulvipennis* var. *annulatus* Stich.); Kula Ljums (02.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953 (as *Plagiognathus fulvipennis* Kbm., *P. fulvipennis* var. *circumcincta* Stich., *P. fulvipennis* var. *annulata* Stich, and *P. fulvipennis* var. *diversicornis* Reut.): Elbassan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Plagiognathuis* [sic] (*Plagiognathus*) *fulvipennis* (Kirschbaum, 1856)): Borshi südlich Vlora (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1973: [?; illegible in our copy] [NHMT]. Halimi, 2011: Petrelë (12.VI.2009); K. Krastës (24.VI.2008). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022) [PCMG].

***Psallus (Hylopsallus) variabilis* (Fallén, 1807)**

Location of record: Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

***Psallus (Phylidea) ocularis* (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)**

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Mancini, 1953 (as *Stenarus* [sic] *maculipes* Reut): Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

Note: Misja (1973) quotes Ciski (1940) with Albanian records of ‘*Sthenarus maculipes* Reut.’. However, ‘Rudnik’ and ‘İpek’ are mentioned there. ‘Rudnik’ may refer to the mountain range Rudnik Raduša located in North Macedonia. ‘İpek’ (Turkish) is now Pejë, Peja (Albanian) or Peć (Serbo-Croatian), located in Western Kosovo.

***Psallus (Psallus) varians varians* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1841)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Psallus varians* H. Sch.): Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Psallus varians* H.–Sch.): Oroshi. Josifov, 1970 (as *Psallus (Psallus) varians* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1842) [sic]): Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Bizë bei Shënnergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, lux, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Tinicephalus (Tinicephalus) hortulanus* (Meyer-Dür, 1843)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Maja e Madhe (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënnergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Maja e Madhe (1400–1789 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Tuponia (Chlorotuponia) hippophaes* (Fieber, 1861)**

Locations of records: Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Zvërnec, Manasteri i Shën Mërisë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Tuponia michalki* Wagn.): Scutari [Shkodër] (leg.

Tamanini, 194). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zvërnec (14.VI.2022) [PCMG].

[?] *Tuponia (Tuponia) tamarisci* (Perris, 1857)

Location of record: [?] Elbasan (Qark Elbasan).

Reference: [?] Mancini, 1953 (as *Tuponia tamaricis* [sic] Perr.): Elbassan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

Note: The occurrence of this species on the Balkan Peninsula is considered unlikely by Josifov (1970, 1986).

THAUMASTOCORIDAE Kirkaldy, 1908: THAUMASTOCORINAE Kirkaldy, 1908

***Thaumastocoris peregrinus* Carpintero & Dellapé, 2006**

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: van der Heyden, 2017d: Vlorë (phot. Aleksander Golemaj, 06.XII.2016).

Superfamily: CIMICOIDEA Latreille, 1802

NABIDAE A. Costa, 1853: PROSTEMMATINAE Reuter, 1890: PROSTEMMATINI Reuter, 1890

***Alloeorhynchus (Alloeorhynchus) flavipes* (Fieber, 1836)**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Velipoja. Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (08.VII.1918) [HNHM].

[?] *Prostemma (Prostemma) aeneicolle* Stein, 1857

Location of record: ?

References: [?] Stichel, 1960: Albanien. [?] Josifov, 1986: Albanien. [?] Kerzhner, 1996: Albania.

Note: Josifov (1986) and Kerzhner (1996) include Albania in the distribution range, possibly with reference to Stichel (1960). More detailed information could not be obtained.

***Prostemma (Prostemma) guttula guttula* (Fabricius, 1787)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Ploshtan (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Ura Lapaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Prostemma guttula* F.): Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Nabis guttula* Fabr.): Berat, Valona. Csiki, 1940 (as *Prostemma guttula* F.): Lušna: Ura i Lopez [Ura Lapaj] (21.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Prostemma guttula* F.): Plostan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

***Prostemma (Prostemma) sanguineum* (Rossi, 1790)**

Locations of records: Korçë (Qark Korçë); Nangë (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Ura Lapaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Skutari [Shkodër] (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905); Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck); Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Nabis sanguineus* Rossi): Skutari [Shkodër], Oroshi, Velipoja. Royer, 1924a (as *Nabis sanguineus* Rossi): env. de Koritza [Korçë] (VI, 1 ♀). Csiki, 1940: Lušna: Ura i Lopez [Ura Lapaj] (21.VII.1918); Nangat (30.VII.1918) [HNHM].

NABIDAE A. Costa, 1853: NABINAE A. Costa, 1853: NABINI A. Costa, 1853

***Himacerus (Aptus) mirmicoides* (O. Costa, 1834)**

Locations of records: Kaninë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Peshkopi (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Rrapshë (Malësi e Madha, Qark Shkodër); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Reduviolus lativentris* Boh.): Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck); Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Reduviolus myrmecoides* [sic] Costa): Cukali, Oroshi, Valona, Kanina. Mancini, 1953 (as *Nabis mirmecoides* [sic] Costa): Piskopeja, Rapsa (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) (NHMW); Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Aptus mirmicoides* (O. Costa, 1834)): Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Unterwuchs in Apfelpflanze, 350 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1973 (as *Aptus mirmicoides* Costa): Korçë (02.VIII.1969) [NHMT].

[?] *Himacerus (Stalia) boops* (Schiodte, 1870)

Location of record: [?] Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër).

Reference: [?] Csiki, 1940 (*Nabis boops* Schiodte): Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m) [HNHM].

Note: This species is mainly distributed from Central Europe to Southern Scandinavia. Josifov (1970, 1986) doubts its presence on the Balkan Peninsula.

***Nabis (Aspilaspis) viridulus* Spinola, 1837**

Locations of records: Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Halimi, 2011 (as *Aspilaspis viridis pallidus* Brullè [sic]): Vorë (24.V.2009). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

***Nabis (Dolichonabis) limbatus* Dahlbom, 1851**

Locations of records: Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Zharrëz (Patos, Qark Fier).

References: Halimi, 2011 (as *Dolichonabis limbatus* Dahlbom, 1851): Petrelë (12.VI.2009). Halimi et al., 2018 (as *Dolichonabis limbatus* Dahlbohm, 1850 [sic]): Zharëza (V.–IX.2015–2017).

***Nabis (Limnonabis) lineatus* Dahlbom, 1851**

Locations of records: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Lezhë (Qark Lezhë); Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Misja, 1970 (as *Dolichonabis lineatus* Dhlb.): Lezhë (04.VII.1968); Vorë (10.X.1968); Tiranë (26.IV.1968). Halimi, 2011 (as *Dolichonabis lineatus* Dahlbom, 1851): Ibë (26.VII.2008); Spille (27.IX.2007).

***Nabis (Nabicula) flavomarginatus* Scholtz, 1847**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Josifov, 1970 (as *Dolichonabis flavomarginatus* (Scholtz, 1847) [sic]): Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Halimi, 2011: Dajt (25.VI.2008); Vorë (24.V.2008).

[?] *Nabis (Nabis) fesus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Locations of records: [?] Bicaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); [?] Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); [?] Malësi e Madha (Qark Shkodër); [?] Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); [?] Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); [?] Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); [?] Vlorë (Qark Vlorë)

References: [?] Schumacher, 1914 (*Reduviolus fesus* L.): Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. [?] Horváth, 1916 (Nabididae [Distant, 1904]: *Reduviolus fesus* L.):

Oroshi, Valona. [?] Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (05.VII.1918); Malçija [Malësi e Madha] (29.VII.1918) [HNHM]. [?] Mancini, 1953: Bicaj (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra); Petrela, Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

Note: Josifov (1970) suggests that all records mentioned above are of *Nabis pseudoferus* Remane, 1949, but Kerzhner (1996) included Albania in his distribution list of *N. ferus*.

[?] *Nabis (Nabis) palifer* Seidenstücker, 1954

Note: Kerzhner (1996) mentions Albania in his distribution list. No primary literature could be found.

***Nabis (Nabis) pseudoferus pseudoferus* Remane, 1949**

Locations of records: Gllavë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastrë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lezhë (Qark Lezhë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkozë (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Zall-Bastar (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Josifov, 1970 (as *Nabis pseudoferus* Remane, 1949): Dajti (Westhang, 1100 m, 29.VI.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Kulla e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Nabis pseudoferus* Rem.): Ndroq (07.V.1968); Lezhë (04.VII.1968); Gllavë (30.X.1968); Vlorë (16.–28.V.1969); Korçë (02.–05.VIII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Dajt (25.VI.2008, 18.IX.2007); Shkozë (24.IX.2008); M. Robit (03.VIII.2008). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022) [PCMG].

Note: See note on *Nabis (Nabis) ferus* (Linnaeus, 1758).

***Nabis (Nabis) punctatus punctatus* A. Costa, 1847**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Josifov, 1970 (as *Nabis feroides* Remane, 1953): Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Kulla e Lumës bei Kukësi (Luzernefeld, 300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Nabis (Nabis) rugosus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Hoçisht (Devoll, Qark Korçë); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës); Prenishtë (Pogradec, Qark Korçë); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Tomorr-Tyrbja e Abaz Aliut (Skrapar, Qark Berat); Vermosh (Malësi e Madha, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Reduviolus rugosus* L.): Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Reduviolus rugosus* L.): Cukali. Royer, 1924a (as *Reduviolus rugosus* L.): Prënisti (1.000 m, V, 1 ♂). Mancini, 1953: Vermosa, Pashtrik (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970: Tomor, Kloster Abbas Ali (1800 m, 08.–10.VI.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Rotbuchenwald, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Hoçisht (07.IX.2022) [PCMG].

Note: Horváth (1916) also mentions an Albanian record from ‘Shar Dagh (Ljuboten)’. This refers to the mountain range of Šar Panina-Ljuboten between Kosovo and North Macedonia.

***Nabis (Tropiconabis) capsiformis* Germar, 1838**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Josifov, 1970 (as *Nabis capsiformis* Germar, 1837 [sic]): Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI]. Halimi, 2011: Spille (27.IX.2007).

ANTHOCORIDAE Fieber, 1836: ANTHOCORINAE Fieber, 1836: ANTHOCORINI Fieber, 1836

***Acompocoris pygmaeus* (Fallén, 1807)**

Location of record: Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Anthocoris gallarumulmi* (De Geer, 1773)**

Locations of records: Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Anthocoris gallarum-ulmi* [sic] Geer [sic]): Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Anthocoris gallarum ulmi* [sic] Deg.): Oroshi. Misja, 1973: Tiranë (22.IV.1970) [NHMT].

***Anthocoris nemoralis* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Kepi i Rodonit (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Shën Thanas (Voskopojë, Qark Korçë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (*Anthocoris nemoralis* Fabr. var. *superbus* Westh.): Shen Thanas. Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI]. Halimi, 2011: K. Rodonit (21.V.2007).

***Anthocoris nemorum* (Linnaeus, 1761)**

Locations of records: Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vermosh (Malësi e Madha, Qark Shkodër).

References: Mancini, 1953: Vermosa (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Halimi, 2011: Dajt (18.IX.2007).

***Anthocoris visci* Douglas, 1889**

Location of record: Butrint (Sarandë, Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Misja, 1973: Butrint (30.X.1970) [NHMT].

ANTHOCORIDAE Fieber, 1836: ANTHOCORINAE Fieber, 1836: ORIINI Carayon, 1958

***Orius (Heterorius) horvathi* (Reuter, 1884)**

Location of record: Peshkopi (Dibër, Qark Dibër).

Reference: Misja, 1973: Peshkopi (14.IX.1970) [NHMT].

***Orius (Heterorius) minutus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Mali i Shkëlzenit (Tropojë, Qark Kukës); Ura i Vezirit (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Triphleps minuta* L.): Vezir cupr. (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Triphleps minuta* L.): Vezir çuprija ad fluvium Drini barz. Csiki, 1940: Montes Skölsen (02.VII.1917, 1750–2030 m); Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (13.VII.1918, 1000–1600 m). Josifov, 1970: Kulla e Lumës bei Kukësi (Luzernefeld, 300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Kulla e Lumës bei Kukësi (Unterwuchs in Apfelplantage, 350 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Orius (Orius) laevigatus laevigatus* (Fieber, 1860)**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Orius laevigatus* Fieb.): Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Orius (Orius) laevigatus* (Fieber, 1860)): Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI].

***Orius (Orius) niger* (Wolff, 1811)**

Locations of records: Bicaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Orius niger* Wolff ab. *Ulrichi* [sic] Fieb.): Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953: Bicaj (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Orius (Orius) niger* Wolff, 1804 [sic]): Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1973: Tiranë (II–III.1970) [NHMT].

ANTHOCORIDAE Fieber, 1836: LYCTOCORINAE Reuter, 1884: LYCTOCORINI Reuter, 1884

***Lyctocoris (Lyctocoris) campestris* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Velipoja. Josifov, 1970: Kulla e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI].

ANTHOCORIDAE Fieber, 1836: LYCTOCORINAE Reuter, 1884: SCOLOPINI Carayon, 1954

***Scoloposcelis pulchella angusta* Reuter, 1876**

Location of record: Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Scoloposcelis angusta* Reut.): Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Scoloposcelis angusta* Reut.): Velipoja (nympha).

Note: Josifov (1970, 1986) mentions the Albanian locality 'Velipoja' (Schumacher, 1914; Horváth, 1916), which was not accepted or overlooked by Péricart (1972, 1996a).

ANTHOCORIDAE Fieber, 1836: LYCTOCORINAE Reuter, 1884: XYLOCORINI Carayon, 1972

***Xylocoris (Xylocoris) cursitans* (Fallén, 1807)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Piezostethus cursitans* Fall.): Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Velipoja. Josifov, 1970: Bizë bei Shënjergji (an und unter Buchenrinde, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Xylocoris (Xylocoris) obliquus* A. Costa, 1853**

Location of record: Elbasan (Qark Elbasan).

Reference: Péricart, 1972: Elbasan! (leg. Mader, Természettudományi Muséum Állatára, Budapest, Hongrie) [HNHM?].

CIMICIDAE Latreille, 1802: CIMICINAE Latreille, 1802

[?] *Cimex hirundinis* Lamarck, 1816 [*Oeciacus hirundinis* (Lamarck, 1816)]

Location of record: ?

Reference: [?] Stichel, 1959: Albanien.

Note: To our knowledge, the above source is the only, but uncertain, reference to Albania (see Péricart, 1996b).

***Cimex lectularius* Linnaeus, 1758**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Divjakë (Qark Fier); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Librazhd (Qark Elbasan); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lushnjë (Qark Fier); Milot (Kurbin, Qark Lezhë); Oriku (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Pukë (Qark Shkodër); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Skutari [Shkodër] (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Skutari [Shkodër], Pashaliman [Oriku], Valona. Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (15.VIII.1917; 18.VII.1918, 20.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953: Berat, Qukes, Petrela, Miloti, Librazhd, Lusnia, Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941); Puka (leg. Capra). Josifov, 1970: Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961) [SDEI]. [?] Misja, 1970 (as *Cimex lectularius* L. (*columbarius* Jen.): Kudo në banesa [everywhere in homes]. Halimi, 2011: Divjakë (22.IX.2008).

Note: Misja (1970) erroneously uses *Cimex columbarius* Jenyns, 1839 as a synonym.

Superfamily: REDUVIOIDEA Latreille, 1807

REDUVIIDAE Latreille, 1807: EMESINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: LEISTRACHINI Stål, 1863

***Ploiaria domestica* Scopoli, 1786**

Locations of records: Butrint (Sarandë, Qark Vlorë); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Kolonjë (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Seman (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Walker, 1875 (as *Emesodema domesticum* Scop.): Butrinto. Mancini, 1953: Elbassan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1970 (as *Ploearia* [sic] *domestica* Scop.): Elbasan (21.VIII.1969); Tiranë (13.X.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Ploearia* [sic] *domestica* Scopoli, 1786): Kolonjë (24.IX.2008). Halimi et al., 2018 (as *Ploearia* [sic] *domestica* Scopoli, 1786): Seman (V.–IX.2015–2017).

REDUVIIDAE Latreille, 1807: EMESINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: METAPTERINI Stål, 1874

***Ischnonyctes barbarus* (Lucas, 1849)**

Location of record: Illjas (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Dioli, 1993: Regione di Valona, Lias, vallone di Gjper (02.VII.1993, 2 Nymphs).

***Metapterus caspicus* (Dohrn, 1863)**

Location of record: Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier).

Reference: Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

***Metapterus linearis* A. Costa, 1862**

Location of record: Buçimas (Pogradec, Qark Korçë).

Reference: Royer, 1924a: Starova [Buçimas] (V, 1 spécimen).

REDUVIIDAE Latreille, 1807: PEIRATINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843

Ectomocoris (Ectomocoris) ululans (Rossi, 1790)

Locations of records: Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier).

References: Mancini, 1953: Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

Peirates hybridus (Scopoli, 1763)

Locations of records: Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Pulaj (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Rrashbull (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Shëngjin (Qark Lezhë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); [?] Lavdar (Scrapar, Qark Berat); [?] Shkëmb (Cërrik, Qark Elbasan).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Pirates* [sic] *hybridus* Scop.): Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898); Pulaj (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905); Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Pirates* [sic] *hybridus* Scop.): Skutari [Shkodër], Pulaj, Velipoja, Valona. Royer, 1924a (as *Pirates* [sic] *hybridus* Scop.): plaine de Koritza [Korçë] (IX, 4 ♂, 4 ♀). Mancini, 1953 (as *Pirates* [sic] *hybridus* Scop.): Shen Gjin, Rashtbul, [?] Shkamb [Shkemb or Lavdar], [?] Rusterj, Skodra [Shkodër] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Elbassan (leg. Mader); Skutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Pirates* [sic] *hybridus* (Scopoli, 1763)): Tirana (Sommer 1942, leg. Bischoff); Tirana (15.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Pirates* [sic] *hybridus* Scop.): Tiranë (07.X.1963). Halimi, 2011 (as *Pirates* [sic] *hybridus* Scopoli, 1763): Ndroq (06.V.2007); Divjaka (22.IX.3008). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

Note: The locality 'Rusterj', mentioned by Mancini in 1953, remains unclear. 'Shkamb' may refer to either the village of Shkëmb, Qark Elbasan, or the village of Lavdar (Shkëmb), Qark Berat.

Peirates strepitans Rambur, 1839

Locations of records: Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Pulaj (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Pirates* [sic] *strepitans*): Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898); Pulaj (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905); Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Pirates* [sic] *strepitans* Ramb.): Velipoja. Mancini, 1953 (as *Pirates* [sic] *strepitans* Rmb): Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

REDUVIIDAE Latreille, 1807: PHYMATINAE Laporte, 1832: PHYMATINI Laporte, 1832

Phymata (Phymata) crassipes (Fabricius, 1775)

Location of record: Maliq (Qark Korçë).

References: [?] Dudich, 1922: Albanien [HNHM]. Misja, 1973 (Phymatidae): Maliq (30.VII.1970) [NHMT].

REDUVIIDAE Latreille, 1807: REDUVIINAE Latreille, 1807

Holotrichius obtusangulus Stål, 1874

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); [?] Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Berat (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Berat, Valona. Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–

27.V.1961) [SDEI, ZISB]. [?] Misja, 1973 (*Holotrichus* [sic] *spec.*): Ibë (03.VII-1696) [NHMT].

***Pasira basiptera* Stål, 1859**

Locations of records: Milot (Kurbın, Qark Lezhë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Reuter, 1891: Avlona (1884–1885, leg. E. von Oertzen). Mancini, 1953: Miloti, Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

***Reduvius personatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Bicaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Hamallaj (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Papër (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Oroshi. Csiki, 1940: Bičaj (12.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953: Durrec, Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970: Tirana (Sommer 1942, leg. Bischoff). Misja, 1970: Tiranë (06.IX.1963). Halimi, 2011: Hamallaj (14.VIII.2008); Papër (09.VIII.2008).

REDUVIIDAE Latreille, 1807: STENOPODAINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843

***Oncocephalus pilicornis* Reuter, 1882**

Locations of records: Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Oncocephalus pilicornis* H. Sch. [sic]): Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Oncocephalus pilicornis* H.-Sch. [sic]): Valona. Halimi, 2011: M. Robit (03.VIII.2009). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

***Oncocephalus plumicornis* (Germar, 1822)**

Location of record: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Misja, 1970: Ibë (17.VI.1961).

***Oncocephalus squalidus* (Rossi, 1790)**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Krrabë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Pulaj (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898); Pulaj (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Pulaj, Velipoja, Valona. Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (500 m, lux, 02.–12.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Tiranë (24.V.1966). Halimi, 2011: Krrabë (24.VI.2008); M. Robit (03.VIII.2008).

***Pygolampis bidentata* (Goeze, 1778)**

Location of record: Durrës (Qark Durrës).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Durrec (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

***Sastrapada baerensprungi* (Stål, 1859)**

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Horváth, 1916 (as *Sastrapada Baerensprungi* [sic] Stål): Valona.

REDUVIIDAE Latreille, 1807: HARPACTORINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: HARPACTORINI Amyot & Serville, 1843

Coranus (Coranus) griseus (Rossi, 1790)

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Divjakë (Qark Fier); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Pishë-Poro (Fier, Qark Fier); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Shkozet (Rrogzhinë, Qark Tiranë); Spille (Rrogzhinë, Qark Tiranë); Sukth (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Coranus aegyptius* F.): Durrec (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra). Josifov, 1970 (as *Coranus aegyptiacus* [sic] (Fabricius, 1775)): Borshi südlich Vlora (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Coranus aegyptius* F.): Vorë (14.V.1968); Pish-Poro (06.X.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Coranus aegyptius* Fabricius, 1775: Shkozet (24.IX.2008); Sukth (22.VI.2009); Spille (27.IX.2007); Divjakë (22.IX.2008). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

Note: Based on current knowledge, all European, Anatolian, and Caucasian records of *Coranus aegyptius* (auct. non Fabricius, 1775) should be attributed to this species (Putshkov & Moulet, 2009). The two species differ only in the structure of the male genitalia.

Coranus (Coranus) kerzhneri P.V. Putshkov, 1982

Location of record: Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Shëngjin (Qark Lezhë).

Reference: Putshkov & Moulet, 2009: San Giovanni di Medua [Shëngjin], Elbasan (HNHM!) [HNHM].

Coranus (Coranus) subapterus (De Geer, 1773)

Locations of records: Poliçan (Qark Berat); Spille (Rrogzhinë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Josifov, 1970: Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea*-Macchie, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vorë (14.V.1969); Tiranë (23.IX.1969); Vlorë (07.X.1969). Halimi, 2011: Spille (27.IX.2007).

Note: Mancini (1953) mentions a locality called 'Pecurici', which refers to the town of Pecurice in present-day Montenegro.

Coranus (Coranus) tuberculifer Reuter, 1881

Location of record: Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Pashtrik (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

Rhynocoris (Rhynocoris) annulatus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Locations of records: Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Mirditë (Qark Lezhë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Rhynocoris* [sic] *annulatus* L.): Merdita (leg. Adolph Winneguth, 1906, 1908) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Rhynocoris* [sic] *annulatus* L.): Merdita. Csiki, 1940 (as *Rhynocoris* [sic] *annulatus* L.): Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (13.VII.1918, 1000–1600 m) [HNHM].

[?] *Rhynocoris (Rhynocoris) cuspidatus* Ribaut, 1921

Locations of records: Dardhë (Korçë, Qark Korçë); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Shëngjin (Qark Lezhë).

Reference: Mancini, 1953 (*Rhynocoris* [sic] *cuspidatus* Rib.): Durrec, Dardha, Shen Gjin, Rustany [?] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

Note: Mancini (1953) mentions the locality 'Hodzha' (Hoça e Qytetit) which is located

in present-day Kosovo. The location of 'Rustany' in Albania could not be determined (see Table 2). According to Putshkov & Moulet (2009), this is a western Mediterranean species. Any records from the eastern Mediterranean should be verified.

Rhynocoris (Rhynocoris) erythropus (Linnaeus, 1767)

Location of record: [?] Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Rhynocoris* [sic] *erythropus* L.): Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Rhynocoris* [sic] *erythropus* L.): Oroshi. [?] Josifov, 1986: Albanien.

Rhynocoris (Rhynocoris) iracundus (Poda, 1761)

Locations of records: Bicaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Koplik (Malësi e Madha, Qark Shkodër); Krumë (Has, Qark Kukës); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lapardha 1 (Berat, Qark Berat); Lukovë (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Mali i Corajt (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Poshnjë (Dimal, Qark Berat); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Seman (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastrë); Ura Lapaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Zvërnec (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Rhynocoris* [sic] *iracundus* Poda): Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck); Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Rhynocoris* [sic] *iracundus* Poda): Cukali, Oroshi. Csiki, 1940 (as *Rhynocoris* [sic] *iracundus* Poda): Lušna: Ura i Lopez [Ura Lapaj] (21.VII.1918); Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (13.VII.1918, 1600–1800 m) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Rhynocoris* [sic] *iracundus* Poda): Kruma, Bicaj, Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918); Kopliku (leg. Capra); Tirana (coll. Mancini). Josifov, 1970 (*Rhynocoris* [sic] *iracundus* (Poda, 1761)): Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlora, Mali i Corajt (700–1100 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Lukova nördlich Saranda (250 m, 24.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea-Macchie*, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti (Westhang, 1100 m, 29.VI.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (10.–15.VII.1961); Durrës (Ödland mit hohen Disteln, 02.IX.1958, leg. Klausnitzer) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Ibë (08.VI.1968). Halimi, 2011: Spille (27.IX.2007); M. Robit (03.VIII.2008). Halimi et al., 2018: Seman (V.–IX.2015–2017). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zvërnec (14.VI.2022) [PCMG]. Halimi et al., 2024: Poshnje (20.VIII.2019); Lapardha (05.VI.2020) [NHMT].

Notes: Schumacher (1914) mentions the locality 'Janina', which refers to the present-day city of Ioannina (Albanian Janinë, Janina) in Greece. Horváth (1916) also refers to a record from 'Shar Dagh (Ljuboten)', which is the mountain range of Šar Panina-Ljuboten between Kosovo and North Macedonia.

Rhynocoris (Rhynocoris) punctiventris (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1846)

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Krrabë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Rhynocoris* [sic] *punctiventris* H.–Sch.): Cukali. Josifov, 1970 (as *Rhynocoris* [sic] *punctiventris* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1846)): Flora [sic; Flora is a misspelling of Vlora] (VII.1958, leg. Grebenščikov); Borshi südlich Vlora (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea-Macchie*, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961) [SDEI, ZISB]. Misja, 1970: Ibë (04.VII.1963); Vorë (25.VI.1969). Halimi, 2011: Kërrabë [sic] (26.VI.2008).

Rhynocoris (Rhynocoris) rubricus (Germar, 1814)

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shëngjin (Qark Lezhë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Rhinocoris* [sic] *iracundus* Poda var. *rubricus* Germ.): Berat. Mancini, 1953 (as *Rhinocoris* [sic] *iracundus* var. *rubricus* Germ.): Durrec, Shen Gjin (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

Sphedanolestes (Sphedanolestes) pulchellus (Klug, 1830)

Locations of records: Poliçan (Qark Berat); Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916: Valona. Josifov, 1970: Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea*-Macchie, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Halimi, 2011: Spille (27.IX.2009).

Zelus (Diplodacus) renardii Kolenati, 1857

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: van der Heyden, 2017f: Vlorë (phot. Aleksander Golemaj, 22.XI.2016, 15.XII.2016, 20.VI.2017, 30.VI.2017).

Infraorder: PENTATOMORPHA Leston, Pendergrast & Southwood, 1954

Superfamily: ARADOIDEA Brullé, 1836

ARADIDAE Brullé, 1836: ANEURINAE Douglas & Scott, 1865

Aneurus (Aneurodes) avenius (Dufour, 1833)

Location of record: Mirditë (Qark Lezhë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Aneurus laevis* F.): Merdita (leg. Adolph Winneguth, 1906, 1908) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Merdita.

Aneurus (Aneurus) laevis (Fabricius, 1775)

Location of record: Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

ARADIDAE Brullé, 1836: ARADINAE Brullé, 1836

Aradus (Aradus) betulae (Linnaeus, 1758)

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Milot (Kurbin, Qark Lezhë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Aradus Betulae* [sic] L.): Cukali. Csiki, 1940: Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (19.VII.1918, 1000–1600 m) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953: Miloti (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (an und unter Buchenrinde, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI].

Aradus (Aradus) conspicuus Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Konjat (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mirakë (Librazhd, Qark Elbasan); Mirditë (Qark Lezhë); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Aradus crenatus* Say): Merdita (leg. Adolph Winneguth, 1906, 1908); Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Aradus crenatus* Say): Cukali, Merdita. Mancini, 1953 (as *Aradus crenatus* Say): Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Aradus crenatus* Say): Bizë bei Shënjergji (an und unter Buchenrinde, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI].

Misja, 1970 (as *Aradus crenatus* Say): Bizë (09.VII.1961). Heiss, 2006: Konja (1/1 leg. Mader, no date, coll. Eckerlein, Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle, Geneva, Switzerland) [MHNG]. Halimi, 2011 (as *Aradus crenatus* Say, 1832): Dajt (18.IX.2007); Mirakë (29.VII.2009).

Note: According to Heiss (2006), the two specimens from the Natural History Museum Vienna, Austria were found in the Albanian locality of 'Fuša, Rappojanit, Ricarvaš, 1800 m, Vermosa Rapsa'. It is certain that this refers to the trough valley Ropojani or Ropojana, which is part of the Albanian Alps (Prokletije), and is located southwest of the town of Vusanje in present-day Montenegro. Although the meaning of 'Ricarvaš' remains unclear, 'Vermosa Rapsa' is a reference to the villages of Vermosh and Rhapshë on the Albanian side.

***Aradus (Aradus) corticalis* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Milot (Kurbini, Qark Lezhë); Sukth (Durrës, Qark Durrës).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Aradus corticalis* var. *annulicornis* F.): Miloti (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Halimi, 2011: Sukth (22.VI.2009).

***Aradus (Aradus) depressus depressus* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Locations of records: Sauk (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Aradus depressus* F.): Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Aradus depressus* F.): Velipoja. Misja, 1973 (as *Aradus depressus* F.): Sauk (27.IV.1970) [NHMT].

***Aradus (Aradus) flavicornis* Dalman, 1823**

Location of record: Elbasan (Qark Elbasan).

Reference: Heiss, 2006: Elbasan (leg. Priesner, IX.1918, Oberösterreichisches Landesmuseum, Linz, Austria) [OLML].

***Aradus (Aradus) krueperi* Reuter, 1884**

Locations of records: Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Aradus Krueperi* [sic] Reut.): Velipoja. Halimi, 2011 (as *Aradus krueperi* [sic] Reuter, 1884): Spille (27.IX.2007).

***Aradus (Aradus) lugubris* Fallén, 1807**

Location or record: Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Pashtrik (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

***Aradus (Aradus) pallescens frigidus* Kiritschenko, 1913**

Locations of records: Labinot-Fushë (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës).

References: Mancini, 1953: Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Halimi, 2011 (as *Aradus frigidus* Kiritschenko, 1913): F. Labinot (29.VII.2009).

***Aradus (Aradus) ribauti* Wagner, 1956**

Location of record: [?] Rrushkull (Mirditë, Qark Lezhë); [?] Rrushkull (Qark Durrës); [?] Rrushkull (Dajç, Qark Shkodër).

Reference: Heiss, 2006: Ruskuli (leg. Mader, Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle, Geneva, Switzerland; coll. E. Heiss, Innsbruck, Austria); Ruskuli (leg. Mader, 23.XI.1918, coll. Priesner, Oberösterreichisches Landesmuseum, Linz, Austria) [MHNG, PCEH, OLML].

Note: The location 'Ruskuli' (Heiss, 2006) is not clearly associated with any of the three Albanian villages named Rrushkull in Qark Lezhë, Qark Durrës and Qark Shkodër.

***Aradus (Aradus) versicolor* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Velipoja. Mancini, 1953: Berat, Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1916). Misja, 1973: Tiranë (20.IV.1970) [NHMT].

Superfamily: LYGAEOIDEA Schilling, 1829

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: LYGAEINAE Schilling, 1829 [Lygaeidae: Lygaeinae sensu Henry 1977]

***Arocatus longiceps* Stål, 1872**

Location of record: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI].

***Arocatus roeselii* (Schilling, 1829)**

Location of record: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Misja, 1970 (as *Arocatus roeseli* [sic] Schill.): Borsh (13.V.1961).

***Caenocoris nerii* (Germar, 1847)**

Location of record: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI].

***Graptostethus servus servus* (Fabricius, 1787)**

Locations of records: Durrës (Qark Durrës); Shëngjin (Qark Lezhë).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Graptostethus servus* var. *maculicollis* Germ.): Durrec (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Péricart, 1998a: S. Giov. di Madua [sic; Shëngjin] (leg. Mader, HNHM!).

***Horvathiolus superbus* (Pollich, 1781)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Lezhë (Qark Lezhë).

Reference: Mancini, 1953 (as *Spilostethus superbus* Pollich and *Spilostethus superbus* var. *kolenatii* Horv.): Lezhe (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Berat (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

***Lygaeosoma sardeum sardeum* Spinola, 1837**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Krumë (Has, Qark Kukës); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Milot (Kurbini, Qark Lezhë); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Mancini, 1953 (as *Lygaeosoma reticulatum* H. S.): Pashtrik, Korab, Kulla Ljums, Kruma (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Berat, Miloti (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

***Lygaeus creticus* Lucas, 1853**

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Tiranë, University, Fac. Nat. Sciences (Qark Tiranë).

Reference: van der Heyden, 2017a: Vlorë (phot. Aleksander Golemaj, 13.II.2017,

04.V.2017, 09.V.2017). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Tiranë (07.VI.2022) [ZIUT].

***Lygaeus equestris* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Alipostivan, Mali i Tomorrit, Teqeja e Baba Aliut (Përmet, Qark Gjirokaster); Berat (Qark Berat); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Buçimas (Pogradec, Qark Korçë); Divjakë (Qark Fier); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lezhë (Qark Lezhë); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mirditë (Qark Lezhë); Oriku (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Parku Kombëtar i Qafshatës (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Peshtan (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Shën Thanas (Voskopojë, Qark Korçë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Shtiqën (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Spilostethus equestris* L.): Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck); Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905); Merdita (leg. Adolph Winneguth, 1906, 1908); Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Spilostethus equestris* L.): Cukali, Merdita, Oroshi, Pashaliman [Oriku], Valona, Shen Thanas. Royer, 1923 (as *Spilostethus equestris* L.): environs de Koritza [Korçë] (V, VII–VIII, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀); Starova [Buçimas] (V, 1 ♀). Csiki, 1940 (as *Spilostethus equestris* L.): Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918); Stičen (in radices Montibus Djalica Ljums, 09.VII.1918); Montes Korab (25.VIII.1917, 1600–1800 m) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Spilostethus equestris* L.): Kula Ljums, Shkodra (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Berat (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Tirana (09.–12.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlora (Fluštal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Unterwuchs in Apfelplantage, 350 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Lezhë (03.VII.1968); Vlorë (27.V.1969); Korçë (05.VII.1969); Qafë-Shtamë (04.X.1969). Halimi, 2011: Dajt (18.IX.2007); Divjakë (22.IX.2008). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Alipostivan (17.VI.2022) [PCMG]. Halimi et al., 2024: Peshtan (13.IX.2019) [NHMT].

Notes: According to Horváth (1916), there is also a record from 'Shar Dagh (Ljuboten)', which refers to the mountain range Šar Panina-Ljuboten between Kosovo and North Macedonia. The location 'Sisevo' (Mancini, 1953) refers to the village Šiševo or Shishovë which is located in today's North Macedonia.

***Lygaeus simulans* Deckert, 1985**

Locations of records: Okol (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

Reference: van der Heyden & Dioli, 2019: Okol, scree at the base of Mount Maja Harapit (1200 m, 12.VII.1993); Theth (21.VI.2014, phot. Peter La-Belle).

***Melanocoryphus albomaculatus* (Goeze, 1778)**

Locations of records: Alipostivan, Mali i Tomorrit, Teqeja e Baba Aliut (Përmet, Qark Gjirokaster); Berat (Qark Berat); Gostilë (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Kodrat e Krastës (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Krumë (Has, Qark Kukës); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës); Ura Lapaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); [?] Mali i Thatë (Pogradec, Qark Korçë); [?] Mali i Sogorit (Gramsh, Qark Elbasan).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck); Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905); Berat (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Lygaeus leucopterus* Goeze): Cukali. Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918, 04.VII.1918); Lušna: Ura i Lopez [Ura Lapaj] (21.VII.1918); Köstil (17.VII.1917); Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (13.VII.1918, 1000–1600 m); Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Spilostethus albomaculatus* Goeze): Pashtrik, Korab, Kula Ljums, Kruma (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Berat (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Fluštal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Suha-Gora [Mali i Thatë or Mali i Sogorit] (20.IX.1961). Halimi,

2011: K. Krastës (24.VI.2008). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Alipostivan (17.VI.2022) [PCMG].

Note: Misja's (1970) 'Suha-Gora' locality refers to either the mountain Mali i Sogorit, Qark Elbasan, or the mountain Mali i Thatë, Qark Korçë, but not to the North Macedonian locality Suhagora.

***Spilostethus pandurus* (Scopoli, 1763)**

Locations of records: Ardenica (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Berat (Qark Berat); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Byshek (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kodrat e Krastës (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Lapardha 1 (Berat, Qark Berat); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkalla e Priskës (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vodicë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Zvërnec, Manasteri i Shën Mërisë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Berat, Valona. Mancini, 1953 (as *Spilostethus pandurus* Scop. and *S. pandurus* var. *militaris* F.): Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Lygaeus pandurus* (Scopoli, 1763)): Borshi südlich Vlora (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlora (SW-Hang mit *Pistacia* und *Phlomis*, 200–400 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Lygaeus pandurus* Scop.): Borsh (13.V.1961); Sh. Priskë (26.V.1961). Halimi, 2011 (as *Lygaeus pandurus* Scopoli, 1763): K. Krastës (24.VI.2008); Byshek (18.VII.2009). Halimi et al., 2018 (as *Lygaeus pandurus* Scopoli, 1763): Ardenica (V.–IX.2015–2017). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zvërnec (14.VI.2022) [PCMG]. Halimi et al., 2024: Vodic (27.VII.2019); Lapardha (25.VIII.2019) [NHMT].

***Spilostethus saxatilis* (Scopoli, 1763)**

Locations of records: Alipostivan, Mali i Tomorrit, Teqeja e Baba Aliut (Përmet, Qark Gjirokaster); Berat (Qark Berat); Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Darëzezë e Re (Qark Fier); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Hoçisht (Devoll, Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lybeshë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Malësi e Madha (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Milot (Kurbini, Qark Lezhë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Peshtan (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Poshnjë (Dimal, Qark Berat); Prenisht (Pogradec, Qark Korçë); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Tarabosh (Skodër, Qark Skodër); Tomorr-Tyrbja e Abaz Aliut (Skrapar, Qark Berat); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër); Ura Lapaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë); Zharrëz (Patos, Qark Fier).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck); Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905); Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Cukali, Oroshi, Berat, Valona. Royer, 1923: Prënist (1.000 m, V, 2 ♀). Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (16.VIII.1917, 03.VII.1918); Lušna: Ura i Lopez [Ura Lapaj] (22.VIII.1917); Malësi e Madha [Malësi e Madha] (22.VIII.1917); Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (13.VII.1918, 1600–1800 m); Montes Korab (25.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums, Korab, Tarabosh (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Berat, Miloti (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Lygaeus saxatilis* (Scopoli, 1763)): Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Tomor, Kloster Abbas Ali (1800 m, 08.–10.VI.1961); Dajti (Westhang, 1100 m, 29.VI.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Unterwuchs in Apfelplantage, 350 m,

25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Lygaeus saxatilis* Scop.): Dajt (11.V.1965). Halimi, 2011 (as *Lygaeus saxatilis* Scopoli, 1763): Dajt (25.V.2008, 18.IX.2007); Vorë (20.V.2009). Halimi et al., 2018 (as *Lygaeus saxatilis* Scopoli, 1763): Zharëza, Darzezë (V.–IX.2015–2017). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Alipostivan (17.VI.2022); Hoçisht (07.IX.2022) [PCMG]. Halimi et al., 2024: Poshnje (23.VII.2019); Peshtan (13.IX.2019); Lybesh (03.IX.2020) [NHMT].

Note: Mancini (1953) also mentions an Albanian record from Prizren, a city in today's Kosovo.

***Tropidothorax leucopterus* (Goeze, 1778)**

Locations of records: Durrës (Qark Durrës); Kepi i Rodonit (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Kunë (Lezhë, Qark Lezhë); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Lygaeus leucopterus* Gze): Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Lygaeus leucopterus* Goeze): Cukali. Mancini, 1953: Durrec, Skodra [Shkodër] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1970: Kune (03.VII.1968). Halimi, 2011: K. Rodonit (21.V.2007).

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: ORSILLINAE Stål, 1872: NYSIINI Uhler, 1876 [Lygaeidae: Orsillinae: Nysiini sensu Henry 1977]

***Ortholomus punctipennis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838)**

Location of record: Hoçisht (Devoll, Qark Korçë).

Reference: Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Hoçisht (07.IX.2022) [PCMG].

***Nithecus jacobaeae* (Schilling, 1829)**

Location of record: Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër).

Reference: Csiki, 1940: *Nysius jacobaeae* [sic] Schill.): Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m).

***Nysius graminicola graminicola* (Kolenati, 1845)**

Locations of records: Bradashesh (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Nysius graminicola* Kol.): Valona. Josifov, 1970 (as *Nysius (Macroparius) graminicola* (Kolenati, 1845)): Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Nysius graminicola* Kol.): Tiranë (05.IV.1969, 03.V.1969); Vlorë (16.–29.V.1969); Korçë (05.VIII.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Nysius graminicola* Kolenati, 1846): Bradashesh (11.V.2007). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

***Nysius senecionis senecionis* (Schilling, 1829)**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Nysius Senecionis* [sic] Schill.): Valona. Csiki, 1940 (as *Nysius Senecionis* [sic] Schill.): Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918). Josifov, 1970 (as *Nysius (Tropinysius) senecionis* (Schilling, 1829)): Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Luzernefeld, 300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Halimi, 2011 (as *Nysius senecionis* Schilling, 1829): Spille (27.IX.2007).

***Nysius thymi thymi* (Wolff, 1804)**

Locations of records: Këlcyrë (Qark Gjirokastrë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Misja, 1970 (as *Nysius thymi* Wolff): Vorë (10.X.1969); Këlcyrë (28.X.1968).

Note: The locality 'Prizren' given by Mancini (1953) is in the south of Kosovo.

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: ORSILLINAE Stål, 1872: ORSILLINI Stål, 1872
[Lygaeidae: Orsillinae: Orsillini sensu Henry 1977]

***Belonochilus numenius* (Say, 1832)**

Location of record: Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier).

Reference: Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

[?] *Orsillus depressus* (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)

Note: It should be noted that Péricart's (1998a, 2001a) citation of Josifov (1986) as evidence for an Albanian record is incorrect. Josifov (1986) only mentions Crete, Macedonia, Dalmatia, and Bulgaria.

***Orsillus maculatus* (Fieber, 1861)**

Locations of records: Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Kaninë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916: Kanina. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (28.V.1969). Halimi, 2011: Golem (19.VII.2009).

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: ISCHNORRHYNCHINAE Stål, 1872 [Lygaeidae: Ischnorrhynchinae sensu Henry 1977]

***Kleidocerys ericae* (Horváth, 1908)**

Locations of records: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Tomorr-Tyrbja e Abaz Aliut (Skrapar, Qark Berat); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Ischnorrhynchus* [sic] *Ericae* [sic] Horv.: Valona. Josifov, 1970 (as *Kleidocerys truncatulus ericae* (Horváth, 1908)): Tomor, Kloster Abbas Ali (1800 m, 08.–10.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti (Westhang, 1100 m, 29.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Kleidocerys resedae resedae* (Panzer, 1797)**

Locations of records: Durrës (Qark Durrës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Rrashbull (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Uznovë (Berat, Qark Berat).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Ischnorrhynchus resedae* Pnz): Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Misja, 1973 (as *Kleidocerys* [sic] *resedae* Pz.): Durrës (18.VII.1970) [NHMT]. Halimi, 2011 (as *Kleidocerys resedae* Panzer, 1797): Petrelë (12.VI.2009); Rrashbull (14.VIII.2009). Halimi et al., 2024: Uznov (20.VII.2019) [NHMT].

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: CYMINAE Baerensprung, 1860: CYMINI Baerensprung, 1860 [Cymidae: Cyminae sensu Henry 1977]

***Cymus claviculus* (Fallén, 1807)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Shkëlzenit (Tropojë, Qark Kukës); Tropojë (Qark Kukës).

References: Csiki, 1940: Tropoja, Montes Skolsen (02.VIII.1917, 1000 m). Josifov, 1970: Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–

15.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Cymus glandicolor* Hahn, 1832**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916: Berat. Mancini, 1953 (Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Misja, 1970: Vlorë (22.V.1969). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

***Cymus melanocephalus* Fieber, 1861**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Gostilë (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Tropojë (Qark Kukës); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916: Valona. Csiki, 1940: Tropoja (01.VIII.1917); Köstil (30.VII.1918). Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlora (Sumpf am Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (Kulturland, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1973: Velipojë (16.VIII.1969) [NHMT]. Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: BLISSINAE Stål, 1862 [Blissidae sensu Henry 1977]

***Dimorphopterus doriae* (Ferrari, 1874)**

Location of record: Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Blissus doriae* Ferr.): Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Blissus Doriae* [sic] Ferr.): Oroshi.

***Ischnodemus sabuleti* (Fallén, 1826)**

Locations of records: Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Spille (Rrogzhinë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916: Valona. Misja, 1973: Golem (13.V.1970) [NHMT]. Halimi, 2011: Spille (27.IX.2007).

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: HENESTARINAE Douglas & Scott, 1865 [Geocoridae: Henestarinae sensu Henry 1977]

***Henestaris halophilus* (Burmeister, 1835)**

Locations of records: Fier (Qark Fier); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); [?] Rrushkull (Mirditë, Qark Lezhë); [?] Rrushkull (Qark Durrës); [?] Rrushkull (Dajç, Qark Shkodër).

References: Mancini, 1953: Ruskuli (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (17.V.1969), Fier (06.X.1969).

Note: The location ‘Ruskuli’ (Mancini, 1953) is not clearly associated with any of the three Albanian villages named Rrushkull in Qark Lezhë, Qark Durrës and Qark Shkodër.

***Henestaris laticeps laticeps* (Curtis, 1836)**

Location of record: Divjakë (Qark Fier).

Reference: Halimi, 2011 (as *Henestaris laticeps* Curtis, 1836): Divjakë (22.IX.2008).

Note: Péricart (1998a, 2001a) refers to Josifov (1986), who in turn confidently quotes an unverifiable statement of Stichel (1960) (see Josifov, 1970).

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: GEOCORINAE Dahlbom, 1851 [Geocoridae: Geocorinae sensu Henry 1977]

Geocoris (Geocoris) arenarius (Jakovlev, 1867)

Location of record: Vurg (Sarandë, Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Misja, 1973: Vurg (20.V.1970) [NHMT].

Geocoris (Geocoris) ater (Fabricius, 1787)

Locations of records: Këlcyrë (Qark Gjirokastër); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Geocoris ater* F. var. *albipennis* F.): Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Geocoris albipennis* Fabr.): Oroshi. Csiki, 1940 (as *Geocoris ater* F. var. *albipennis* F.): Kula Ljums (16.VIII.1917). Mancini, 1953 (as *Geocoris ater* var. *albipennis* F. and *Geocoris ater* var. *steveni* Le P. S.): Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra); Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Misja, 1970: Vlorë (10.X.1968); Këlcyrë (29.X.1968); Tiranë (06.IX.1969). Péricart, 1998a: Scutari [Shkodër] (MCSN!) [most likely Mancini's collection]. Halimi, 2011: Spille (27.IX.2007).

Geocoris (Geocoris) grylloides (Linnaeus, 1761)

Location of record: Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI].

Geocoris (Geocoris) lineola lineola (Rambur, 1839)

Location of record: Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër).

Reference: Josifov, 1970 (as *Geocoris lineola* (Rambur): Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961) [SDEI].

Geocoris (Geocoris) megacephalus (Rossi, 1790)

Location of record: Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier).

References: Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017). [?] Péricart, 1998a: Albania (HMHM!).

Geocoris (Geocoris) pallidipennis pallidipennis (A. Costa, 1843)

Location of record: Elbasan (Qark Elbasan).

Reference: Péricart, 1998a: Elbassan (HNHM!).

Geocoris (Piocoris) erythrocephalus erythrocephalus (Lepelletier & Serville, 1825)

Locations of records: Apollonia (Fier, Qark Fier); Berat (Qark Berat); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kaninë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lybeshë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Peqin (Qark Elbasan); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Sherishtë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Shkozet (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Piocoris erythrocephalus* Lep. Serv.): Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck); Berat (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Piocoris erythrocephalus* Lep.): Oroshi, Kishbarda [Sherishtë], Berat, Sop [Appollonia], Valona, Kanina. Csiki, 1940 (as *Piocoris erythrocephalus* Lep. & Serv.): Kula Ljums (05.VII.1918,

06.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953 (as *Piocoris erythrocephalus* Le P. S.): Kula Ljums, Elbassan, Durrec (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra); Qukes, Petrela, Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Piocoris erythrocephalus* (Lepeletier & Audinet-Serville, 1825)): Durrës (Ödland, 02.–14.IX.1959, leg. Klausnitzer); Tirana (09.–12.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlora (SW-Hang mit *Pistacia* und *Phlomis*, 200–400 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea*-Macchie, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Unterwuchs in Apfelpflanzung, 350 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Piocoris erythrocephalus* Lep. S.): Ndroq (25.IV.1968); Vorë (28.IV.1968, 21.VI.1969), Vlorë (20.–27.V.1969), Velipojë (16.VIII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Vorë (24.V.2009); Shkozet (24.IX.2008); Peqin (10.VIII.2008). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017). Halimi et al., 2024: Lybesh (13.VI.2020) [NHMT].

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: ARTHENEINAE Stål, 1872: ARTHENEINI Stål, 1872 [Artheneidae sensu Henry 1977]

***Artheneis balcanica* (Kormilev, 1938)**

Location of record: Tiranë (Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Misja, 1973: Tiranë (22.IV.1970) [NHMT].

***Holcocranum saturejae* (Kolenati, 1845)**

Location of record: Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier).

Reference: Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: PACHYGRONTHINAE Stål, 1865: TERACRIINI Stål, 1872 [Pachygronthidae: Teracriinae sensu Henry 1977]

***Cymophyes (Cymophyes) ochroleuca* Fieber, 1870**

Location of record: Lezhë (Qark Lezhë).

Reference: Misja, 1970: Lezhë (03.VII.1968).

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: HETEROGASTRINAE Stål, 1872 [Heterogastridae sensu Henry 1977]

***Heterogaster affinis* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Heterogaster affinis* var. *rubricatus* Put.): Berat, Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Misja, 1973: Vorë (22.VI.1969) [NHMT].

***Heterogaster artemisiae* Schilling, 1829**

Locations of records: Korçë (Qark Korçë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).

References: Mancini, 1953: Shkodra (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1973: Korçë (04.VIII.1969) [NHMT].

***Heterogaster cathariae* (Geoffroy, 1785)**

Location of record: Gërmenj (Barmash, Kolonjë, Qark Korçë).

Reference: Dhellemmes, 2021e: District de Kolonjë, Albanie (01.X.2021; N 40.225343 E 20.659088 [Gërmenj]).

***Heterogaster urticae* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Locations of records: Jah Salihi (Tropojë, Qark Kukës); Kaninë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Heterogaster Urticae* [sic] Fabr.): Valona, Kanina. Misja, 1973: Cernicë (B. Curri) [Jah Salihi] (26.VIII.1971) [NHMT]. Halimi, 2011: Spille (27.IX.2007). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

***Platyplax inermis* (Rambur, 1839)**

Location of record: Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier).

Reference: Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

***Platyplax salviae* (Schilling, 1829)**

Locations of records: Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Mirakë (Librazhd, Qark Elbasan).

Reference: Misja, 1970: Korçë (04.VIII.1969). Péricart, 1998a: Elbassan (coll. Eckerlein!). Halimi, 2011: Mirakë (29.VII.2009).

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: OXYCARENINAE Stål, 1862 [Oxycarenidae sensu Henry 1977]

***Macroplax fasciata fasciata* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Këlcyrë (Qark Gjirokastrë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shtiqën (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); [?] Prezë (Vorë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Macroplax fasciata* H.–Sch.): Valona. Csiki, 1940 (as *Macroplax fasciata* H.–S.): Stiçen (in radices Montibus Djalica Ljums, 09.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953 (as *Macroplax fasciata* H. S.): Bresh [Prezë?] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Macroplax fasciata* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1835)): Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea-Macchie*, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Macroplax fasciata* H.–S.): Këlcyrë (28.X.1968); Vlorë (21.V.1969).

Note: Mancini's (1953) record from the locality of 'Bresh' possibly refers to the village of Prezë, Preza (formerly also known as Bresa, Breša).

***Macroplax preysleri* (Fieber, 1837)**

Location of record: Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI].

***Metopoplax fuscinervis* Stål, 1872**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër).

Reference: Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918); Montes Korab (25.VII.1918, 1850–1900 m).

***Metopoplax origani* (Kolenati, 1845)**

Locations of records: Çermë e Poshtme (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Kodrat e Krujës (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Reuter, 1891: Avlona (1884–1885, leg. E. von Oertzen). Horváth, 1916 (as *Metopoplax Origani* [sic] Kol.): Valona. Josifov, 1970: Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Dajti (Westhang, 1100 m, 29.VI.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Golem (07.X.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Metopoplax origami* [sic] Kolenati, 1845): K. Krujës (12.V.2008); M. Robit (03.VIII.2008); çerme (18.IX.2009).

***Microplax albofasciata* (A. Costa, 1847)**

Locations of records: Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

References: Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953: Elbassan (leg. Mader).

***Microplax interrupta* (Fieber, 1837)**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918, 04.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953: Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Microplax interrupta* (Fieber, 1836) [sic]): Dajti (Westhang, 1100 m, 29.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Oxycaenus (Euoxycareus) pallens* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850)**

Location of record: Këlcyrë (Qark Gjirokastër).

Reference: Misja, 1970: Këlcyrë (28.X.1968).

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: RHYPAROCHROMINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: ANTILLOCORINI Ashlock, 1964 [Rhyparochromidae: Rhyparochrominae: Antillocorini sensu Henry 1977]

***Oxycaenus (Oxycaenus) lavaterae* (Fabricius, 1787)**

Location of record: Shtuf (Ana e Malit, Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

Reference: van der Heyden (2024): near Shtuf, municipality of Shkodër (29.IV.2023, phot. Kacper Jędrusiak).

***Tropistethus fasciatus* Ferrari, 1874**

Locations of records: Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër).

References: Josifov, 1970: Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1973: Farkë (24.IV.1970) [NHMT]. Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

***Tropistethus holosericeus* (Scholtz, 1846)**

Locations of records: Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Skutari [Shkodër] (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905); Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Skutari [Shkodër], Velipoja. Mancini, 1953: Scutari [Shkodër], Velipoja (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: RHYPAROCHROMINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: DRYMINI Stål, 1872 [Rhyparochromidae: Rhyparochrominae: Drymini sensu Henry 1977]

***Drymus (Sylvadrymus) brunneus brunneus* (R.F. Sahlberg, 1848)**

Location of record: Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (*Drymus brunneus* Sahlbg.): Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (*Drymus brunneus* Sahlb.): Velipoja.

[?] *Drymus (Sylvadrymus) sylvaticus* (Fabricius, 1775)

Location of record: ?

Reference: [?] Stichel, 1960: Albanien.

***Eremocoris podagricus* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Locations of records: Durrës (Qark Durrës); Mirditë (Qark Lezhë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Eremocoris podagricus* L. [sic] and *Eremocoris podagricus* L. [sic] var. *alpinus* Garb): Velipoja (leg. Apfelbeck); Durazzo (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Eremocoris podagricus* Fabr. and *Eremocoris podagricus* Fabr. var. *alpinus* Garb.: Velipoja, Durazzo. Mancini, 1953 (as *Eremocoris podagricus* F. and *Eremocoris podagricus* F. var. *alpinus* Garb.): Merdita (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918). Péricart, 1998b: Merdita (MCSN!) [most likely Mancini's collection].

***Ischnocoris bureschi* Josifov, 1976**

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Péricart, 1998b: Kula Ljums (NHMW!).

[?] *Ischnocoris hemipterus* (Schilling, 1829)

Location of record: ?

References: [?] Stichel, 1960: Albanien. [?] Josifov, 1986: Albanien [quoting from Stichel, 1960].

***Ischnocoris punctulatus* Fieber, 1861**

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

***Lygaeosoma sardeum sardeum* Spinola, 1837**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Krumë (Has, Qark Kukës); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Milot (Kurbin, Qark Lezhë); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Mancini, 1953 (as *Lygaeosoma reticulatum* H. S.): Pashtrik, Korab, Kula Ljums, Kruma (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Berat, Miloti (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

***Scolopostethus affinis* (Schilling, 1829)**

Location of record: Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Velipoja.

***Scolopostethus cognatus* Fieber, 1861**

Location of record: Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

***Scolopostethus decoratus* (Hahn, 1833)**

Locations of records: Labinot-Fushë (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Misja, 1970: Tiranë (05.IV.1969); Korçë (05.VIII.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Scolopostethus decorates* [sic]): Vorë (24.V.2009); F. Labinot (29.VII.2009).

***Scolopostethus pictus* (Schilling, 1829)**

Locations of records: Maja e Koret (Qark Vlorë); Mamurras (Kurbin, Qark Lezhë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Velipoja, Kjore [Maja e Koret]. Mancini, 1953: Mamurras, Shkodra (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

[8] *Scolopostethus thomsoni* Reuter, 1875

Note: Péricart (1998b, 2001a) refers to Mancini (1953). The locality 'Hodzha' (Hoça e Qytetit) mentioned there is located in present-day Kosovo.

***Taphropeltus contractus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Zvërnec, Manasteri i Shën Mërisë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

References: Reuter, 1891: Avlona (1884–1885, leg. E. von Oertzen). Josifov, 1970: Kulla e Lumës bei Kukësi (25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zvërnec (14.VI.2022) [PCMG].

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: RHYPAROCHROMINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: GONIANOTINI Stål, 1872 [Rhyparochromidae: Rhyparochrominae: Goniatonini sensu Henry 1977]

***Aoploscelis bivirgata* (A. Costa, 1853)**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).

References: Horváth, 1916: Skutari [Shkodër]. Csiki, 1940 (as *Aoploscelis bivirgatus* [sic] Costa): Kulla Ljums (03.VII.1918).

***Aphanus rolandri* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: van der Heyden, 2018a: Vlorë (phot. Aleksander Golemaj, 30.VI.2017).

***Emblethis denticollis* Horváth, 1878**

Location of record: Peshkopi (Dibër, Qark Dibër).

Reference: Péricart, 1998c: Pescopic (MCSN!).

***Emblethis griseus* (Wolff, 1802)**

Locations of records: Gostilë (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).

References: Csiki, 1940: Köstil (30.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953 (as *Emblethis griseus* Wolff and *Emblethis bullatus* Fieb.): Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra).

***Emblethis verbasci* (Fabricius, 1803)**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Pulaj (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Pulaj (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Emblethis Verbasci* [sic] Fabr.): Pulaj. Mancini, 1953: Kulla Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Poliçan (17.VI.2022) [PCMG].

Note: Mancini (1953) also mentions an Albanian record from Prizren, a city in present-day Kosovo.

***Ischnopeza hirticornis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark

Tiranë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953: Berat (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Ischnopeza hirticornis* F. [sic]): Vorë (23.V.1969); Tiranë (06.IX.1969).

***Pterotmetus staphyliniformis* (Schilling, 1829)**

Locations of records: Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Peshkopi (Dibër, Qark Dibër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Pterotmetus staphylinoides* [sic] Burm.): Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Cukali. Misja, 1973: Peshkopi (14.IX.1970) [NHMT].

***Trapezonotus (Trapezonotus) arenarius arenarius* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Mirditë (Qark Lezhë); Pukë (Qark Shkodër); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Trapezonotus arenarius* L.): Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës], Merdita (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Puka (leg. Capra). Misja, 1970 (as *Trapezonotus arenarius* L.): Vorë (22.VI.1969).

Note: Records from 'Peristeri' (Schumacher, 1914) refer to the mountain range Baba or Pelister in North Macedonia.

***Trapezonotus (Trapezonotus) dispar* Stål, 1872**

Locations of records: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Shkëlzenit (Tropojë, Qark Kukës); Mirditë (Qark Lezhë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Velipoja. Csiki, 1940: Montes Skölsen (02.VIII.1917, 1750–2030 m); Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (13.VII.1918, 1600–1800 m). Mancini, 1953: Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës], Merdita (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1970: Ibë (05.VI.1969). Halimi, 2011: M. Robit (03.VIII.2008).

***Trapezonotus (Trapezonotus) ullrichi* (Fieber, 1837)**

Locations of records: Bicaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Mirditë (Qark Lezhë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Trapezonotus Ullrichi* [sic] Fieb.): Oroshi. Csiki, 1940 (as *Trapezonotus Ullrichi* [sic] Fieb.): Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (13.VII.1918, 1600–1800 m). Mancini, 1953: Elbasan, Bicaj, Merdita (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Trapezonotus (Trapezonotus) ullrichi* (Fieber, 1836) [sic]): Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961) [SDEI, ZISB].

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: RHYPAROCHROMINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: LETHAEINI Stål, 1872 [Rhyparochromidae: Rhyparochrominae: Lethaeini sensu Henry 1977]

***Lethaeus cribratissimus* (Stål, 1858)**

Location or record: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Sarandë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Saranda (28.V.1961) [SDEI].

Note: The locality 'Kopfstein' mentioned by Péricart (1998b) in southern Albania

('Süd-Albanien, Kopfstein, leg. Apfelbeck, HNHM!') has not been identified.

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: RHYPAROCHROMINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: MEGALONOTINI J. A. Slater, 1957 [Rhyparochromidae: Rhyparochrominae: Megalonotini sensu Henry 1977]

***Icus angularis* Fieber, 1861**

Location of record: Korçë (Qark Korçë).

Reference: Misja, 1973: Korçë (05.VIII.1969) [NHMT].

***Lamprodema maura* (Fabricius, 1803)**

Location of record: ?

Reference: Péricart, 1998c (as *Lamprodema maurum* [sic] (Fabricius, 1803)): Albanie [quoting from Roubal, 1959].

***Lasiocoris crassicornis* (Lucas, 1849)**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Himarë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Josifov, 1970 (as *Lasiocoris antennatus* Montandon, 1889): Borshi südlich Vlorë (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1973 (as *Lasiocoris antennatus* Mont.): Himarë (21.V.1970) [NHMT].

***Megalonotus chiragra* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Locations of records: Divjakë (Qark Fier); Gostilë (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Rhyparochromus chiragra* F.): Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Rhyparochromus chiragra* Fabr.): Velipoja. Csiki, 1940 (as *Rhyparochromus chiragra* F.): Kösztil [Gostilë] (30.VII.1918); Montes Korab (28.VII.1918, 1750 m). Mancini, 1953 (as *Rhyparochromus chiragra* F. and *Rhyparochromus chiragra* [?] var. *incertus* Rey): Korab, Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës], Pashtrik (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1970: Tiranë (26.IV.1969). Halimi, 2011: Divjakë (22.IX.2008).

Note: According to Josifov (1970, 1986), the Albanian records are questionable due to possible confusion with *Megalonotus sabulicola* (Thomson, 1870).

***Megalonotus dilatatus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1840)**

Location of record: Pulaj (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

Reference: Horváth, 1916 (as *Rhyparochromus dilatatus* H.–Sch.): Pulaj.

***Megalonotus emarginatus* (Rey, 1888)**

Location of record: ?

Reference: Péricart, 1998c: Albanie (HNHM!).

***Megalonotus praetextatus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Mirditë (Qark Lezhë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Rhyparochromus praetextatus* H. Sch.): Berat (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Rhyparochromus praetextatus* H.–Sch.): Velipoja, Berat. Csiki, 1940 (as *Rhyparochromus praetextatus* [sic] H.–S.): Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (14.VII.1918, 2000–2500 m). Mancini, 1953 (as *Rhyparochromus praetextatus* H. S.): Merdita (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

***Megalonotus puncticollis* (Lucas, 1849)**

Location of record: Orikum (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Horváth, 1916 (as *Rhyparochromus puncticollis* Luc.): Pashaliman [Orikum].

Note: The locality 'Lapad' mentioned by Mancini (1953) for this species was not found in Albania. However, it is possible that this refers to Lapad, a city district of Dubrovnik in Croatia.

***Megalonotus sabulicola* (Thomson, 1870)**

Location of record: Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Gostilë (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Roubal, 1965 (as *Megalonotus sabulicola* v. *incertus* (Rey)): Köstil, Elbassan.

***Pezocoris apicimacula* (A. Costa, 1853)**

Locations of records: Bradashesh (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Misja, 1970: Vorë (17.V.1968). Halimi, 2011: Bradashesh (11.V.2007).

***Proderus bellevoeyi* Puton, 1874**

Location of record: Pojan (Maliq, Qark Korçë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Proderus crassicornis* Jak.): Pojani. Péricart, 1998c: Pojan (HNMM!).

***Proderus suberythropus* (A. Costa, 1842)**

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Péricart, 1998c: Vloze [sic; Vlore!] (coll. Servadei, MSNV!).

Note: Péricart's 'Vloze' (1998 c) is certainly a misspelling of Vlore.

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: RHYPAROCHROMINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: MYODOCHINI Blanchard, 1845 [Rhyparochromidae: Rhyparochrominae: Myodochini sensu Henry 1977]

***Pachybrachius capitatus* (Horváth, 1882)**

Location of record: Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Pamera capitata* Horv.): Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Pamera capitata* Horv.): Velipoja. Péricart, 1998c: Velipoja (HNHM!).

***Paraparomius leptopoides* (Baerensprung, 1859)**

Locations of records: Kepi i Rodonit (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Misja, 1970: Velipojë (16.VIII.1969); Tiranë (06.IX.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Paromius leptopoides* Baerensprung, 1859 [sic]): K. Rodonit (21.V.2007). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

***Paromius gracilis* (Rambur, 1839)**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orikum (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916: Pashaliman [Orikum], Valona. Mancini, 1953: Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vloza (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

[?] *Paromius longulus* Dallas, 1852

Location of record: [?] Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: [?] Halimi, 2011: Ibë (26.VII.2008).

Note: *Paromius longulus* is a species found in the Nearctic and Neotropical regions (Ashlock & Slater, 1988; Slater & O'Donnell, 1995). Its presence in Albania needs to be verified.

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: RHYPAROCHROMINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: PLINTHISINI J.A. Slater & Sweet, 1961 [Rhyparochromidae: Rhyparochrominae: Plinthisini sensu Henry 1977]

Plinthisus (Nanoplinthisus) fasciatus Horváth, 1882

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlora).

Reference: Reuter, 1891: Avlona (1884–1885, leg. E. von Oertzen).

Plinthisus (Plinthisus) brevipennis (Latreille, 1807)

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Qark Kukës); Maja e Koret (Qark Vlorë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Velipoja, Kjore [Maja e Koret]. Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (06.VII.1918).

Plinthisus (Plinthisus) coracinus Horváth, 1876

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: [?] Reuter, 1891: Albanien (1887, leg. J. Emge). Horváth, 1916: Valona. Péricart, 1998b: Avlona (= Vlonë [sic], leg. Van Oertzen, coll. Seidenstücker, NMHM!).

Plinthisus (Plinthisus) longicollis Fieber, 1861

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Kaninë (Vlorë, Qark Vlora).

References: [?] Horváth, 1876: Albanien. Horváth, 1916 (as *Plinthisus longicollis* Fieb. and *Plinthisus hungaricus* Horv.: Kanina. Josifov, 1970 (as *Plinthisus (Plinthisus) longicollis* Fieber, 1861 and *Plinthisus (Plinthisus) hungaricus* Horváth, 1875): Borshi südlich Vlora (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI].

Note: The locality 'Lapad' mentioned by Mancini (1953) for *Plinthisus longicollis* Fieb. and *Plinthisus hungaricus* Horv., Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) was not found in Albania. However, it is possible that this refers to Lapad, a city district of Dubrovnik in Croatia.

Plinthisus (Plinthisus) mehadiensis Horváth, 1881

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Qark Kukës).

References: Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (06.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

Note: The locality 'Sisevo' (Šiševo, Shishovë) mentioned by Mancini (1953) is located in present-day North Macedonia.

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: RHYPAROCHROMINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: RHYPAROCHROMINI Amyot & Serville, 1843 [Rhyparochromidae: Rhyparochrominae: Rhyparochromini sensu Henry 1977]

Beosus maritimus (Scopoli, 1763)

Locations of records: Bardhor (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Kavajë (Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Pulaj (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Pulaj (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Pulaj. Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Scutari

[Shkodër] (leg. Capra). Misja, 1970: Kavajë (14.VII.1969); Velipojë (16.VIII.1969); Tiranë (06.IX.1969). Halimi, 2011: Bardhore (08.VI.20079).

***Beosus quadripunctatus* (Müller, 1766)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Pulaj (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Sherishtë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Pulaj (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905); Berat (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Pulaj, Kishbarda [Sherishtë], Berat. Mancini, 1953: Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra); Qukes, Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Misja, 1970: Vlorë (19.V.1969, 05.X.1969). Halimi, 2011: Ibë (26.VII.2008). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

Note: According to Péricart (1998c), 'Rudnik' is listed as one of the Albanian records (HNHM!). It is highly probable that this refers to the mountain range or village of Rudnik Raduša in North Macedonia.

***Graptopeltus lynceus* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Labinot-Fushë (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Aphanus lynceus* F.): Berat (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Aphanus lynceus* Fabr.): Berat. Mancini, 1953 (as *Raglius lynceus* F.): Durrec, Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1970: Korçë (05.VIII.1969). Halimi, 2011: L. Fushë (29.VII.2009).

***Graptopeltus validus* (Horváth, 1875)**

Location of record: Berat (Qark Berat).

Reference: Horváth, 1916 (as *Aphanus consors* Horv. var. *Lethierryi* [sic] Montd.): Berat.

[?] *Peritrechus flavicornis* Jakovlev, 1877

Location of record: Lushnjë (Qark Fier).

Reference: Misja, 1973: Lushnjë (03.VIII.1971) [NHMT].

Note: According to Aukema et al. (2013) the record in Misja (1973) needs verification.

[x] *Peritrechus geniculatus* (Hahn, 1832)

Note: Aukema et al. (2013) cite Misja (1973) as the source for an Albanian record. However, Misja (1973) quotes Csiki (1940), who reads 'Korita'. Friese (1967) interprets this 'Csiki site' as a locality north of Goduša [in the Bijelo Polje district], Montenegro.

***Peritrechus gracilicornis* Puton, 1877**

Locations of records: Bicaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mirditë (Qark Lezhë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953: Bicaj, Merdita (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1970: Tiranë (26.IV.1969). Halimi, 2011: Vorë (24.V.2009).

Note: The species is also mentioned to occur in the Albanian locality 'Ipak' by Péricart (1998c) (HNHM!). It is presumed that this refers to 'Ipek' (Albanian Pejë, Peja or Serbo-Croatian Peć), which currently belongs to Kosovo.

***Peritrechus lundii* (Gmelin, 1790)**

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

References: Csiki, 1940: as *Peritrechus lundii* [sic] Gmel.: Kula Ljums (08.VII.1918). Péricart, 1998c: Kula Ljums (HNHM!).

Peritrechus meridionalis* Puton, 1877*Location of record:** Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).**References:** Reuter, 1891: Avlona (1884–1885, leg. E. von Oertzen). Horváth, 1916: Valona. Péricart, 1998c: Valona (= Vlonë [sic]) (HNHM!).**Note:** The species is also mentioned to occur in the Albanian locality 'Ipak' by Péricart (1998c) (HNHM!). It is presumed that this refers to 'Ipek' (Albanian Pejë, Peja or Serbo-Croatian Peć), which currently belongs to Kosovo.***Peritrechus nubilus* (Fallén, 1807)****Locations of records:** Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vurg (Sarandë, Qark Vlorë).**References:** Schumacher, 1914: Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Velipoja, Valona. Misja, 1973: Vurg (20.V.1970) [NHMT].***Peritrechus pusillus* Horváth, 1884****Locations of records:** Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).**References:** Schumacher, 1914: Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Velipoja, Valona.***Raglius alboacuminatus alboacuminatus* (Goeze, 1778)****Locations of records:** Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Parku Kombëtar i Luginës së Valbonës (Tropojë, Qark Kukës).**References:** Csiki, 1940 (as *Raglius alboacuminatus* Goeze): Kula Ljums (05.VII.1918, 06.VII.1918). Gailhampshire, 2018a (as *Raglius alboacuminatus?*): Valbona National Park. Albanian Alps (05.VI.2018).**Note:** The photo taken by Gailhampshire (2018a) does in fact show *Raglius alboacuminatus*.***Raglius confusus* (Reuter, 1886)****Locations of records:** Berat (Qark Berat); Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Peshtan (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Vorë (Qark Tiranë); [?] Prezë (Vorë, Qark Tiranë).**References:** Mancini, 1953: Bresh [Prezë?], Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Berat (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea-Macchie*, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1973: Golem (14.V.1970) [NHMT]. Péricart, 1998c (as *Rhyparochromus (Raglius) confusus* (Reuter, 1886): Vorra [sic; Vora] (coll. Eckerlein!). Halimi et al., 2024: Peshtan (13.IX.2019) [NHMT].**Note:** Mancini's (1953) record from the locality of 'Bresh' possibly refers to the village of Prezë, Preza (formerly also known as Bresa, Breša).***Rhyparochromus phoeniceus* (Rossi, 1794)****Locations of records:** Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Krumë (Has, Qark Kukës); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Parku Kombëtar i Qafshatës (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës); Peqin (Qark Elbasan); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Tomorr-Tyrbja e Abaz Aliut (Skrapar, Qark Berat).**References:** Horváth, 1916 (as *Aphanus phoeniceus* Rossi): Oroshi. Mancini, 1953 (as *Raglius phoenicius* [sic] Rossi): Pashtrik, Kruma, Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra). Josifov, 1970: Tomor, Kloster Abbas Ali (1800 m, 08.–10.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m,

19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Korçë (05.VIII.1969); Qafë-Shtamë (04.X.1969). Halimi, 2011: Petrelë (12.VI.2009); Peqin (10.VIII.2008).

***Rhyparochromus pini* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Korçë (Qark Korçë); Lybeshë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mirakë (Librazhd, Qark Elbasan); Mirditë (Qark Lezhë); Orenjë (Librazhd, Qark Elbasan); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Poliçan (Qark Berat).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Aphanus pini* L.): Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Aphanus Pini* [sic] L.): Cukali, Oroshi. Csiki, 1940 (as *Raglius pini* L.): Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m). Mancini, 1953 (as *Raglius pini* L.): Mirdita, Oranie (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1970: Korçë (05.VIII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Mirakë (29.VII.2009). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Poliçan (17.VI.2022) [PCMG]. Halimi et al., 2024: Lybesh (08.VIII.2019) [NHMT].

***Rhyparochromus sanguineus* (Douglas & Scott, 1868)**

Locations of records: Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Orikum (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Aphanus phoeniceus* Rossi var. *sanguineus* Dgl. Sc.): Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck). Horváth, 1916 (as *Aphanus phoeniceus* Rossi var. *sanguineus* D. S.): Cukali, Velipoja, Pashaliman [Orikum]. [?] Péricart, 1998c: Albanie (HNHM!).

Notes: The records from 'Peristeri' (Schumacher, 1914) are believed to refer to either the Baba or Pelister mountain range in North Macedonia, or one of the numerous places in Greece with the same name. Horváth (1916) also mentions an Albanian record from 'Shar Dag (Ljuboten)', which is located in the Šar Panina-Ljuboten mountain range between Kosovo and North Macedonia.

***Rhyparochromus vulgaris* (Schilling, 1829)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë, Parku i Madh i Liqenit artificial (Qark Tiranë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Aphanus vulgaris* Schill.): Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898); Berat (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Aphanus vulgaris* Schill.): Velipoja, Berat. Mancini, 1953 (as *Raglius vulgaris* Schill.): Berat (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Halimi, 2011: Spille (27.IX.2007). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Tiranë (17.VI.2022) [PCMG].

***Xanthochilus minusculus* (Reuter, 1885)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Aphanus reuteri* Horv.): Berat (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Aphanus Reuteri* [sic] Horv.): Berat. Péricart, 1998c (as *Rhyparochromus (Xanthochilus) minusculus* (Reuter, 1885): Elbassan (HNHM!), Tirana (MCSN!).

[?] *Xanthochilus omissus* (Horváth, 1911)

Location of record: Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Misja, 1973: Vorë (17.V.1968) [NHMT].

Note: According to Péricart (1998c) only known from Tanscaucasia. The record from Albania (Misja, 1973) has to be confirmed.

***Xanthochilus quadratus* (Fabricius, 1798)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Gostilë (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Tropojë (Qark Kukës); Ura Lapaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Raglius quadratus* F.): Tropoja (06.VIII.1917); Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918); Lušna: Ura i Lopez [Ura Lapaj] (21.VII.1918); Kösztil [Gostilë] (30.VII.1918). Mancini, 1953 (as *Raglius quadratus* F.): Kula Ljums, Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Geröllhang in *Fagus-Abies*-Wald in 1350 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Kulla e Lumës bei Kukësi (Unterwuchs in Apfelplantage, 350 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (19.V.1969).

Note: The records from 'Peristeri' (Schumacher, 1914) are believed to refer to either the Baba or Pelister mountain range in North Macedonia, or one of the numerous places in Greece with the same name.

***Xanthochilus saturnius* (Rossi, 1790)**

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Misja, 1970: Vlorë (16.IX.1969).

LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829 [s. lat.]: RHYPAROCHROMINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: STYGNOCORINI Gulde, 1937 [Rhyparochromidae: Rhyparochrominae: Stygnocorini sensu Henry 1977]

***Hyalochilus ovatulus* (A. Costa, 1853)**

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Reuter, 1891: Avlona (1884–1885, leg. E. von Oertzen).

***Stygnocoris fuligineus* (Geoffroy, 1785)**

Location of record: Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës).

Reference: Csiki, 1940: Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (19.VIII.1917, 2300–2500 m).

***Stygnocoris sabulosus* (Schilling, 1829)**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Sarandë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Josifov, 1970 (as *Stygnocoris pedestris* (Fallén, 1807): Borshi südlich Vlora (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1973 (as *Stygnocoris pedestris* Fall.): Sarandë (30.X.1970) [NHMT].

***Stygnocorisella mayeti* (Puton, 1879)**

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Horváth, 1916 (as *Stygnocoris Mayeti* [sic] Put.): Valona.

PIESMATIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843

***Piesma maculatum* (Laporte, 1833)**

Location of record: Ura Lapaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Csiki, 1940 (as *Piesma maculata* [sic] Lap.): Lušna: Ura i Lopez [Ura Lapaj] (21.VII.1918) [HNHM].

BERYTIDAE Fieber, 1851: BERYTINAE Fieber, 1851: BERYTINI Fieber, 1851

***Apoplymus pectoralis* Fieber, 1859**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Reuter, 1891: Avlona (1884–1885, leg. E. von Oertzen). Horváth, 1916: Valona. Mancini, 1953: Berat (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

***Berytinus (Berytinus) minor minor* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Berytinus minor* H.–S.): Kula Ljums (04.VII.1918); Montes Korab (27.VIII.1917, 1500–1800 m) [HNHM]. Halimi, 2011 (as *Berytinus minor* Herrich-Schäffer [sic], 1835): Vorë (24.V.2009).

***Berytinus (Lizinus) consimilis* (Horváth, 1885)**

Locations of records: Lushnjë (Qark Fier); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

References: Mancini, 1953: Lusnia (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Berytinus (Lizinus) montivagus* (Meyer-Dür, 1841)**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953: Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vorë (02.V.1968). Halimi, 2011: Vorë (24.V.2009).

Note: The locality 'Lapad' mentioned by Mancini (1953) in Albania (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW] was not found in Albania. However, it is possible that this refers to Lapad, a city district of Dubrovnik in Croatia.

***Berytinus (Lizinus) striola* (Ferrari, 1874)**

Location of record: ?

Reference: Péricart, 1984: Albanie (!). Péricart, 2001b: Albania.

***Neides aduncus* Fieber, 1859**

Locations of records: Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Porto Romano (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).

References: Horváth, 1916: Skutari [Shkodër]. Mancini, 1953: Portes [Porto Romano] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

***Neides tipularius* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Bicaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Neides favosus* Fieb.): Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Neides tipularius* L. and *Neides favosus* Fieb.): Bicaj (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1973: Korçë (29.VII.1970) [NHMT]. Halimi, 2011: Dajt (25.VI.2008).

Note: Mancini (1953) also mentions an Albanian record from 'Rabic', which is likely referring to the hill Rabić in present-day Bosnia and Herzegovina.

BERYTIDAE Fieber, 1851: GAMPSOCORINAE Southwood & Leston, 1859: GAMPSOCORINI Southwood & Leston, 1859

***Gampsocoris culicinus culicinus* Seidenstücker, 1948**

Locations of records: Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kukës (Qark Kukës); Peshkopi (Dibër,

Qark Dibër).

Reference: Misja, 1973 (as *Gampsocoris culicinus* Seid.): Korçë (27.VII.1970); Kukës (10.IX.1970); Peshkopi (13.IX.1970) [NHMT].

***Gampsocoris enslini* Seidenstücker, 1953**

Location of record: between Borsh and Lukovë (Himarë, Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: zwischen Borshi und Lukova (14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI].

***Gampsocoris punctipes punctipes* (Germar, 1822)**

Locations of records: Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Reuter, 1891 (as *Metacanthus elegans* Curt.): Avlona (1887, leg. J. Emge). Schumacher, 1914 (as *Metacanthus elegans* Curt.): Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905). Horváth, 1916 (as *Gampsocoris punctipes* Germ.): Oroshi. Mancini, 1953 (as *Gampsocoris punctipes* Germ.): Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

BERYTIDAE Fieber, 1851: METACANTHINAE Douglas & Scott, 1865: METATROPINI Douglas & Scott, 1865

***Metatropis rufescens* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

Location of record: Jah Salihi (Tropojë, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Misja, 1973: Çernicë (B. Curr) [Jah Salihi] (26.VIII.1971) [NHMT].

Superfamily: PYRRHOCOROIDEA Amyot & Serville, 1843

PYRRHOCORIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843

***Pyrrhocoris apterus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Hoçisht (Devoll, Qark Korçë); Kepi i Rodonit (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lezhë (Qark Lezhë); Maminas (Shijak, Qark Durrës); Oriku (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898); Valona (leg. Patsch); Berat (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Velipoja, Pashaliman [Oriku], Berat, Valona. Csiki, 1940 (as *Pyrrhocoris apterus* ab. *membranaceus* Westh.): Kula Ljums (05.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Pyrrhocoris apterus* L. and *Pyrrhocoris apterus* var. *membranaceus* Westh.): Durrec (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1970: Lezhë (03.VII.1968); Maminas (15.VI.1968); Tiranë (28.IV.1969, 05.II.1970). Halimi, 2011: Golem (19.VII.2009); K. Rodonit (21.V.2007). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Hoçisht (07.IX.2022); Korçë (12.VI.2022) [PCMG].

***Pyrrhocoris marginatus* (Kolenati, 1845)**

Locations of records: Oriku (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Reuter, 1891 (as *Pyrrhocoris marginatus* Kol.): Avlona (1884–1885, leg. E. von Oertzen). Horváth, 1916: Pashaliman [Oriku].

***Scantius aegyptius rossii* Carapezza, Kerzhner & Rieger, 1999**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Llogara (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Oriku (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Scantius aegyptius* L.): Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Scantius aegyptius* L.): Pashaliman [Oriku], Berat, Valona. Mancini, 1953 (as *Scantius aegyptius* L.): Durrec (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918)

[NHMW]. Misja, 1973 (as *Scantius aegyptius* L.): Llogara (II.–V.1970) [NHMT].

Superfamily: COREOIDEA Leach, 1815

STENOCEPHALIDAE Dallas, 1852

***Dicranocephalus agilis* (Scopoli, 1763)**

Locations of records: Alipostivan, Mali i Tomorrit, Teqeja e Baba Aliut (Përmet, Qark Gjirokaster); Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953: Pashtrik (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1973: Tiranë (22.IV.1970) [NHMT]. Halimi, 2011: Farkë (13.VII.2009). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Alipostivan (17.VI.2022); Poliçan (17.VI.2022) [PCMG].

***Dicranocephalus albipes* (Fabricius, 1781)**

Locations of records: Alipostivan, Mali i Tomorrit, Teqeja e Baba Aliut (Përmet, Qark Gjirokaster); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Krumë (Has, Qark Kukës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Zvërnec (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Stenocephalus albipes* F.): Valona (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Stenocephalus albipes* F.): Valona. Royer, 1923 (*Stenocephalus albipes* Fab.): environs de Koritza [Korçë] (VI, 4 ♂, 1 ♀). Mancini, 1953: Kruma (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea*-Macchie, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (23.V.1969); Korçë (05.VIII.1969). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Alipostivan (17.VI.2022); Zvërnec (14.VI.2022) [PCMG].

[§] *Dicranocephalus marginicollis* (Puton, 1881)

Note: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Stenocephalus divulsus* Horv.) mentions a record from 'Peristeri' (leg. Apfelbeck). This locality may refer to either the Baba or Pelister mountain range in North Macedonia or one of the numerous places with this name in Greece.

***Dicranocephalus medius* (Mulsant & Rey, 1870)**

Locations of records: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Stenocephalus medius* Mls. R.): Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Halimi, 2011: Ibë (26.VII.2008).

RHOPALIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: RHOPALINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: RHOPALINI Amyot & Serville, 1843

***Brachycarenum tigrinus* (Schilling, 1829)**

Locations of records: Hamallaj (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Rhopalus tigrinus* Schill.): Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Rhopalus tigrinus* Schill.): Oroshi, Valona. Josifov, 1970: Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (16.V.1969). Halimi, 2011: Ibë (26.VII.2008); Hamallaj (14.VIII.2008). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

***Corizus hyoscyami hyoscyami* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Alipostivan, Mali i Tomorrit, Teqeja e Baba Aliut (Përmet, Qark Gjirokaster); Ardenica (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Buçimas (Pogradec, Qark Korçë); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kepi i Rodonit (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lezhë (Qark Lezhë); Lukovë (Himarë, Qark

Vlorë); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Maja e Madhe (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Mirditë (Qark Lezhë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Parku Kombëtar i Qafshtamës (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Ploshtan (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Poshnjë (Dimal, Qark Berat); Rubjekë (Shijak, Qark Durrës); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Tropojë (Qark Kukës); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër); Ura Lapaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Zharrëz (Patos, Qark Fier).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Therapha hyoscyami* L.): Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905); Merdita (leg. Adolph Winneguth, 1906, 1908) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Corizus Hyoscyami* [sic] L.): Merdita, Oroshi, Valona. Royer, 1923 (Coreidae): Starova [Buçimas], env. de Koritza [Korçë] (V, 1 ♂). Csiki, 1940 (as *Corizus hyoscyami* L.): Tropoja (01.VIII.1917); Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918, 05.VII.1918, 06.VII.1918); Lušna: Ura i Lopez [Ura Lapaj] (22.VIII.1917); Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (13.VII.1918, 1000–1600 m); Ploštan (29.VII.1918); Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953: Rezej [Rubjekë] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra). Josifov, 1970 (as *Corizus hyoscyami* (Linnaeus, 1758)): Durrës (Ödland, 02.–09.IX.1959, leg. Klausnitzer); Lukova nördlich Saranda (250 m, 24.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Maja e Madhe (1400–1789 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Luzernefeld, 300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Corizus hyoscyami* [sic] L.): Lezhë (03.VIII.1968); Tiranë (26.IV.1969); Qafë Shtamë (04.X.1969). Halimi, 2011: Ibë (26.VII.2008); Golem (19.VII.2009); K. Rodonit (21.V.2007). Halimi et al., 2018 (as *Corizus hyoscyami* Linnaeus, 1758): Zharëza, Ardenica (V.–IX.2015–2017). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Alipostivan (17.VI.2022) [PCMG]. Halimi et al., 2024: Poshnje (20.VIII.2019) [NHMT].

***Liorhysus hyalinus* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Giri i Lalzit (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Këlcyrë (Qark Gjirokastër); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lushnjë (Qark Fier); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916: Valona. Csiki, 1940: Montes Korab (24.VII.1918, 2700 m) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums, Elbassan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra); Petrela, Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (SW-Hang mit *Pistacia* und *Phlomis*, 200–400 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Tirana (09.–12.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (Kulturland, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Luzernefeld, 300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Liorhysus* [sic] *hyalinus* L.): Këlcyrë (28.X.1968); Lushnjë (21.X.1969). Halimi, 2011: Gj. Lalzit (03.IX.2009).

[?] *Maccevethus caucasicus* (Kolenati, 1845)

Locations of records: [?] Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); [?] Gërmenj (Skrapar, Qark

Berat); [?] Kaninë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); [?] Kukës (Qark Kukës); [?] Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); [?] Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: [?] Horváth, 1916 (as *Maccevethus lineola* Fabr.): Valona; Kanina. [?] Mancini, 1953 (as *Macevethus* [sic] *lineola* F. and *Macevethus* [sic] *lineola* F. var. *macedonicus* Kormilev); Elbassan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). [?] Misja, 1973 (as *Maccevethus lineola* F.): Kukës (02.IX.1970) [NHMT]. [?] Halimi, 2011 (*Maccevethus lineola* Fabricius, 1787: Gërmenjë (18.IX.2009).

Note: According to Josifov (1970) and Kment & Baňar (2010), there is a possibility of confusion with *Maccevethus corsicus* Signoret, 1862.

***Maccevethus corsicus corsicus* Signoret, 1862**

Locations of records: Giri i Lalzit (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Josifov, 1970 (as *Maccevethus lutheri* Wagner, 1953): Tirana (IX.–XII.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Maccevethus lutheri* Wgn.): Vlorë (16.V.1969, 07.X.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Maccevethus lutheri* Wagner, 1953): Gj. Lalzit (03.IX.2008). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

[?] *Maccevethus errans* (Fabricius, 1794)

Locations of records: [?] Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); [?] Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: [?] Horváth, 1916 (as *Maccevethus lineola* var. *errans* Fabr.): Valona. [?] Mancini, 1953 (as *Macevethus* [sic] *lineola* F. *errans* F.): Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra).

Note: Josifov (1986) adds a question mark to *Maccevethus errans caucasicus* (Kolenati) for Albania. Kment & Baňar (2010) list the records of Horváth (1916) and Mancini (1953) as *Maccevethus caucasicus* (Kolenati, 1845).

***Rhopalus (Aeschyntelus) maculatus* (Fieber, 1837)**

Locations of records: Bicaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Giri i Lalzit (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); [?] Rrushkull (Mirditë, Qark Lezhë); [?] Rrushkull (Qark Durrës); [?] Rrushkull (Dajç, Qark Shkodër).

References: Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (05.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953: Bicaj, Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Rhopalus maculatus* (Fieber, 1836) [sic]): Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. [?] Misja, 1970: Rrushkull (06.V.1969). Halimi, 2011: Gj. Lalzit (03.IX.2008).

Note: The location ‘Ruskuli’ (Mancini, 1953) or ‘Rrushkull’ (Misja, 1970) is not clearly associated with any of the three Albanian villages named Rrushkull in Qark Lezhë, Qark Durrës and Qark Shkodër.

***Rhopalus (Rhopalus) lepidus* Fieber, 1861**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Ploshtan (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Tropojë (Qark Kukës).

Reference: Csiki, 1940 (as *Rhopalus parumpunctatus* ab. *rufus* Schill.): Tropoja (06.VIII.1917); Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918); Ploştan (29.VII.1918); Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m) [HNHM].

Note: According to Josifov's (1986) research, all Balkan specimens of *Rhopalus rufus* auct. non Schilling, 1829 are *Rhopalus lepidus* Fieber, 1861.

***Rhopalus (Rhopalus) parumpunctatus* Schilling, 1829**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Fushë Lurë

(Dibër, Qark Dibër); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ploshtan (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Pukë (Qark Shkodër); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkalla e Priskës (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Tomorr-Tyrbja e Abaz Aliut (Skrapar, Qark Berat); Tropojë (Qark Kukës); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Corizus parumpunctatus* Schill.): Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck); Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubasić, 1905); Berat (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Cukali, Oroshi, Berat. Royer, 1923: environs de Koritza [Korçë] (VIII, 1 ♂). Csiki, 1940 (as *Rhopalus parumpunctatus* Schill. and *Rhopalus parumpunctatus* ab. *subspeciosus* Schum.): Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918, 06.VII.1918); Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (13.VII.1918, 1000–1600 m); Tropoja (06.VIII.1917); Ploštan (29.VII.1918); Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Rhopalus parumpunctatus* Schill. and *Rhopalus parumpunctatus* var. *subspeciosus* Schum.): Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Puka (leg. Capra); Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Rhopalus parumpunctatus* (Schilling, 1817) [sic]): Vorberg des Dajti (07.IX.1959, leg. Klausnitzer); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (500 m, lux, 02.–12.VI.1961); Tomor, Kloster Abbas Ali (1800 m, 08.–10.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Dajti (Westhang, 1100 m, 29.VI.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi [Fushë Lurë] (19.–24.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Sh. Priskë (26.VI.1961). Halimi, 2011: Dajt (18.IX.2007). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

[?] *Rhopalus (Rhopalus) rufus* Schilling, 1829

Locations of records: [?] Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); [?] Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); [?] Ploshtan (Dibër, Qark Dibër); [?] Tropojë (Qark Kukës).

Reference: [?] Csiki, 1940 (as *Rhopalus parumpunctatus* ab. *rufus* Schill.): Tropoja (06.VIII.1917); Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918); Ploštan (29.VII.1918); Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m) [HNHM].

Note: See note on *Rhopalus lepidus* Fieber, 1861.

***Rhopalus (Rhopalus) subrufus* (Gmelin, 1790)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Krumë (Has, Qark Kukës); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lushnjë (Qark Fier); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Vermosh (Malësi e Madha, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Corizus subrufus* Gmel.): Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck); Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Cukali, Berat, Valona. Mancini, 1953: Elbassan, Kruma, Vermosa (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Lusnia (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Rhopalus subrufus* (Gmelin, 1788) [sic]): Tirana (09.–12.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Luzernefeld, 300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Unterwuchs in Apfelpflanzage, 350 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Tiranë (26.IV.1969); Vlorë (16.–25.V.1969). Halimi, 2011: Dajt (18.IX.2007); M. Robit (03.VIII.2008). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

Notes: Schumacher (1914) mentions a record from 'Poljana', which could refer to a location in Montenegro, Kosovo, or North Macedonia. Horváth (1916) mentions a record from 'Shar Dagh (Ljuboten)', which refers to the Šar Panina-Ljuboten mountain range between Kosovo and North Macedonia.

***Stictopleurus abutilon* (Rossi, 1790)**

Locations of records: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Shkozet (Rrogzhinë, Qark Tiranë); Tarabosh (Skodër, Qark Skodër); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Vermosh (Malësi e Madha, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Zall-Bastar (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Horváth, 1916: Valona. Royer, 1923: environs de Koritza [Korçë] (VII, 2 ♀). Csiki, 1940: Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (13.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953: Farabosk [sic; Tarabosh], Vermosa, Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1970: Tiranë (21.V.1968). Halimi, 2011: Dajt (25.IX.2007); Ibë (26.VII.2008); Shkozet (24.IX.2008). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Poliçan (17.VI.2022); Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022) [PCMG].

Note: We suppose that the locality 'Farabosk' mentioned by Mancini (1953) is a misspelling of Tarabosk, an old spelling of Tarabosh Mountain, located near the village of Shiroka in Qark Shkodër. The place 'Kavac' (Kavaç) mentioned by him is located in modern-day Montenegro.

***Stictopleurus crassicornis* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Këlcyrë (Qark Gjirokastër); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Zall-Bastar (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Csiki, 1940: Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m) [HNHM]. Misja, 1970: Tiranë (16.IV.1968); Këlcyrë (29.X.1968). Halimi, 2011: Ibë (26.VII.2008). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Poliçan (17.VI.2022); Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022) [PCMG].

***Stictopleurus pictus* (Fieber, 1861)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lukovë (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Tomorr-Tyrbja e Abaz Aliut (Skrapar, Qark Berat).

References: Josifov, 1970 (as *Stictopleurus abutilon pictus* (Fieber, 1861): Lukova nördlich Saranda (250 m, 24.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlora (SW-Hang mit *Pistacia* und *Phlomis*, 200–400 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea*-Macchie, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961); Tomor, Kloster Abbas Ali (1800 m, 08.–10.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Luzernefeld, 300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nord-albanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

***Stictopleurus punctatonervosus* (Goeze, 1778)**

Locations of records: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Këlcyrë (Qark Gjirokastër); Krrabë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lybeshë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Tomorr-Tyrbja e Abaz Aliut (Skrapar, Qark Berat).

References: Josifov, 1970: Tomor, Kloster Abbas Ali (1800 m, 08.–10.VI.1961); Iba

unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Këlcyrë (29.X.1968); Ibë (05.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Dajt (18.IX.2007); Kërrabë (24.VI.2008). Halimi et al., 2024: Lybesh (13.VI.2020) [NHMT].

***Stictopleurus subtomentosus* (Rey, 1888)**

Location of record: Korçë (Qark Korçë).

Reference: Misja, 1973 (as *Stictopleurus riveti* Rey [sic]): Korçë (01.VIII.1969) [NHMT].

[?] *Stictopleurus viridicatus* (Uhler, 1872)

Location of record: [?] Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: [?] Halimi et al., 2010; Halimi, 2011 (as *Stictopleurus nysioides* Reuter, 1891): Spille (27.IX.2007).

Note: The Albanian record requires verification, according to Aukema et al. (2013), as this species was previously only known from Kazakhstan, Central and Southern European Russia, and Ukraine on European territories.

RHOPALIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: RHOPALINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: CHOROSOMATINI Fieber, 1860

[?] *Agraphopus lethierryi* Stål, 1872

Location of record: ?

References: [?] Stichel, 1962: Albanien. [?] Josifov, 1970: Albanien [quoting from Stichel, 1962].

***Chorosoma schillingii* (Schilling, 1829)**

Locations of records: Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Këlcyrë (Qark Gjirokastrë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Chorosoma Schillingi* [sic] Schill.): Kula Ljums (02.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Chorosoma schillingii* [sic] Schill.): Elbassan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1970 (as *Chorosoma schillingii* [sic] Schill.): Këlcyrë (28.X.1968); Shkodër (16.VIII.1969). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Poliçan (17.VI.2022) [PCMG].

***Myrmus miriformis miriformis* (Fallén, 1807)**

Locations of records: Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Zvërnec (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

References: Misja, 1970 (as *Myrmus miriformis* Fall.): Golem (07.X.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Myrmus miriformis* Fallén, 1807): Golem (19.VII.2009). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zvërnec (14.VI.2022) [PCMG].

ALYDIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: MICRELYTRINAE Stål, 1868

***Micrelytra fossularum* (Rossi, 1790)**

Location of record: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI, ZISB].

ALYDIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: ALYDINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843

***Alydus calcaratus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Gërmenj (Skrapar, Qark Berat); Ploshtan (Dibër, Qark Dibër);

Shëngjin (Qark Lezhë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Coriscus calcaratus* L.): Ploštan (29.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Misja, 1970: Tiranë (06.IV.1969); Shëngjin (17.VI.1969). Halimi, 2011: Gërmenjë (18.IX.2009).

***Camptopus lateralis* (Germar, 1817)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Bicaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Hoçisht (Devoll, Qark Korçë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Krrabë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lezhë (Qark Lezhë); Lukovë (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Lybeshë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Mali i Corajt (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali me Gropë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Porto Romano (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Zall-Bastar (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Zvërnec (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

References: [?] Dallas, 1852 (as *Alydus lateralis* Germ.): Albania (British Museum London, leg. W. Wilson Saunders). Schumacher, 1914: Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck); Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck); Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubasić, 1905); Valona (leg. Patsch); Berat (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Cukali, Oroshi, Berat, Valona. Royer, 1923: environs de Koritza [Korçë] (VIII, 3 ♀). Csiki, 1940 (as *Camptopus lateralis* Germ. and *Camptopus lateralis* ab. *brevipes* H. S.): Kula Ljums (02.VII.1918, 03.VII.1918, 04.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Camptopus lateralis* Germ. and *Camptopus lateralis* var. *brevipes* H. S.): Kula Ljums, Bicaj, Biza, Porter [Porto Romano], Durrec, Elbassan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Vorberg des Dajti (07.IX.1959, leg. Klausnitzer); Durrës (Dolden-Wiese, 14.IX.1959, leg. Klausnitzer); Lukova nördlich Saranda (250 m, 24.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlora, Mali i Corajt (700–1100 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (Kulturland, 500 m, lux, 02.–12.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Mali me Gropë (Dolinengebiet, 1350 m, 06.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Ibë (06.VI.1968, 22.VI.1969); Lezhë (03.VII.1968); Vlorë (23.–27.V.1969); Korçë (03.VIII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Dajt (18.IX.2007); Kërrabë (24.VI.2008); Ibë (26.VII.2008). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Hoçisht (07.IX.2022); Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022); Zvërnec (14.VI.2022) [PCMG]. Halimi et al., 2024: Lybesh (03.IX.2019) [NHMT].

Note: Mancini (1953) mentions the town of 'Ferijovic', now known as Ferizaj (Ferizović, Uročevac) and located in Kosovo. Additionally, Mancini (1953) mentions the city of Prizren, which is also located in Kosovo.

COREIDAE Leach, 1815: PSEUDOPHLOEINAE Stål, 1868: PSEUDOPHLOEINI Stål, 1868

***Anoplocerus elevatus* (Fieber, 1861)**

Locations of records: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Krrabë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Misja, 1970: Vlorë (27.V.1969); Ibë (05.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Kërrabë (24.VI.2008).

***Arenocoris fallenii* (Schilling, 1829)**

Locations of records: Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Spille (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Pseudophloeus falleni* Schill.): Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (21.V.1969). Halimi, 2011: Spille (27.IX.2007).

***Arenocoris waltlii* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Misja, 1970 (as *Arenocoris waltlii* [sic] H. S.): Vlorë (25.V.1969).

***Bathysolen nubilus* (Fallén, 1807)**

Locations of records: Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

References: Royer, 1923: environs de Koritza [Korçë] (VI, 3 ♂). Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (08.VII.1918) [HNHM].

***Ceraleptus gracilicornis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Kepi i Rodonit (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Prenisht (Pogradec, Qark Korçë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916: Valona. Royer, 1923: Prénisti (1.000 m alt., V, 2 ♂). Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlorë (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Kulla e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (23.–27.V.1969). Halimi, 2011: K. Rodonit (21.V.2007).

Note: In addition to the above, Mancini (1953) also mentions an Albanian record from Prizren, a city located in present-day Kosovo.

***Ceraleptus obtusus* (Brullé, 1839)**

Locations of records: Himarë (Qark Vlorë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1973: Himarë (21.V.1970); Vlorë (27.V.1969) [NHMT].

***Coriomeris affinis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1839)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lezhë (Qark Lezhë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orikum (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Sukth (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Coriomeris spinolae* [sic] Costa), Valona. Mancini, 1953 (as *Coriomeris affinis* H. S. and *Coriomeris spinolae* Costa): Kula Ljums, Durrec, Shkodra (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Coriomeris affinis* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1839) and *Coriomeris spinolai* [sic] (Costa, 1847): Borshi südlich Vlorë (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea*-Macchie, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Coriomeris spinolai* [sic] varietet [sic]

fraudatrix Reut.): Ndroq (14.V.1968); Lezhë (17.VI.1968). Halimi, 2011: Sukth (22.VI.2009).

Note: Mancini (1953) mentions the locality 'Sisevo' (Šiševo, Shishovë), which is located in present-day North Macedonia.

***Coriomeris denticulatus* (Scopoli, 1763)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lezhë (Qark Lezhë); Maja e Madhe (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Tomorr-Tyrbja e Abaz Aliut (Skrapar, Qark Berat); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Cukali. Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Berat, Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea*-Macchie, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961); Tomor, Kloster Abbas Ali (1800 m, 08.–10.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshti, Maja e Madhe (1400–1789 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Apfelplantage, 350 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Lezhë (06.VII.1968); Vlorë (24.V.1969); Ibë (05.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Ibë (26.VII.2008).

***Coriomeris hirticornis* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Locations of records: Alipostivan, Mali i Tomorrit, Teqeja e Baba Aliut (Përmet, Qark Gjirokaster); Berat (Qark Berat); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kaninë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Mali i Corajt (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë); Zvërnec (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916: Valona, Kanina. Mancini, 1953: Berat (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlora, Mali i Corajt (700–1100 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlora (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea*-Macchie, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (25.V.1969). Halimi, 2011: Ibë (26.VII.2008); Vorë (24.V.2009). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Alipostivan (17.VI.2022); Zvërnec (14.VI.2022) [PCMG].

***Coriomeris scabricornis scabricornis* (Panzer, 1805)**

Location of record: Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër).

Reference: Mancini, 1953 (*Coriomeris scabricornis* Pnz): Korab (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

***Loxocnemis dentator* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Locations of records: Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).

References: Mancini, 1953: Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961) [SDEI].

***Strobilotoma typhaecornis* (Fabricius, 1803)**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916: Valona. Mancini, 1953: Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra). Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m,

14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI]. Halimi, 2011: Golem (19.VII.2009). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

***Ulmicola spinipes* (Fallén, 1807)**

Location of record: Bogë (Malësi e Madha, Qark Shkodër).

Reference: Kment et al., 2005: Bogë env. (42°24'N 19°38'E, 19.–21.VI.1994, leg. O. Hovorka, PKPC).

COREIDAE Leach, 1815: COREINAE Leach, 1815: ANISOSCELINI Laporte, 1832

***Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910**

Locations of records: Gërmenj (Barmash, Kolonjë, Qark Korçë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: van der Heyden, 2018b: Vlorë (phot. Aleksander Golemaj, 31.VIII.2018). Dhellemmes, 2021g: District de Kolonjë, Albanie (01.X.2021; N 40.225051 E 20.658522 [Gërmenj]).

COREIDAE Leach, 1815: COREINAE Leach, 1815: COREINI Leach, 1815

***Centrocoris spiniger* (Fabricius, 1781)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Krrabë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lapardha 1 (Berat, Qark Berat); Lezhë (Qark Lezhë); Lukovë (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Poshnjë (Dimal, Qark Berat); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Shkozet (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Zall-Bastar (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck); Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Oroshi, Valona. Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums, Biza (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra). Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (SW-Hang mit *Pistacia* und *Phlomis*, 200–400 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Lukova nördlich Saranda (250 m, 24.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea-Macchie*, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Lezhë (06.VII.1968); Vlorë (23.–24.V.1969); Korçë (05.VIII.1969); Velipojë (16.VIII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Dajt (25.VI.2008); Kërrabë (24.VI.2008); Ibë (26.VII.2008); Shkozet (24.IX.2008). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022) [PCMG]. Halimi et al., 2024: Poshnje (23.VII.2019); Lapardha (01.VIII.2019) [NHMT].

***Centrocoris variegatus* Kolenati, 1845**

Locations of records: Çermë e Poshtme (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vodice (Poliçan, Qark Berat).

References: Horváth, 1916: Valona. Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Halimi, 2011: Cermë (22.IX.2008). Halimi et al., 2024: Vodic (17.V.2020) [NHMT].

***Coreus marginatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Hoçisht (Devoll, Qark Korçë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës);

Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Parku Kombëtar i Qafshamës (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Peshtan (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Pukë (Qark Shkodër); Prenisht (Pogradec, Qark Korçë); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Seman (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Tomorr-Tyrbja e Abaz Aliut (Skrapar, Qark Berat); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër); Vorë (Qark Tiranë); Zharrëz (Patos, Qark Fier).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Syromastes marginatus* L.): Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck); Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck); Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Mesocerus marginatus* L.): Cukali, Oroshi. Royer, 1923 (*Mesocerus marginatus* L.): Prénisti (1.000 m alt., V, 1 ♂). Csiki, 1940 (as *Mesocerus marginatus* L.): Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918, 05.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Mesocerus marginatus* L.): Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Puka (leg. Capra); Qukes, Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Uji Ftohte südllich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea*-Macchie, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961); Tomor, Kloster Abbas Ali (1800 m, 08.–10.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Unterwuchs in Apfelplantage, 350 m, 25.–29.VII.1961); Durrës (Dolden Wiese, 09.IX.1959, leg. Klausnitzer) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Ibë (08.VI.1968); Vorë (26.VI.1969); Qafë-Shtamë (04.X.1969). Halimi et al., 2018: Zharëza, Seman (V.–IX.2015–2017). Halimi, 2011 (as *Coreus (Mesocerus) marginatus* Linnaeus, 1758): Ibë (26.VII.2008). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Hoçisht (07.IX.2022) [PCMG]. Halimi et al., 2024: Peshtan (10.VIII.2019) [NHMT].

Notes: Horváth (1916) mentions a record from 'Shar Dagh (Ljuboten)', which refers to the mountain range Šar Panina-Ljuboten between Kosovo and North Macedonia. Mancini (1953) mentions the locality 'Hodzha' (Hoça e Qytetit), which is located in today's Kosovo.

***Enoplops scapha* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Locations of records: Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Rogozhinë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Coreus scapha* F.): Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Coreus scapha* Fabr.): Oroshi. Misja, 1970: Dajt (11.V.1965). Halimi, 2011: Rogozhinë (12.V.2008).

Note: Horváth (1916) also mentions an Albanian record from 'Shar Dagh (Ljuboten)', which refers to the mountain range Šar Panina-Ljuboten located between Kosovo and North Macedonia.

***Haploprocta sulcicornis* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Vlora (VII.1958, leg. Grebenščikov); Borshi südllich Vlora (SW-Hang mit *Pistacia* und *Phlomis*, 200–400 m, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI].

***Spathocera lobata* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1840)**

Location of record: Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës).

Reference: Csiki, 1940: Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (13.VII.1918, 1600–1800 m) [HNHM].

***Syromastus rhombeus* (Linnaeus, 1767)**

Locations of records: Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Hoçisht (Devoll, Qark Korçë); Kolonjë (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lukovë (Himarë, Qark Vlorë).

References: Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Josifov, 1970: Lukova nördlich Saranda (250 m, 24.V.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Korçë (05.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Farkë (13.VII.2009); Kolonjë (24.IX.2008). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Hoçisht (07.IX.2022) [PCMG].

COREIDAE Leach, 1815: COREINAE Leach, 1815: GONOCERINI Mulsant & Rey, 1870

***Gonocerus acuteangulatus* (Goeze, 1778)**

Locations of records: Gjiri i Kakomesë (Sarandë, Qark Vlorë); Kodrat e Krujë (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Krumë (Has, Qark Kukës); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Patos (Qark Fier); Pukë (Qark Shkodër).

References: Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953: Kruma, Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Puka (leg. Capra). Misja, 1973: Kokome (Sarandë) (31.X.1970) [NHMT]. Halimi, 2011: K. Krujë (12.V.2008). Halimi et al., 2018: Patos (V.–IX.2015–2017).

Note: Mancini (1953) additionally mentions the locality 'Sisevo' (Šiševo, Shishovë), which is located in present-day North Macedonia.

***Gonocerus insidiator* (Fabricius, 1787)**

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: van der Heyden, 2017b: Vlorë (phot. Aleksander Golemaj, 07.VII.2017, 10.VIII.2017).

***Gonocerus juniperi* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1839**

Locations of records: Gërmenj (Barmash, Kolonjë, Qark Korçë); Hotolisht (Librazhd, Qark Elbasan); Krrabë e Vogël (Funarë, Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Pëllumbas (Bërzhitë, Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Sanjollas (Barmash, Kolonjë, Qark Korçë); Zvernëc, Laguna e Nartës (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Dhellemmes, 2021d: District de Kolonjë, Albanie (01.X.2021; N 40.26206 E 20.593188 [Sanjollas], N 40.224932 E 20.658708 [Gërmenj], and N 40.224967 E 20.65874 [Gërmenj]). Van der Heyden et al., 2024: Tirana county (Mount Dajti, 22.V.2020, N 41.211368 E 19.56114, 1 adult, on *Juniperus oxycedrus*. 24.IX.2021, N 41.233605 E 19.964944 [Pëllumbas], 1 adult). Vlorë County (25.IX.2021, N 40.564665 E 19.385827 [Zvernëc, Laguna e Nartës], 1 adult). Korçë County (01.X.2021, N 40.224966 E 20.658739 and N 40.224931 E 20.658708 [Gërmenj], 2 adults. 01.X.2021 N 40.26206 E 20.593188 and N 40.261583 E 20.593736 [Sanjollas], 1 adult, 1 nymph). Elbasan County (03.X.2021, N 41.146686 E 20.379963 [Hotolisht], 1 adult and 03.X.2021, N 41.192807 E 19.997900 [Krrabë e Vogël], 1 adult).

***Plinactus imitator* (Reuter, 1891)**

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: van der Heyden, 2017c: Vlorë (phot. Aleksander Golemaj, 26.IX.2016 and 23.XI.2016).

COREIDAE Leach, 1815: COREINAE Leach, 1815: PHYLLMORPHINI Mulsant & Rey, 1870

[?] *Phyllomorpha lacerata* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835

Location of record: ?

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Albanien?. [?] Josifov, 1986: Albanien.

Note: See the note on *Phyllomorpha laciniata* (Villers, 1789) for Schumacher's (1914)

record of this species.

***Phyllomorpha laciniata* (Villers, 1789)**

Locations of records: Bicaĵ (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë).

References: Dallas, 1852: Albania [?] (British Museum London, leg. W. Wilson Saunders). Schumacher, 1914 (as *Phyllomorpha lacerata* H.S. [Horváth, 1916: Misidentification of *Phyllomorpha laciniata* (Viller, 1789)]): Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck). Horváth, 1916: Oroshi. Mancini, 1953: Bicaĵ (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

Note: Mancini (1953) also mentions an Albanian record from ‘Ohret’. This can only be the city of Ohrid, located in North Macedonia.

Infraorder: PENTATOMOIDEA Leach, 1815

CYDNIDAE Billberg, 1820: CYNINAE Billberg, 1820: CYDNINI Billberg, 1820

***Cydnus aterrimus* (Forster, 1771)**

Locations of records: Alipostivan, Mali i Tomorrit, Teqeja e Baba Aliut (Përmet, Qark Gjirokaster); Ardenica (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Bicaĵ (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Llogara (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Ploshtan (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Brachypelta aterrima* Forst.): Ardenica (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Ardenica, Valona. Csiki, 1940 (as *Brachypelta aterrima* Forst.): Ploštan (29.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953: Bicaĵ (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1973: Llogara (II.–V.1971) [NHMT]. Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Alipostivan (17.VI.2022) [PCMG].

Note: Schumacher (1914) also mentions an Albanian record from ‘Peristeri’. This locality may refer to Baba or Pelister mountain range in North Macedonia, or to one of the many places with this name in Greece.

CYDNIDAE Billberg, 1820: CYDNINAE Billberg, 1820: GEOTOMINI Wagner, 1963

***Geotomus brunnipennis* Wagner, 1953**

Location of record: Mes (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

Reference: Wagner, 1953: Skutari Mesi.

***Geotomus ciliatitylus* Signoret, 1881**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë)

Reference: Horváth, 1916: Berat, Valona.

***Geotomus elongatus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1840)**

Locations of records: Pulaj (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Misja, 1973: Tiranë (II.–VII.1972) [NHMT]. Protić, 2007: Pulaj (Land Museum of Bosnia-Herzegovina in Sarajevo) [ZMBH].

***Geotomus punctulatus* (A. Costa, 1847)**

Locations of records: Apollonia (Fier, Qark Fier); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916: Velipoja, Sop [Appollonia], Valona. Royer, 1922: plaine de Koritza [Korçë] (IX, 1 ♀). Mancini, 1953: Scutari [Shkodër] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (17.V.1969).

***Macroscytus brunneus* (Fabricius, 1803)**

Location of record: Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

Reference: Horváth, 1916: Velipoja.

CYDNIDAE Billberg, 1820: SEHIRINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: SEHIRINI Amyot & Serville, 1843

***Adomerus biguttatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Location of record: Parku Kombëtar i Luginës së Valbonës (Tropojë, Qark Kukës).

Reference: Gailhampshire, 2018b: Valbona National Park. Albanian Alps (04.VI.2018).

Note: Aukema et al. (2013) cite Misja (1973), who in turn refers to Csiki (1940). However, Csiki (1940) refers to a place called 'Ipek' (Turkish), which is now known as Pejë, Peja (Albanian) or Peć (Serbo-Croatian) and is located in present-day Kosovo.

***Canthophorus dubius dubius* (Scopoli, 1763)**

Locations of records: Kunora e Lunës (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Sehirus dubius* Scop.): Korab, Pashtrik, Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Canthophorus dubius* (Scopoli, 1763)): Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Knora e Lurës (1400–2000 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Halimi, 2011 (as *Canthophorus dubius* Scopoli, 1763): Vorë (24.V. 2009).

Note: Mancini (1953) mentions the locality 'Durmitor', which could refer to either a mountain range in northwestern Montenegro or a hill in Serbia.

***Canthophorus impressus impressus* (Horváth, 1880)**

Locations of records: Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Maliq (Qark Korçë); Mirditë (Qark Lezhë); Peshkopi (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Tropojë (Qark Kukës); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Sehirus dubius* Scop. var. *impressus* Horv.): Merdita (Munela). Csiki, 1940 (as *Sehirus dubius* ab. *impressus* Horv.): Tropoja (06.VIII.1917); Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (14.VII.1918, 2000–25000 m); Montes Korab (25.II.1918, 1900 m) [HNHM]. Misja, 1973: Maliq (30.VII.1970); Peshkopi (13.IX.1970) [NHMT]. Halimi, 2011 (as *Canthophorus impressus* Horváth [sic], 1881 [sic]): Vorë (24.V. 2009).

***Canthophorus melanopterus melanopterus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

Locations of records: Pukë (Qark Shkodër); Shtiqën (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Tropojë (Qark Kukës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Sehirus dubius* Scop. var. *melanopterus* H.–Sch. []): Valona. Csiki, 1940 (as *Sehirus dubius* ab. *melanopterus* H.S.): Tropoja, Sticen [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Sehirus dubius* Scop. var. *melanopterus* H. S.): Puka (leg. Capra). Misja, 1970 (as *Canthophorus melanopterus* H. S.): Vlorë (09.–29.V.1969).

***Legnotus fumigatus* (A. Costa, 1853)**

Locations of records: Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Gnathoconus picipes* Fall. var. *fumigatus* Costa): Skutari [Shkodër] (leg. Latif Buljubasić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Gnathoconus picipes* Fall. var. *fumigatus* Costa): Skutari [Shkodër]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Legnotus fumigatus* (Costa, 1855) [sic]): Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Legnotus limbosus* (Geoffroy, 1785)**

Locations of records: Han i Hotit (Malësi e Madha, Qark Shkodër); Maja e Koret (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Gnathoconus limbosus* Geoffr.): Kjore [Maja e Koret]. Mancini, 1953: Han Hotit (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

***Legnotus picipes* (Fallén, 1807)**

Location of record: Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Lurja östlich Kurbneshi (9.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Ochetostethus balcanicus* Wagner, 1940**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poliçan (Qark Berat).

Reference: Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (02.–12.VI.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI].

***Ochetostethus opacus* (Scholtz, 1847)**

Locations of records: Korçë (Qark Korçë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Ochetostethus nanus* H. Sch.): Skutari [Shkodër] (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Royer, 1922 (as *Ochetostethus nanus* H.–S.): environs de Koritza [Korçë] (VIII, 1 ♀).

Note: Lis (2006) states that records of *Ochetostethus nanus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1834) outside the southwestern Mediterranean should be considered misidentifications of *O. opacus* (Scholtz, 1847).

***Sehirus luctuosus* Mulsant & Rey, 1866**

Locations of records: Kodrat e Krujës (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Liqeni i Madh i Buni Jezercës (Qark Shkodër).

References: Mancini, 1953: Buna Jersece (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Halimi, 2011: K. Krujës (12.V.2008).

***Sehirus morio* (Linnaeus, 1761)**

Locations of records: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër).

References: Csiki, 1940: Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m) [HNHM]. Misja, 1970: Ibë (18.V.1960).

[&] *Tritomegas bicolor* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Note: Aukema et al. (2013) cite Misja (1973), who in turn refers to Csiki (1940). The localities 'Ipek' (Turkish), now Pejë, Peja (Albanian) or Peć (Serbo-Croatian), and 'Deçani' are given there, both of which are located in present-day Kosovo.

***Tritomegas sexmaculatus* (Rambur, 1839)**

Locations of records: Durrës (Qark Durrës); Korçë (Qark Korçë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Sehirus sexmaculatus* Ramb.): Durazzo (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Sehirus sexmaculatus* Ramb.): Durazzo. Royer, 1922 (as *Canthophorus sexmaculatus* Ramb.): Koritza [Korçë] (VII, 1 ♂, 1 ♀).

Note: Schumacher (1914) mentions the locality 'Janina', which is now known as the city of Ioannina (Albanian Janinë, Janina) and is located in Greece.

PLATASPIDAE Dallas, 1851: COPTOSOMATINAE Kirkaldy, 1909

***Coptosoma mucronatum* Seidenstücker, 1963**

Location of record: Maliq (Qark Korçë).

Reference: Misja, 1973: Maliq (01.VIII.1970) [NHMT].

***Coptosoma scutellatum* (Geoffroy, 1785)**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ura Lapaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

References: Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918); Lušna: Ura i Lopez [Ura Lapaj] (21.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (SW-Hang, 200–400 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Ibë (05.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Petrelë (12.VI.2009).

ACANTHOSOMATIDAE Signoret, 1864: ACANTHOSOMATINAE Signoret, 1864

***Acanthosoma haemorrhoidale haemorrhoidale* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës).

Reference: Mancini, 1953 (as *Acanthosoma haemorrhoidale* L.): Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës], Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

***Cyphostethus tristriatus* (Fabricius, 1787)**

Location of record: Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Oroshi.

***Elasmucha grisea grisea* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Elasmucha grisea* L.): Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Misja, 1970 (as *Elasmucha betulae* Deg.): K. Lumës (30.VII.1961).

SCUTELLERIDAE Leach, 1815: ELVISURINAE Stål, 1872

***Solenosthedium bilunatum* (Lefebvre, 1827)**

Location of record: Gjiri i Kakomesë (Sarandë, Qark Vlorë).

Reference: Misja, 1973: Kokome (Sarandë) (31.X.1970) [NHMT].

SCUTELLERIDAE Leach, 1815: ODONTOTARSINAE Mulsant & Rey, 1865: ODONTOTARSINI Mulsant & Rey, 1866

[?] *Odontotarsus obsoletus obsoletus* Horváth, 1906

Locations of records: [?] Korçë (Qark Korçë); [?] Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

References: [?] Royer, 1922 (as *Odontotarsus purpureolineatus* Rossi var. *obsoletus* Horv.): environs de Koritza [Korçë] (VII, 1 ♂, 1 ♀). [?] Csiki, 1940 (as *Odontotarsus purpureolineatus* Rossi ab. *obsoletus* Horv.): Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918) [HNHM].

Note: Based on its distribution in Central Asia (Linnavuori, 2008), the above citations are most likely referring to *Odontotarsus purpureolineatus* (Rossi, 1790).

***Odontotarsus purpureolineatus* (Rossi, 1790)**

Locations of records: Alipostivan, Mali i Tomorrit, Teqeja e Baba Aliut (Përmet, Qark Gjirokaster); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Zall-Bastar (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Odontotarsus robustus* Jak.): Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Oroshi. Mancini, 1953: Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea-Macchie*, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkallë

Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Alipostivan (17.VI.2022); Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022) [PCMG].

***Odontotarsus robustus* Jakovlev, 1884**

Locations of records: Darëzezë e Re (Qark Fier); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Krrabë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Lukovë (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Peshtan (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Sarandë (Qark Vlorë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë); Zharrëz (Patos, Qark Fier).

References: Mancini, 1953: Elbassan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Durrës (Ödland, 06.IX.1959, leg. Klausnitzer); Lukova nördlich Saranda (250 m, 24.V.1961); Saranda (28.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (16.–29.V.1969); Vorë (22.VI.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Odontotarsus robustus* Jakovleff [sic], 1883 [sic]: Dajt (25.VI.2007); Kërrabë (24.VI.2008); Ibë (26.VII.2008). Halimi et al., 2018 (*Odontotarsus robustus* Jakoeleff [sic], 1883 [sic]): Zharëza, Darzezë (V.–IX.2015–2017). Halimi et al., 2024: Peshtan (13.IX.2019) [NHMT].

***Odontotarsus rufescens* Fieber, 1861**

Locations of records: Hamallaj (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Misja, 1970 (as *Odontotarsus caratasensis* [sic] Hb.): Vlorë (16.–29.V.1969); Vorë (22.VI.1969). Halimi, 2011 (*Odontotarsus karatasensis* Hoberlandt, 1937 [sic]): Hamallaj (14.VIII.2008).

SCUTELLERIDAE Leach, 1815: ODONTOSCELINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843

***Odontoscelis (Odontoscelis) byrrhus* Seidenstücker, 1972**

Location of record: ?

Reference: Göllner-Scheiding, 1986: Albanien!

***Odontoscelis (Odontoscelis) fuliginosa* (Linnaeus, 1761)**

Locations of records: Jonufër (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Mirakë (Librazhd, Qark Elbasan); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës); Ploshtan (Dibër, Qark Dibër).

References: Csiki, 1940: Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (20.VIII.1917, 1200 m); Ploştan (28.VII.1918), Montes Korab (22.VII.1918, 1000–1700 m; 28.VII.1918, 1750 m) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953: Pashtrik, Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1973: Jonufër (14.V.1971) [NHMT]. Halimi, 2011: Mirakë (29.VII.2009).

***Odontoscelis (Odontoscelis) lineola* Rambur, 1839**

Location of record: [?] Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

Reference: [?] Csiki, 1940 (as *Odontoscelis dorsalis* F.): Kula Ljums (17.VII.1918) [HNHM].

Note: Based on current knowledge, *Odontoscelis dorsalis* (Fabricius, 1798) is distributed from central Asia through North Africa to tropical Africa. Although Csiki (1940) listed this species for Albania, it is likely that he had *Odontoscelis dorsalis* var. *carbonaria* Kormilev, 1939 in hand, which Göllner-Scheiding (1986) synonymised with *Odontoscelis lineola* Rambur, 1839.

[?] *Odontoscelis (Odontoscelis) signata* Fieber, 1861

Location of record: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Misja, 1970 (*Odontoscelis signata* Ramb. [sic]): Ibë (17.VI.1964).

Note: According to Aukema et al. (2013) the record from Albania needs confirmation.

SCUTELLERIDAE Leach, 1815: EURYGASTRINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: EURYGASTRINI Amyot & Serville, 1843

***Eurygaster austriaca* (Schrank, 1776)**

Locations of records: Darëzezë e Re (Qark Fier); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Lybeshë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Royer, 1922: environs de Koritza [Korçë] (V–VI, 3 ♀). Mancini, 1953: Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Eurygaster austriaca* (Schrank, 1778) [sic]): Poliçan westlich Tomor (Kulturland, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Eurygaster austriacus* [sic] Schrk.): Vorë (02.V.1969); Ibë (05.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Eurygaster austriaca* Schrank, 1778 [sic]): Vorë (24.V.2009). Halimi et al., 2018 (as *Eurygaster austriaca* Schrank, 1778 [sic]): Darëzezë (V.–IX.2015–2017). Halimi et al., 2024: Lybesh (13.VI.2020) [NHMT].

***Eurygaster dilaticollis* Dohrn, 1860**

Locations of records: Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Tomorr-Tyrbja e Abaz Aliut (Skrapar, Qark Berat).

References: Wagner, 1951 (as *Eurygaster schreiberi marginella* Wagner, 1951): Pashtrik. Josifov, 1970 (as *Eurygaster schreiberi* Montandon,): Tomor, Kloster Abbas Ali (1800 m, 08.–10.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Poliçan (17.VI.2022) [PCMG].

Note: Josifov (1981) regarded *Eurygaster dilaticollis* Dohrn, 1860 and *Eurygaster schreiberi* Montandon, 1885 as different species. Later (Josifov, 1986), however, he considered them synonymous, as also suggested by Göllner-Scheiding (2006).

***Eurygaster integriceps* Puton, 1881**

Locations of records: Rrashbull (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Valona. Halimi, 2011: Rrashbull (14.VIII.2008).

***Eurygaster maura* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Ardenica (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Berat (Qark Berat); Dukat (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Hoçisht (Devoll, Qark Korçë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Krabbe (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Lybeshë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Roskovec (Qark Fier); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë); Zvërnec (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

References: [?] Dallas, 1851 (as *Eurygaster maurus* [sic] Linn.): Albania (British Museum London; leg. W. Wilson Saunders). Horváth, 1916 (as *Eurygaster maura* L. and *Eurygaster maura* L. var. *picta* Fabr.): Berat, Valona, Dukati. Mancini, 1953 (as *Eurygaster maurus* [sic] L.): Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (Kulturland, 500 m, 12.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Eurygaster maurus* [sic] L.): Vorë (07.V.1968); Ibë (05.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Farkë (13.VII.2009). Halimi et al., 2018: Ardenica, Roskovec (V.–IX.2015–2017). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Hoçisht (07.IX.2022); Krabbe (16.VI.2022); Zvërnec (14.VI.2022) [PCMG]. Halimi et al., 2024: Lybesh (03.IX.2019) [NHMT].

***Eurygaster testudinaria* (Geoffroy, 1785)**

Locations of records: Hoçisht (Devoll, Qark Korçë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Papër (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Eurygaster testudinarius* [sic] Geoff., *Eurygaster testudinarius* [sic] var. *triguttata* Wagn., and *Eurygaster testudinarius* [sic] var. *cinerea* Rey): Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941); Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Kulla e Lumës bei Kukësi (Fluštal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Eurygaster testudinarius* [sic] Geoff.): Korçë (05.VIII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Papër (09.VIII.2008). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Hoçisht (01.VIII.2019) [PCMG].

Note: Mancini (1953) also mentions an Albanian record from ‘Rikavec’, a hill located in present-day Kosovo.

SCUTELLERIDAE Leach, 1815: EURYGASTRINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: PSACASTINI Mulsant & Rey, 1865

***Psacasta (Psacasta) exanthematica exanthematica* (Scopoli, 1763)**

Locations of records: Durrës (Qark Durrës); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Orikum (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Sukth (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Psacasta exanthematica* Scop.): Pashaliman [Orikum], Valona. Mancini, 1953 (as *Psacasia* [sic] *exantematica* [sic] Scop.): Durrec (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1970 (as *Psacasta axanthematica* [sic] Scop.): Ibë (05.VII.1969); Korçë (05.VIII.1969); Shkodër (17.VIII.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Psacasta exanthematica* Scopoli, 1763): Sukth (22.VI.2009).

PENTATOMIDAE Leach, 1815: ASOPINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843

***Picromerus bidens* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkalla e Priskës (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953: Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Misja, 1970: Sh. Priskë (26.VI.1961).

***Picromerus conformis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1841)**

Locations of records: Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Oroshi. Halimi, 2011 (as *Picromerus conformis* Herrich-Schäffer [sic], 1894 [sic]): Dajt (25.VI.2008). Halimi et al., 2014 (as *Picromerus conformis* Herrich-Schäffer, 1894 [sic]): Dajt, Vorë, Farkë (2008–2010).

***Picromerus nigridens* (Fabricius, 1803)**

Location of record: Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941).

***Rhacognathus punctatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Location of record: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës).

References: Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (06.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

***Troilus luridus* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Location of record: Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës).

Reference: Mancini, 1953: Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW].

***Zicrona caerulea* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kodrat e Krastës (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër).

References: Royer, 1922: environs de Koritza [Korçë] (VI, 1 ♀). Mancini, 1953 (as *Zicrona caerulea* [sic] L.): Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra). Misja, 1970: Ndroq (15.IV.1968); Ibë (12.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011: K. Krastës (24.VI.2008). Halimi et al., 2014: Farkë (2008–2010).

PENTATOMIDAE Leach, 1815: PENTATOMINAE Leach, 1815: AELIINI Douglas & Scott, 1865

***Aelia acuminata* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Darëzezë e Re (Qark Fier); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Parku Kombëtar i Qafshamës (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Rrashbull (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Seman (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastrë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vodicë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Vorë (Qark Tiranë); Zall-Bastar (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Zharrëz (Patos, Qark Fier); Zvërnec (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck); Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905); Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Cukali, Oroshi, Berat, Valona. Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Umgebung Durrës (Dolden-Wiese, 09.IX.1959, leg. Klausnitzer); Umgebung Durrës (Ödland, 06.IX.1959, leg. Klausnitzer); Borshi südlich Vlora (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkallë Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vorë (24.IV.1968); Tiranë (26.V.1968); Vlorë (19.V.1969); Qafë-Shtamë (04.X.1969); Korçë (01.–05.VIII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Dajt (18.IX.2007); Rashbull (14.VIII.2008). Halimi et al., 2014: Dajt, Ndroq (2008–2010). Halimi et al., 2018: Zharëza, Seman, Darëzezë (V.–IX.2015–2017). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022); Zvërnec (14.VI.2022) [PCMG]. Halimi et al., 2024: Vodic (13.VIII.2019); Peshtan (17.VI.2020) [NHMT].

***Aelia klugii* Hahn, 1833**

Locations of records: Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Aelia klugi* [sic] Hhn): Pashtrik (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Aelia klugi* [sic] Hahn, 1833): Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Halimi, 2011: Farkë (13.VII.2009).

Note: Mancini (1953) also mentions an Albanian record from ‘Rikavec’, a hill located in present-day Kosovo.

***Aelia rostrata* Boheman, 1852**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Miras-Qytezë (Devoll, Qark Korçë); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Qytezë (Devoll, Qark Korçë); Sauk (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Tropojë (Qark Kukës); Ura Lapaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Zall-Bastar (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck); Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Cukali, Valona. Royer, 1922: environs de Koritza [Korçë] (VI–VII, 4 ♂, 6 ♀). Csiki, 1940: Tropoja (01.VII.1917), Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918), Ura i Lopez [Ura Lapaj] (21.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953: Biza (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra); Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Wiesen in 1300 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Kulla e Lumës bei Kukësi (Unterwuchs in Apfelplantage, 350 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Tiranë (26.IV.1969); Saukë (13.IV.1961). Halimi, 2011: Farkë (13.VII.2009). Halimi et al., 2014: Ibë, Farkë (2008–2010). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Miras-Qytezë (03.IX.2019); Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022) [PCMG].

***Aelia virgata* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1841)**

Location of record: Shkozet (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Halimi, 2011: Shkozet (24.IX.2008).

***Neottiglossa bifida* (A. Costa, 1847)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orikum (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Horváth, 1916: Pashaliman [Orikum], Valona. Mancini, 1953: Biza (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961) [SDEI, ZISB]. Halimi, 2011: Farkë (13.VII.2009). Halimi et al., 2014: Vorë, Farkë (2008–2010).

***Neottiglossa leporina* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1830)**

Locations of records: Alipostivan, Mali i Tomorrit, Teqeja e Baba Aliut (Përmet, Qark Gjirokaster); Hoçisht (Devoll, Qark Korçë); Shkozet (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë); Zvërnec (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

References: Misja, 1970 (as *Neottiglossa* [sic] *leporina* H.–S.): Vorë (24.IV.1968); Vlorë (27.V.1969). Halimi, 2011: Shkozet (24.IX.2008). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Alipostivan (17.VI.2022); Hoçisht (07.IX.2022); Zvërnec (14.VI.2022) [PCMG].

***Neottiglossa lineolata* (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)**

Location of record: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Krrabë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

Reference: Halimi, 2011: Kërrabë (24.VI.2008); Ibë (26.VII.2008).

PENTATOMIDAE Leach, 1815: PENTATOMINAE Leach, 1815: ANTESTIINI Distant, 1902

***Dryadocoris apicalis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1842)**

Location of record: Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

Reference: van der Heyden, 2019: Vlorë (phot. Aleksander Golemaj, 01.VII.2018, 06.IV.2019, 04.VI.2019).

PENTATOMIDAE Leach, 1815: PENTATOMINAE Leach, 1815: CARPOCORINI Mulsant & Rey, 1866

***Antheminia lunulata* (Goeze, 1778)**

Locations of records: Divjakë (Qark Fier); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Parku Kombëtar i Qafshamës (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Shijak (Qark Durrës); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

Referendes: Mancini, 1953 (as *Carpocoris lunulatus* Goeze): Bazar Shiak (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1970: Vorë (23.–27.V.1969); Korçë (05.VIII.1969); Qafë-Shtamë (04.X.1969). Halimi, 2011: Divjakë (22.IX.2008).

***Antheminia varicornis* (Jakovlev, 1874)**

Locations of records: Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Zall-Bastar (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Dolycoris varicornis* Jak.): Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Dolycoris varicornis* Jak.): Velipoja, Valona. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (06.X.1969). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022) [PCMG].

***Carpocoris (Carpocoris) fuscispinus* (Boheman, 1851)**

Locations of records: Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Krrabë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Robit (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Shkëlzenit (Tropojë, Qark Kukës); Milot (Kurbini, Qark Lezhë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Shkozet (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Oroshi. Csiki, 1940: Montes Skölsen (02.VIII.1917, 1300 m) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Carpocoris pudicus* Poda var. *fuscispina* Boh.): Kula Ljums, Shkodra, Elbasan, Valona (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra), Qukes, Petrela, Miloti (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Misja, 1970: Tiranë (26.IV.1969, 23.IX.1969). Halimi, 2011: Kërrabë (24.VI.2008); Ibë (26.VII.2008); M. Robit (03.VIII.2008); Shkozet (24.IX.2008). Halimi et al., 2014: Ibë, Vorë (2008–2010).

***Carpocoris (Carpocoris) mediterraneus mediterraneus* Tamanini, 1958**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lukovë (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër); Zvërnec (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

References: Josifov, 1970 (as *Carpocoris mediterraneus* Tamanini, 1958): Vlora (VII.1958, leg. Grebenščikov); Umgebung Durrës (Ödland, 06.IX.1959, leg. Klausnitzer); Borshi südlich Vlora (SW-Hang mit *Pistacia* und *Phlomis*, 200–400 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Lukova nördlich Saranda (250 m, 24.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961); Dajti (Westhang, 1100 m, 29.VI.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961); Dajti, Shkallë Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Umgebung Shkodra (lux, 05.VIII.VIII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zvërnec (14.VI.2022) [PCMG].

Note: Synonymized by Ribes et al. (2007) with *Carpocoris (Carpocoris) fuscispinus*

(Boheman, 1851), restored by Lupoli et al. (2013).

Carpocoris (Carpocoris) melanocerus (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Krrabë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Peshtan (Poliçan, Qark Berat).

References: Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Coriomeris* [mistake] *melanocerus* (Mulsant & Rey, 1852): Bizë bei Shënnergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Halimi, 2011: Krrabë (24.VI.2008). Halimi et al., 2014: Ibë, Ndroq (2008–2010). Halimi et al., 2024: Peshtan (17.VI.2020) [NHMT].

Carpocoris (Carpocoris) pudicus (Poda, 1761)

Locations of records: Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër); [?] Korçë (Qark Korçë); [?] Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); [?] Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë).

References: [?] Horváth, 1916 (as *Carpocoris pudicus* Poda (*purpureipennis* Deg.)): Cukali, Oroshi. [?] Royer, 1922 (as *Carpocoris pudicus* Poda (*purpureipennis* De G.)): environs de Koritza [Korçë] (VI, 1 ♀). Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (06.VII.1918); Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (13.VII.1918, 16.VII.1918, 1000–1800 m) [HNHM]. Josifov, 1970: Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

Note: Horváth (1916) and Royer (1922) used *Carpocoris pudicus* (Poda, 1761) and *Carpocoris purpureipennis* (De Geer, 1773) as synonyms, making it unclear which one they are referring to.

Carpocoris (Carpocoris) purpureipennis (De Geer, 1773)

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Krrabë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Lybeshë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Milot (Kurbini, Qark Lezhë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Peshtan (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Shkozë (Rrogzhinë, Qark Tiranë); Spille (Rrogzhinë, Qark Tiranë); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Tropojë (Qark Kukës); Ura Lapaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë); Zall-Bastar (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck); Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905); Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck); Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. [?] Horváth, 1916 (as *Carpocoris pudicus* Poda (*purpureipennis* Deg.)): Cukali, Oroshi. [?] Royer, 1922 (as *Carpocoris pudicus* Poda (*purpureipennis* Deg.)): environs de Koritza [Korçë] (VI, 1 ♀). Csiki, 1940 (as *Carpocoris pudicus* Poda ab. *pyrrhosoma* [sic] Westh.): Tropoja (01.VIII.1917), Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918), Ura i Lopez [Ura Lapaj] (21.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Carpocoris pudicus* Poda var. *pyrrhosoma* [sic] Nesth. [sic]): Petrela, Miloti (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Bizë bei Shënnergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nord-albanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Carpocoris purpureipennis* [sic] Deg.): Tiranë (20.IV.1969); Vlorë (22.V.1969); Vorë (14.VI.1969). Halimi, 2011: Dajti (18.IX.2007); Krrabë (24.VI.2008); Vorë (24.V.2009); Spille (27.IX.2007); Shkozë (24.IX.2008). Halimi et al., 2014: Ibë, Vorë (2008–2010). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022) [PCMG]. Halimi et al., 2024: Lybesh (10.VIII.2019); Peshtan (08.VIII.2019) [NHMT].

Note: See note on *Carpocoris* (*Carpocoris*) *pudivus* (Poda, 1761).

***Chlorochroa (Rhytidolomia) juniperina juniperina* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); [?] Rrushkull (Mirditë, Qark Lezhë); [?] Rrushkull (Qark Durrës); [?] Rrushkull (Dajç, Qark Shkodër).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Chlorochroa juniperina* L.): Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1970 (as *Pitedia juniperina* L.): Rrushkull [sic; see Note] (06.IV.1969).

Note: It is unclear which of the three Albanian villages named 'Rrushkull' is referred to by Misja, 1970.

***Chlorochroa (Rhytidolomia) pinicola* (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)**

Locations of records: Kodrat e Krujës (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Maja e Koret (Qark Vlorë); Tomorr-Tyrbja e Abaz Aliut (Skrapar, Qark Berat).

References: Horváth, 1916: Kjöre [Maja e Koret]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Pitedia pinicola* (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)): Kloster Abbas Ali (1800 m, 08.–10.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Halimi, 2011 (as *Pitedia pinicola* Mulsant & Rey, 1852): K. Krujës (12.V.2008).

***Codophila varia* (Fabricius, 1787)**

Locations of records: Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Lapardha 1 (Berat, Qark Berat); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Uznovë (Berat, Qark Berat); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Valona. Mancini, 1953: Varra [Vlorë] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970: Vlorë (VII.1958, leg. Grebenščikov) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (28.V.1969, 05.X.1969). Halimi, 2011: Dajt (18.IX.2007). Halimi et al., 2014: Dajt, Farkë (2008–2010). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017). Halimi et al., 2024: Uznovë (20.VII.2019); Lapardha (01.VIII.2019) [NHMT].

***Dolycoris baccharum* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Fushë Lurë (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Hoçisht (Devoll, Qark Korçë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Koplik (Malësi e Madha, Qark Shkodër); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Krumë (Has, Qark Kukës); Krrabë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lybeshë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Parku Kombëtar i Qafshatës (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ploshtan (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shëngjin (Qark Lezhë); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Shkozet (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Tomorr-Tyrbja e Abaz Aliut (Skrapar, Qark Berat); Tropojë (Qark Kukës); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastër); Uznovë (Berat, Qark Berat); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë); Zall-Bastar (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Zvërnec (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

References: [?] Dallas, 1851 (as *Pentatoma baccharum* Linn.): Albania (British Museum London; leg. W. Wilson Saunders). Schumacher, 1914: Oroshi (leg. Apfelbeck); Cukali-gebirge (leg. Apfelbeck); Valona (leg. Patsch). Horváth, 1916: Cukali, Oroshi, Valona [ZMBH]. Royer, 1922: environs de Koritza [Korçë] (VI, 1 ♀, VII, 4 ♂, 2 ♀). Csiki, 1940: Tropoja (04.VII.1917); Kulla Ljums (24.VIII.1917, 03.VII.1918, 05.VII.1918; 06.VII.1918); Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (19.VIII.1917, 1900–2300 m, 20.VIII.1917, 1150 m, 16.VII.1918, 1000–1600 m); Ploştan (29.VII.1918); Montes Korab (24.VIII.1917, 25.VIII.1917, 1500–1800 m, 24.VII.1918, 2200–2400 m, 26.VII.1918, 1800 m) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953: Kulla Ljums, Kruma (Mus. Vienna,

1914–1918) [NHMW]; Scutari [Shkodër], Kopliku (leg. Capra); Petrela, Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Umgebung Durrës (Ödland, 06.IX.1959, leg. Klausnitzer); Borshi südlich Vlora (14.–27.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Tomor, Kloster Abbas Ali (1800 m, 08.–10.VI.1961); Dajti (Südhang-Wiese, 900 m, 30.VI.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961); Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lure [Fushë Lurë] (Geröllhang in *Fagus-Abies*-Wald in 1350 m, 19.–24.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Ndroq (07.V.1968); Vorë (02.V.1968); Tiranë (16.IV.1969); Shëngjin (19.VI.1969); Ibë (05.VII.1969); Vlorë (16.–29.V.1969); Korçë (02.–05.VIII.1969); Qafë-Shtamë (04.X.1969). Halimi, 2011: Dajt (25.VI.2008, 18.IX.2007); Kërrabë (24.VI.2008); Shkozë (24.IX.2008). Halimi et al., 2014: Dajt, Ibë, Farkë (2008–2010). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Hoçisht (01.VIII.2019, 07.IX.2022); Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022); Zvërnec (14.VI.2022) [PCMG]. Halimi et al., 2024: Lybesh (08.VIII.2019); Uznov (07.V.2020) [NHMT].

***Enigmocoris fissiceps* (Horváth, 1906)**

Locations of records: Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Maminas (Shijak, Qark Durrës); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Misja, 1970 (as *Holcostethus fissiceps* Horv.): Maminas (08.VI.1968). Halimi, 2011 (as *Holcostethus fissiceps* Horváth [sic], 1906): Vorë (24.V.2009). Halimi et al., 2014 (*Holcostethus fissiceps* Horváth [sic], 1906): Vorë, Farkë (2008–2010).

***Holcogaster fibulata* (Germar, 1831)**

Locations of records: Kaninë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Sanjollas (Barmash, Kolonjë, Qark Korçë).

References: Horváth, 1916: Kanina. Josifov, 1970 (as *Holcogaster exilis* Horváth, 1903): Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea*-Macchie, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Dhellemmes, 2021f: District de Kolonjë, Albanie (01.X.2021; N 40.261577 E 20.593765 and N 40.261993 E 20.593363 [Sanjollas]).

***Holcostethus (Holcostethus) sphacelatus* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Parku Kombëtar i Qafshtamës (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Shkallë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Josifov, 1970: Dajti, Shkall Prisk (850 m, 27.VI.–02.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Qafë Shtamë (04.X.1969). Halimi, 2011: Dajt (25.V.2008). Halimi et al., 2014: Dajt, Ndroq (2008–2010).

***Palomena prasina* (Linnaeus, 1761)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Bradashesh (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Hoçisht (Devoll, Qark Korçë); Krumë (Has, Qark Kukës); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Mali me Gropë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Parku Kombëtar i Qafshtamës (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Pashtrikë (Has, Qark Kukës); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Oroshi. Mancini, 1953: Kruma, Pashtrik (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Csiki, 1940: Kulla Ljums (06.VII.1918), Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (Vallis Sija, 20.VIII.1917, 900 m) [HNHM]. Josifov, 1970: Mali me Gropë (Dolinengebiet, 1350 m, 06.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (Rotbuchenwald, 1400–1500 m, 10.–

15.VII.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Golem (09.VII.1965); Qafë Shtamë (04.X.1969). Halimi, 2011: Bradashesh (11.V.2007). Halimi et al., 2014: Vorë (2008–2010). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Hoçisht (07.IX.2022) [PCMG].

Peribalus (Peribalus) strictus strictus (Fabricius, 1803)

Locations of records: Durrës (Qark Durrës); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Peribalus strictus* F.): Kula Ljums, Elbassan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Holcostethus strictus* (Fabricius, 1803): Umgebung Durrës (Ödland, 06.IX.1959, leg. Klausnitzer); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Rabitsch, 2018 (as *Peribalus strictus* (Fabricius, 1803): Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

Peribalus (Peribalus) strictus vernalis (Wolff, 1804)

Locations of records: Këlcyrë (Qark Gjirokastrë); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Maminas (Shijak, Qark Durrës); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Parku Kombëtar i Qafshamës (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Rrashbull (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Shtiçën (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Peribalus vernalis* Wlff): Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905); Velipoja (leg. Mustajbeg Kurbegović, 1897–1898) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Peribalus vernalis* Wolff): Oroshi, Velipoja. Csiki, 1940 (as *Staria vernalis* Wolff): Stiçen (in radices Montibus Djalica Ljums, 9.VII.1918), Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës], 13.VII.1918, 1600–1800 m) [HNHM]. Misja, 1970 (as *Holcostethus vernalis* Wolff): Këlcyrë (28.X.1968); Maminas (08.VI.1968); Tiranë (26.IV.1969); Vorë (22.VI.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Holcostethus vernalis* Wolff, 1804): Rrashbull (14.VIII.2008). Halimi et al., 2014 (as *Holcostethus vernalis* Wolff, 1804): Vorë (2008–2010).

Staria lunata (Hahn, 1835)

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lybeshë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Maja e Koret (Qark Vlorë); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Parku Kombëtar i Qafshamës (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastrë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vodice (Poliçan, Qark Berat).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Cukali, Valona, Kjore [Maja e Koret]. Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918), Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (09.VII.1918, 1000–1600 m) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953: Kula Ljums, Elbassan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970: Vorberg des Dajti (07.IX.1959, leg. Klausnitzer); Borshi südl. Vlorë (14.–27.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südl. Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (*Arbutus-Phillyrea-Macchie*, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961); Dajti (Westhang, 1100 m, 29.VI.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (16.–29.V.1969); Qafë-Shtamë (04.X.1969). Halimi, 2011: Dajti (18.IX.2007). Halimi et al., 2014 (as *Staria lunata* Hahn [sic], 1835): Dajti, Ibë, Farkë (2008–2010). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017). Halimi et al., 2024: Vodice (17.V.2020); Lybesh (13.VI.2020) [NHMT].

PENTATOMIDAE Leach, 1815: PENTATOMINAE Leach, 1815: EYSARCORINI Mulsant & Rey, 1866

***Eysarcoris aeneus* (Scopoli, 1763)**

Locations of records: Durrës (Qark Durrës); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Markaj (Tropojë, Qark Kukës); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Horváth, 1916 (as *Eusarcoris* [sic] *aeneus* Scop.): Velipoja. Mancini, 1953 (as *Eusarcoris* [sic] *aeneus* Scop.): Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Umgebung Durrës (Ödland, 06.IX.1959, leg. Klausnitzer); Iba unterhalb Krraba (400 m, 17.–22.VI.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1973: Markaj (B. Curr) (27.VIII.1971) [NHMT].

***Eysarcoris ventralis* (Westwood, 1837)**

Locations of records: Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Shkozet (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Tropojë (Qark Kukës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë); Zall-Bastar (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Eusarcoris* [sic] *inconspicuus* H. Sch.): Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck); Valona (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Eusarcoris* [sic] *inconspicuus* H. Sch.): Cukali, Valona. Csiki, 1940 (as *Eusarcoris* [sic] *inconspicuus* H.–S.): Tropoja (01.VIII.1917), Kula Ljums (13.VIII.1917) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Eusarcoris* [sic] *inconspicuus* H. S.): Petrela, Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Misja, 1970 (as *Eusarcoris* [sic] *inconspicuus* H. S.): Vorë (29.IV.1968); Tiranë (03.V.1969); Vlorë (16.–28.V.1969); Korçë (02.VIII.1969); Shkodër (18.V.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Eysarcoris inconspicuus* [sic] Herrich-Schäffer [sic], 1844: Shkozet (24.IX.2008). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022) [PCMG].

Note: Breddin (1909) synonymised '*Eusarcoris conspicuus* Stål, auct.' with this species. He obviously intended '*Pentatoma inconspicuum* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1844'.

***Stagonomus amoenus* (Brullé, 1832)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Darëze e Re (Qark Fier); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Priskë e Madhe (Tirane, Qark Tirane); Pukë (Qark Shkodër); Rogozhinë (Qark Tiranë); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Cukali. Mancini, 1953: Puka (leg. Capra); Berat (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Stagonomus* (*Stagonomus*) *amoenus* (Brullé, 1832)): Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Priskë (26.VI.1961). Halimi, 2011: Rogozhinë (12.V.2009). Halimi et al., 2014: Dajt (2008–2010). Halimi et al., 2018: Darze e (V.–IX.2015–2017).

***Stagonomus bipunctatus bipunctatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Giri i Lalzit (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shëngjin (Qark Lezhë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Stagonomus bipunctatus* L.): Shen Gjin (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra). Misja, 1970 (as *Stagonomus* (*D*) [*Dalleria*] *bipunctatus* L.): Vlorë (29.V.1969); Ibë (05.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Stagonomus bipunctatus* Linnaeus, 1758): Gj. Lalzit (03.IX.2008). Halimi et al., 2014 (as *Stagonomus bipunctatus* Linnaeus, 1758): Dajt, Vorë, Ndroq (2008–2010).

***Stagonomus bipunctatus pusillus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1833)**

Locations of records: Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Misja, 1970 (as *Stagonomus* (*D*) [*Dalleria*] *pusillus* H.–S.): Ibë (05.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Stagonomus pusillus* Herrich-Schäffer [sic], 1830 [sic]): Ndroq (06.05.2007). Halimi et al., 2014 (as *Stagonomus pusillus* Herrich-

Schäffer [sic], 1830 [sic]: Ibë, Ndroq (2008–2010).

Note: It is plausible that this subspecies occurs in Albania. The list of Josifov (1986) probably omits it by mistake.

***Stagonomus venustissimus* (Schrank, 1776)**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Kepi i Rodonit (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Tropojë (Qark Kukës).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Eusarcoris* [sic] *venustissimus* Schrk.): Tropoja (03.VIII.1917) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Eusarcoris* [sic] *melanocephalus* F.): Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Eysarcoris fabricii* Kirkaldy, 1904): Borshi südlich Vlora (SW-Hang mit *Pistacia* und *Phlomis*, 200–400 m, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI]. Halimi, 2011 (as *Eysarcoris fabricii* Kirkaldy, 1904): K. Rodonit (21.V.2007).

PENTATOMIDAE Leach, 1815: PENTATOMINAE Leach, 1815: HALYINI Amyot & Serville, 1843

***Apodiphus amygdali* (Germar, 1817)**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Bradashesh (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Lezhë (Qark Lezhë); Lybeshë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Apodiphus Amygdali* [sic] Ger.): Oroshi. Mancini, 1953: Elbassan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Apodyphus* [sic] *amygdali* (Germar, 1817)): Vlora (VII.1958, leg. Grebenščikov); Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Lezhë (03.VII.1968); Vorë (22.VI.1969); Ibë (05.VI.1969). Halimi, 2011: Bradashesh (11.V.2007). Halimi et al., 2024: Lybesh (13.VI.2020) [NHMT].

***Erthesina fullo* Thunberg, 1783**

Locations of records: Durrës (Qark Durrës); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Lupoli et al., 2021: Durrës. Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Tiranë (27.III.2022; phot. Drita Kaleshi).

***Mustha spinosula* (Lefebvre, 1831)**

Locations of records: Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Himarë (Qark Vlorë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Krrabë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Lukovë (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Sherishtë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë). Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë); Zvërnec, Manasteri i Shën Mërisë (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916: Kishbarda [Sherishtë] (nympha). Mancini, 1953 (as *Musta* [sic] *spinulosa* Lef.): Tirana (coll. Mancini); Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Lukova nördlich Saranda (250 m, 24.V.1961); Himara (20.VII.1958, leg. Grebenščikov [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Ibë (04.VII.1965, 25.VI.1968, 05.VII.1969); Vorë (05.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Krrabë (24.VI.2008); Golem (19.VII.2009). Halimi et al., 2014: Dajt, Ibë (2008–2010). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zvërnec (14.VI.2022) [PCMG].

PENTATOMIDAE Leach, 1815: PENTATOMINAE Leach, 1815: PENTATOMINI Leach, 1815

***Acrosternum heegeri* Fieber, 1861**

Locations of records: Lushnjë (Qark Fier); Sanjollas (Barmash, Kolonjë, Qark Korçë).

References: Misja, 1973 (as *Acrosternum haegeri* [sic] Fieb.): Lushnjë (05.VIII.1971) [NHMT]. Dhellemmes, 2021a: District de Kolonjë, Albanie (01.X.2021; N 40.261712 E 20.593693 [Sanjollas]).

***Acrosternum millierei* (Musant & Rey, 1866)**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Sanjollas (Barmash, Kolonjë, Qark Korçë).

References: Josifov, 1970 (as *Acrosternum millierei* [sic] (Musant & Rey, 1866)): Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI]. Dhellemmes, 2021b: District de Kolonjë, Albanie (01.X.2021; N 40.262238 E 20.59333 [Sanjollas]).

***Nezara viridula* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Divjakë (Qark Fier); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Hoçisht (Devoll, Qark Korçë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Lezhë (Qark Lezhë); Lushnjë (Qark Fier); Lybeshë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shesh (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Uznovë (Berat, Qark Berat); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Nezara viridula* var. *smaragdula* F. and *Nezara viridula* var. *torquata* F.): Sesh (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Umgebung Durrës (Ödland, 02.IX.1959, leg. Klausnitzer); Shkodra (lux, 05.–08.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Lezhë (03.VI.1969); Vorë (21.V.1968); Lushnjë (31.X.1968); Tiranë (26.IV.1969). Halimi, 2011: Divjakë (22.IX.2008). Halimi et al., 2014: Ibë, Farkë, Ndroq (2008–2010). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Hoçisht (30.VII.2019) [PCMG]. Halimi et al., 2024: Uznov (15.VIII.2019); Lybesh (08.VIII.2019) [NHMT].

***Pentatoma (Pentatoma) rufipes* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Martanesh (Bulqizë, Qark Dibër); Papër (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan).

References: Misja, 1970: Martanesh (24.VII.1967); Bizë (28.VII.1966). Halimi, 2011: Papër (09.VIII.2008).

***Rhaphigaster nebulosa* (Poda, 1761)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Çermë e Poshtme (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poshnjë (Dimal, Qark Berat); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Poshnjë (Dimal, Qark Berat).

References: Mancini, 1953: Berat, Skutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941); Josifov, 1970: Tirana (Sommer 1942, leg. Bischoff [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Ibë (06.VI.1969); Tiranë (06.V.1969, 05.X.1969, 26.XI.1969). Halimi, 2011: Cerme (22.IX.2008). Halimi et al., 2024: Poshnje (20.VIII.2019); Vodice (17.V.2020) [NHMT].

PENTATOMIDAE Leach, 1815: PENTATOMINAE Leach, 1815: PIEZODORINI Atkinson, 1888

***Piezodorus lituratus* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Dardhë (Korçë, Qark Korçë); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Krrabë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Krumë (Has, Qark Kukës); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Pukë (Qark Shkodër); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Tropojë (Qark Kukës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Piezodorus lituratus* Fabr. and *Piezodorus lituratus* Fabr. var. *alliaceus* Germ.): Oroshi, Valona. Csiki, 1940 (as *Piezodorus lituratus* F. and *Piezodorus lituratus* F. var. *alliaceus* Germ.): Tropoja (01.VIII.1917); Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Piezodorus lituratus* F. and *Piezodorus lituratus* F. var. *alliaceus* Germ.): Berat, Skutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941); Durrec, Elbassan, Kruma, Dardha (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Puka (leg. Capra). Josifov, 1970: Tirana (Sommer 1942, leg. Bischoff); Vorberg des Dajti (07.IX.1959, leg. Klausnitzer); Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Luzernefeld, 300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Golem (10.VII.1968); Vlorë (16.–29.V.1969); Ibë (05.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Kërrabë (24.VI.2008); Ibë (26.VII.2008). Halimi et al., 2014: Ibë, Vorë (2008–2010).

PENTATOMIDAE Leach, 1815: PENTATOMINAE Leach, 1815: SCIOCORINI Amyot & Serville, 1843

***Dyrodere umbraclatus* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Locations of records: Golem (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Papër (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Rogozhinë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Misja, 1973: Golem (14.V.1970) [NHMT]. Halimi, 2011: Rogozhinë (12.V.2009); Papër (09.VIII.2008).

***Sciocoris (Aposciocoris) homalonotus* Fieber, 1851**

Locations of records: Kepi i Rodonit (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Velipojë (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916: Velipoja. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (27.V.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Sciocoris homalonotus* [sic] Fieber, 1852): K. Rodonit (21.V.2007).

***Sciocoris (Aposciocoris) macrocephalus* Fieber, 1851**

Locations of records: Lumi i Selitës (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Josifov, 1970 (as *Sciocoris (Aposciocoris) macrocephalus* Fieber, 1852 [sic]): Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: L. Selitës (03.VII.1961).

***Sciocoris (Aposciocoris) microphthalmus* Flor, 1860**

Locations of records: Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Cukali. Csiki, 1940: Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (13.VII.1918, 1600–1800 m), Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953: Korab (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970: Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (28.V.1969).

***Sciocoris (Sciocoris) cursitans cursitans* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Locations of records: Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ploshtan (Dibër, Qark Dibër); Pukë (Qark Shkodër); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Csiki, 1940 (as *Sciocoris cursitans* F.): Ploştan (28.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Sciocoris cursitans* F.): Puka (leg. Capra); Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Misja, 1970 (as *Sciocoris cursitans* F.): Vlorë (16.–29.V.1969).

***Sciocoris (Sciocoris) sulcatus* Fieber, 1851**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Peqin (Qark Elbasan); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Zall-Bastar (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953: Qukes (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlora (litorale Terrasse mit *Olea* und *Ficus*, 50–150 m, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1973: Korçë (26.VII.1970) [NHMT]. Halimi, 2011: Peqin (10.VIII.2008). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zall-Bastar (15.VI.2022) [PCMG].

PENTATOMIDAE Leach, 1815: PENTATOMINAE Leach, 1815: STRACHIINI Mulsant & Rey, 1866

***Bagrada (Nitilia) abeillei* Puton, 1881**

Locations of records: Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Parku Kombëtar i Qafshamës (Krujë, Qark Durrës); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Misja, 1970 (as *Bagrada obellei* [sic] Put.): Qafë-Shtamë (04.X.1969). Halimi, 2011: Dajt (18.IX.2007). Halimi et al., 2014: Dajt, Vorë (2008–2010).

***Eurydema (Eurydema) oleracea* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Buçimas (Pogradec, Qark Korçë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Llixhat e Elbasanit (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Parku Kombëtar i Qafshamës (Krujë, Qark Durrës).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Eurydema oleraceum* [sic] L.): Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Cukali. Royer, 1922 (as *Eurydema oleraceum* [sic] L. var. *flavatum* Schrk.): Stabova [sic; Starova see Buçimas, Tabel 1] (env. de Koritza) (VI–VII, 4 ♀). Csiki, 1940 (as *Eurydema oleraceum* [sic] L., *E. oleraceum* [sic] L. var. *flavatum* Schrk., *E. oleraceum* [sic] L. var. *consimile* Horv., *E. oleraceum* [sic] L. var. *confluens* Roy., and *E. oleraceum* [sic] L. var. *albomarginatum* Goeze): Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918, 05.VII.1918, 06.VII.1918); Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (20.VIII.1917, 1200 m, 13.VII.1918, 1000–1600 m); Montes Korab (26.VII.1918, 1800 m) [HNHM]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Eurydema oleraceum* [sic] (Linnaeus, 1758)): Bizë bei Shënjergji (Wiesen in Rotbuchenzone, 1400–1500 m, 10.–15.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Korçë (05.VIII.1969); Qafë-Shtamë (04.X.1969). Halimi, 2011: Llixha (26.20.2008).

***Eurydema (Eurydema) ornata* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lapardha 1 (Berat, Qark Berat); Lukovë (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Lybeshë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Maja e Korabit (Qark Dibër); Mali i Cukalit (Qark Shkodër); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Poliçan (Qark Berat); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Shtiqën (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Spille (Rrogzhinë, Qark Tiranë); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastrë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vorë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Schumacher, 1914 (as *Eurydema ornatum* L. and *E. festivum* L. var. *decoratum* H. Sch.): Valona (leg. Patsch); Cukaligebirge (leg. Apfelbeck); Orosi (leg. Apfelbeck); Berat (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Eurydema ornata* [sic] L., *E. festiva* L., and *E. festiva* L. var. *decorata* H.–Sch.): Berat, Valona, Cukali, Oroshi. Royer, 1922 (as *Eurydema festivum* L. and *E. festivum* L. var. *chloroticum* Horv.): environs de Koritza [Korçë] (VIII, 1 ♂, 1 ♀). Csiki, 1940 (as *Eurydema ornatum* [sic] L. var. *mehadiense* Horv., *E. ornatum* [sic] L. var. *decorata* H. S., and *E. ornatum* [sic] L. ab. *Christophi* [sic] Jak.): Montes Korab (22.VII.1918, 1000–1700 m); Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918, 05.VII.1918); Stiçen (in radices Montibus Djalica Ljums, 19.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Eurydema ornatum* [sic] L., *E. ornatum* [sic] L. var. *mehadiense* Horv., *E. ornatum* [sic] L. var. *picta* H. S., *E. ornatum* [sic] L. var. *decorata* H.

S., *E. ornatum* [sic] L. var. *christophi* Jak., and *Eurydema ornatum* [sic] L. var. *chlorotica* [sic] Horv.): Biza, Kula Ljums (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra); Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Eurydema ornatum* [sic] (Linnaeus, 1758)): Vlorë (VII.1958, leg. Grebenščikov); Borshi südlich Vlorë (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961); Lukova nördlich Saranda (250 m, 24.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Poliçan westlich Tomor (Kulturland, 500 m, 02.–12.VI.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Flußtal des Luma, 250–300 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vorë (29.IV.1968); Vlorë (26.V.1969); Tiranë (26.IV.1969); Korçë (05.VIII.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Eurydema ornate* [sic] Linnaeus, 1758): Spille (27.IX.2007). Halimi et al., 2014 (as *Eurydema ornate* [sic] Linnaeus, 1758): Dajt, Ibë, Farkë (2008–2010). Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017). Halimi et al., 2024: Lapardha (01.VIII.2019); Lybesh (13.VI.2020) [NHMT].

[A] *Eurydema (Horvatheurydema) fieberi* Schummel, 1837

Note: Aukema et al. (2013) cite Misja (1973), who in this case refers to Csiki (1940). There, however, it reads ‘Mitrovica’. This place is located in present-day Kosovo.

***Eurydema (Rubrodorsalium) spectabilis* Horváth, 1882**

Locations of records: Durrës (Qark Durrës); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Mancini, 1953 (as *Eurydema spettabile* [sic] Horv.): Durrec (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (29.V.1969).

***Eurydema (Rubrodorsalium) ventralis* Kolenati, 1846**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë).

References: Mancini, 1953: Scutari [Shkodër] (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Josifov, 1970 (as *Eurydema ventrale* [sic] Kolenati, 1846): Tirana (09.–12.V.1961); Borshi südlich Vlorë (Flußtal des Lumi i Borshi, 14.–27.V.1961) [SDEI].

PENTATOMIDAE Leach, 1815: PODOPINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: GRAPHOSOMATINI Mulsant & Rey, 1865

***Ancyrosoma leucogrammes* (Gmelin, 1790)**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Byshek (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Durrës (Qark Durrës); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Marikaj (Vorë, Qark Tiranë); Milot (Kurbini, Qark Lezhë); Orikum (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Rrashbull (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Shtiqën (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelene (Tepelene, Qark Gjirokastrë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Zvërnec (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë).

References: Horváth, 1916: Pashaliman [Orikum], Valona. Csiki, 1940 (as *Ancyrosoma leucogramma* [sic] Gmel.): Stiçen (in radices Montibus Djalica Ljums, 09.VII.2018) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Ancyrosoma albolineatum* F.): Kula Ljums, Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës], Elbasan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra); Petrela, Miloti (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Ancyrosoma leucogrammes* (Gmelin, 1789) [sic]): Durrës (Dolden-Wiese, 14.IX.1959, leg. Klausnitzer); Borshi südlich Vlorë (SW-Hang, 200–400 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Kula e Lumës bei Kukësi (Unterwuchs in Apfelplantage, 350 m, 25.–29.VII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970: Vlorë (06.–29.V.1969); Marikaj (04.VII.1969); Durrës (18.VII.1969); Shkodër (17.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011: Rashbull (14.VIII.2008), Byshek (18.VII.2009). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Zvërnec (14.VI.2022) [PCMG].

Note: Mancini (1953) also mentions ‘Uskub’ as a record location. Uskub is the Turkish

name for Skopje, today's capital of North Macedonia.

***Derula flavoguttata* Mulsant & Rey, 1856**

Locations of records: Borsh (Himarë, Qark Vlorë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Miras-Qytezë (Devoll, Qark Korçë); Qytezë (Devoll, Qark Korçë); Tragjas (Vlorë, Qark Vlorë); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastrë)

References: Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918) [HNHM]. Josifov, 1970: Borshi südlich Vlorë (SW-Hang mit *Pistacia* und *Phlomis*, 200–400 m, 14.–27.V.1961); Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1973: Tragjas (10.V.1972) [NHMT]. Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Miras-Qytezë (03.IX.2019) [PCMG].

***Graphosoma (Graphosoma) italicum italicum* (O.F. Müller, 1766)**

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Bizë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Darëzeze e Re (Qark Fier); Elbasan (Qark Elbasan); Han i Grabomit (Malësi e Madha, Qark Shkodër); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Kulla e Lumës (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Lybeshë (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Mali i Gjalicës (Qark Kukës); Maminas (Shijak, Qark Durrës); Orosh (Mirdita, Qark Lezhë); Peshtan (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Qukës (Përrenjas, Qark Elbasan); Selitë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Seman (Lushnjë, Qark Fier); Shkodër (Qark Shkodër); Shkozë (Rrogozhinë, Qark Tiranë); Theth (Shkodër, Qark Shkodër); Tiranë (Qark Tiranë); Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (Tepelenë, Qark Gjirokastrë); Ura Lapaj (Kukës, Qark Kukës); Uznovë (Berat, Qark Berat); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë); Vodice (Poliçan, Qark Berat); Vorë (Qark Tiranë); Zharrëz (Patos, Qark Fier).

References: [?] Dallas, 1851 (as *Graphosoma lineatum* Linn.): Albania (British Museum London; leg. W. Wilson Saunders). Schumacher, 1914 (as *Graphosoma italicum* Muell.): Orosi (leg. Latif Buljubašić, 1905) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916 (as *Graphosoma italicum* Muell.): Oroshi. Royer, 1922 (as *Graphosoma italicum* Muell.): environs de Koritza [Korçë] (VII, 1 ♂, 2 ♀). Csiki, 1940: Kula Ljums (03.VII.1918, 05.VII.1918), Lušna: Ura i Lopez [Ura Lapaj] (21.VII.1918), Montes Djalica Ljums [Mali i Gjalicës] (13.VII.1918, 1000–1600 m) [HNHM]. Mancini, 1953 (as *Graphosoma italicum* Muell.): Kula Ljums, Elbasan (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]; Hani Grabon, Mali Daiti (Mus. Trieste); Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Capra); Qukes, Berat, Petrelë, Scutari [Shkodër] (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Josifov, 1970 (as *Graphosoma lineatum* (Linnaeus, 1758)): Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena (200 m, 29.–31.V.1961); Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (Wiese, 1000–1100 m, 03.–08.VII.1961); Bizë bei Shënjergji (10.–15.VII.1961); Thethi, Shalabach-Tal, Nordalbanische Alpen (900–1200 m, 01.–04.VIII.1961); Stadtgebiet Shkodra, lux, 05.–08.VIII.1961) [SDEI]. Misja, 1970 (as *Graphosoma lineatum* L.): Vlorë (22.V.1969); Maminas (15.VI.1968); Ibë (05.VII.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Graphosoma lineatum* Linnaeus, 1758): Dajt (18.IX.2007); Shkozë (24.IX.2008). Halimi et al., 2014 (as *Graphosoma lineatum* Linnaeus, 1758): Dajt, Vorë (2008–2010). Halimi et al., 2018 (as *Graphosoma lineatum* Linnaeus, 1758): Zharëza, Seman, Darëzeze (V.–IX.2015–2017). Gkrazntani & Kallenborn, 2023: Tiranë (14.VI.2022) [PCMG]. Halimi et al., 2024 (as *Graphosoma lineatum* Linnaeus, 1758): Uznov (20.VII.2019); Vodice (27.VII.2019); Lybesh (03.IX.2019); Peshtan (13.IX.2019) [NHMT].

Note: *Graphosoma italicum* (O.F. Müller, 1766) was previously considered a synonym of *Graphosoma lineatum* (Linnaeus, 1758) by most entomologists. However, recent molecular biological findings by Lupoli (2017) have shown that they are distinct species, both genetically and geographically.

***Graphosoma (Graphosoma) melanoxanthum* Horváth, 1903**

Location of record: Mali i Çajupit (Libohovë, Qark Gjirokastrë).

Reference: Ramsay, 2014: Çajup (10.VIII.1933, 2 specimens; 16.VIII.1935, leg. A.H.G. Alston & N.Y. Sandwith) [BMNH].

Graphosoma (Graphosoma) semipunctatum (Fabricius, 1775)

Locations of records: Farkë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Hamallaj (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Koplik (Malësi e Madha, Qark Shkodër); Patos (Qark Fier); Petrelë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Poshnjë (Dimal, Qark Berat); Roskovec (Qark Fier); Shëngjin (Qark Lezhë); Uznovë (Berat, Qark Berat); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Mancini, 1953: S. Giovanni di Medua [Shëngjin] (coll. Mancini); Kopliku (leg. Capra); Petrela (leg. Tamanini, 1941). Misja, 1970: Vlorë (27.V.1969). Halimi, 2011: Petrelë (12.VI.2009); Hamallaj (14.VIII.2008). Halimi et al., 2014: Ibë, Farkë (2008–2010). Halimi et al., 2018: Patos, Roskovec (V.–IX.2015–2017). Halimi et al., 2024: Uznov (07.V.2019); Poshnje (23.VII.2019) [NHMT].

[&] *Leprosoma inconspicuum* Baerensprung, 1859

Note: Rider (2006) and Péricart (2010) most probably refer to Mancini's (1953) record from 'Uskub' (the Turkish name for Skopje), which is now the capital of North Macedonia.

Tholagmus flavolineatus (Fabricius, 1798)

Locations of records: Hamallaj (Durrës, Qark Durrës); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Ndroq (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Misja, 1970: Vlorë (27.V.1969). Halimi, 2011: Hamallaj (14.VIII.2008). Halimi et al., 2014 (as *Thalagmus* [sic] *flavolineatus* Fabricius, 1798): Ibë, Ndroq (2008–2010).

Ventocoris (Ventocoris) rusticus (Fabricius, 1781)

Locations of records: Bardhor (Kavajë, Qark Tiranë); Ibë (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Labinot-Fushë (Elbasan, Qark Elbasan); Korçë (Qark Korçë); Mali i Dajtit (Tiranë, Qark Tiranë); Sanjollas (Barmash, Kolonjë, Qark Korçë); Vlorë (Qark Vlorë).

References: Misja, 1970 (as *Ventocoris trigonus* Krym.): Vlorë (19.V.1969); Korçë (05.VIII.1969). Halimi, 2011 (as *Ventocoris trigonus* Krynicki [sic], 1871): Bardhore (08.VI.2009); F. Labinot (29.VII.2009). Halimi et al., 2014 (as *Ventocoris trigonus* Krynicki [sic], 1871): Dajt, Ibë (2008–2010). Dhellemmes, 2021: District de Kolonjë, Albanie (01.X.2021; N 40.261908 E 20.593458 [Sanjollas]).

[?] *Vilpianus galii* (Wolff, 1802)

Location of record: ?

References: [?] Stichel, 1962: Albanien. [?] Josifov, 1970: Albanien [quoting from Stichel, 1962].

PENTATOMIDAE Leach, 1815: PODOPINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843: PODOPINI Amyot & Serville, 1843

Podops (Opocrates) curvidens A. Costa, 1843

Locations of records: Berat (Qark Berat); Poçem (Mallakastër, Qark Fier); Shëngjin (Qark Lezhë).

References: Schumacher, 1914: Berat (leg. Patsch) [ZMBH]. Horváth, 1916: Berat. Mancini, 1953: Shen Gjin (Mus. Vienna, 1914–1918) [NHMW]. Rabitsch, 2018: Poçem (24.–29.IV.2017).

Podops (Opocrates) rectidens Horváth, 1883

Location of record: Shëngjin (Qark Lezhë).

Reference: Misja, 1973 (as *Podops incerta* Horv.): Shëngjin (05.V.1970) [NHMT].

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REFERENCES

- Andersen, N. M., 1995, Infraorder Gerromorpha Popov, 1971 – semiaquatic bugs, pp. 77–114. In Aukema, B., Rieger, C. (eds), Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic Regions, Vol. 1, Enicocephalomorpha, Dipsocoromorpha, Nepomorpha, Gerromorpha, and Leptopodomorpha. *The Netherlands Entomological Society*, Amsterdam, 222 pp.
- Ashlock, P. D., Slater, A., 1988, Family Lygaeidae Schilling, 1829. The seed Bugs and Chinch Bugs, pp. 167–245. In Henry, T. J., Froeschner, R. C. (eds), Catalog of the Heteroptera, or True Bugs, of Canada and the Continental United States. *E. J. Brill*, Leiden, 958 pp.
- Aukema, B. (ed.), Catalogue of the Palaearctic Heteroptera. <https://catpalhet.linnaeus.naturalis.nl> (last accessed 09 March 2025).
- Aukema, B., Rieger, C. (eds), 1995–2006, Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic Region, Vol. 1–5. *The Netherlands Entomological Society*, Amsterdam, 222 pp., 361 pp., 577 pp., 346 pp., and 550 pp.
- Aukema, B., Rieger, C., Rabitsch, W. (eds), 2013, Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic Region, Vol. 6, Supplement. *The Netherlands Entomological Society*, Amsterdam, 629 pp.
- Bredden, G., 1909, Rhynchoten von Ceylon gesammelt von Dr. Walter Horn. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique*, 53: 250–309.
- Cobben, R. H., 1960, Die Uferwanzen Europas. Hemiptera-Heteroptera Saldidae, pp. 209–263. In Stichel, W., 1958–1960. Illustrierte Bestimmungstabellen der Wanzen. II. Europa (Hemiptera Heteroptera Europae), Vol. 3. *Wolfgang Stichel*, Berlin-Hermsdorf, 428 pp.
- Csiki, E., 1940, Féliszárnyúrovarok. Hemipteren. Csiki Ernő állatani kutatásai Albániában. Explorationes zoologicae ab E. Csiki in Albania peractae, pp. 289–315. In Teleki P., E. Cziki. A Magyar Tudományos Akadémia Balkán-kutatásainak tudományos eredményei, Vol. 1. *Magyar Tudományos Akadémia*, Budapest, 332 pp.
- Csóka, G., Hirka, A., Mutun, S., Glavendekić, M., Mikó, Á., Szöcs, L., Paulin, M., Béla Eötvös, C., Gáspár, C., Csepelényi, M., Szénási, Á., Franjević, M., Gninenko, Y., Dautbašić, M., Muzejinović, O., Zúbrik, M., Netoiu, C., Buzatu, A., Bălăcenoiu, F., Jurc, M., Jurc, D., Bernardinelli, I., Streito, J.-C., Avtziš, D., Hrašovec, B., 2019, Spread and potential host range of the invasive oak lace bug [*Corythucha arcuata* (Say, 1832) - Heteroptera: Tingidae] in Eurasia. *Agricultural and Forest Entomology*, 22(1): 61–74. <https://doi.org/10.1111/afe.12362> (Author manuscript; last accessed 01 February 2024).
- Dallas, W. S., 1851, List of the specimens of hemipterous insects in the collection of the British Museum, Part I. *Taylor*, London, 1: 1–365.
- Dallas, W. S., 1852, List of the specimens of hemipterous insects in the collection of the British Museum, Part II. *Taylor*, London, 2: 369–592.
- Dhellemmes, T., 2021a, *Acrosternum heegeri* [sic]. <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/101358049> (last accessed 09 February 2024).
- Dhellemmes T., 2021b, *Acrosternum millierei*. <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/101321907> (last accessed 09 February 2024).
- Dhellemmes, T., 2021c, *Dicyphus albonasutus*. <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/101286718>; <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/101286717> (last accessed 09 February 2024).
- Dhellemmes, T., 2021d, *Gonocerus juniperi*. <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/101358036>;

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/101286710>; <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/101285133> (last accessed 09 February 2024).
- Dhellemmes, T., 2021e, *Heterogaster cathariae*. <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/101286712> (last accessed 09 February 2024).
- Dhellemmes, T., 2021f, *Holocogaster fibulata*. <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/101358045>; <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/101321906> (last accessed 09 February 2024).
- Dhellemmes, T., 2021g, *Leptoglossus occidentalis*. <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/101285138> (last accessed 09 February 2024).
- Dhellemmes, T., 2021h, *Pseudomegacoelum beckeri*. <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/101285132> (last accessed 09 February 2024).
- Dhellemmes, T., 2021i, *Ventocoris rusticus*. <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/97121826> (last accessed 09 February 2024).
- Dioli, P., 1993, Spedizione alpinistico-scientifica 'Progetto Alpi Albanesi 1993'. I. *Ischnonyctes barbarus* (Lucas, 1849) per i Balcani (Insecta, Heteroptera, Reduviidae) e osservazioni sui Metapterini Stal, 1874 europei. *Il Naturalista Valtellinese - Atti Museo civico di storia naturale di Morbegno*, 4: 17–24.
- Dudich, E., 1922, Die Phymatiden des Ungarischen National-Museums. *Annales Historico-Naturales Musei Nationalis Hungarici*, 19: 161–181.
- Fent, M., Kment, P., Çamur-Elipek, B., Kirgiz, T., 2011, Annotated catalogue of Enicocephalomorpha, Dipsocoromorpha, Nepomorpha, Gerromorpha, and Leptopodomorpha (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) of Turkey, with new records. *Zootaxa*, 2856: 1–84.
- Friese, G., 1967, Ergebnisse der Albanien-Expedition 1961 des Deutschen Entomologischen Institutes. 61. Beitrag. Verzeichnis albanischer Fundorte. *Beiträge zur Entomologie*, 17: 405–434.
- Gailhampshire, 2018a, *Raglius alboacuminatus?*. https://www.flickr.com/photos/gails_pictures/30824437687/ (last accessed 09 February 2024).
- Gailhampshire, 2018b, *Adomerus biguttatus*. https://www.flickr.com/photos/gails_pictures/43610962960/ (last accessed 09 February 2024).
- GeoNames geographical database. <https://www.geonames.org> (last accessed 07 March 07 2022).
- Gkrazntani, M., Kallenborn, H. G., 2023, Beitrag zur Wanzenfauna (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) Albaniens mit Erstmeldungen von drei Arten. *Heteropteron*, 68: 20–28.
- Göllner-Scheidung, U., 1986, Revision der Gattung *Odontoscelis* Laporte de Castelnau, 1832. *Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift (N.F.)*, 33: 95–127.
- Göllner-Scheidung, U., 2006, Family Scutelleridae Leach, 1815 – shield bugs, pp. 190–227. In Aukema, B., Rieger, C. (eds), Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic regions, Vol. 5, Pentatomorpha II. *The Netherlands Entomological Society*, Amsterdam, 550 pp.
- Golub, V. B., 1975, Obzor klopov-kruzhevnikov roda *Dictyonota* Curtis (Heteroptera, Tingidae) fauny SSSR i Mongolii [Review of the lacebugs of the genus *Dictyonota* Curtis (Heteroptera, Tingidae) of the fauna of the USSR and Mongolia]. *Nasekomye Mongolii*, 3: 56–78 (not seen, quoting from Péricart, 1983).
- Graf, W., Bauernfeind, E., Bequirai, S., Duda, M., Frank, T., Gunczy, J., Heckes, U., Hess, M., Kunz, G., Meulenbroek, P., Paill, W., Rabitsch, W., Vitecek, S., 2017, The fauna of the Vjosa river and the adjacent floodplain at Poçem. *University of Vienna*, Wien, 23 pp. https://balkanrivers.net/uploads/legacy/Vjosa_assessment_201709.pdf (last accessed 14 September 2024).
- Graf, W., Grabowski, M., Hess, M., Heckes, U., Rabitsch, W., Vitecek, A., 2018, Contribution to the knowledge of aquatic invertebrate Fauna of the Vjosa in Albania. *Acta ZooBot Austria*, 155: 135–153.

- Grupče, R., 1961, Beitrag zur Kenntnis der Heteroptera Aquatica (Corixinae) von Mazedonien. *Fragmenta Balcanica*, 4(88): 29–36.
- Halimi, E., 2011, Vlerësim në njohjen e insekteve gjysmëflatrafortë (Rendi Hemiptera, Klasa Insekta, Tipi Arthropoda) të Shqipërisë së Mesme: të dhëna sistematike ekologjike. *Doctoral Thesis*, University of Tirana. 230 pp.
- Halimi, E., Paparisto, A., Mara, A., 2018, Some systematics and ecological data for true bugs (Hemiptera) in some habitats in Fieri. *International Journal of Environmental Pollution and Environmental Modelling*, 1(4): 85–90.
- Halimi, E., Paparisto, A., Topi, D., 2014, A contribution to the knowledge of the stink bugs (pentatomidae, hemiptera) in the ecosystems in tirana region (Albania) [sic]. *Global Advanced Research Journal of Agricultural Science*, 3: 77–84.
- Halimi, E., Paparisto, A., Alameti, E., 2020, Some systematics data for species Miridae - Plant bugs (Hemiptera) in habitats of coastal region (Kavaja) [sic]. *II. International Agricultural, Biological & Life Science Conference*, Edirne, Turkey, 1–3 September, 2020: 465–470.
- Halimi, E., Paparisto, A., Misja, K., 2010, Some systematics and ecological data for true bugs (Hemiptera) in some habitats in Albania. *Natura Montenegrina*, 9: 469–479.
- Halimi, E., Qirinxhi, X., Paparisto, A., Subashaj, G., 2024, Contribution to knowledge of the true bugs species (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) in the habitats of the Berati area in Albania. *Journal of Biological Research*. <https://doi.org/10.4081/jbr.2024.12479> (last accessed 14 September 2024).
- Heiss, E., 2006, New records of Aradidae from the Balkan countries (Heteroptera, Aradidae). *Acta entomologica Serbica*, 11: 1–10.
- Heiss, E., Péricart, J., 2007, Hémiptères Aradidae Piesmatidae et Dipsocoromorphes Euro-Méditerranéens. *Faune de France. France et Régions Limitrophes* 91. *Fédération française des Sociétés des Sciences naturelles*, Paris. 509 pp.
- Horváth, G., 1876, Die Hemipteren-Gattung *Plinthisus* (Westw.) Fieb. *Verhandlungen der Kaiserlich-Königlichen Zoologisch-Botanischen Gesellschaft in Wien*, 26: 721–736.
- Horváth, G., 1906, Synopsis Tingitidarum Regionis palaearticae. *Annales Musei Nationalis Hungarici*, 4: 1–117.
- Horváth, G., 1916, Albánia Hemiptera-faunája (Fauna hemipterorum Albaniae). *Annales Musei Nationalis Hungarici*, 14: 1–16.
- Horváth, G., 1924, Remarques sur trois espèces du genre *Mesovelia* MR. *Annales Historico-Naturales Musei Nationalis Hungarici*, 21: 135–136.
- Jansson, A., 1995, Family Corixidae Leach, 1815 – water boatmen, pp. 26–56. In Aukema, B., Rieger, C. (eds), *Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic Region, Volume 1, Enicocephalomorpha, Dipsocoromorpha, Nepomorpha, Gerromorpha and Leptopodomorpha. The Netherlands Entomological Society*, Amsterdam, 222 pp.
- Jansson, A., 1986, The Corixidae (Heteroptera) of Europe and some adjacent regions. *Acta Entomologica Fennica*, 47: 1–94.
- Josifov, M., 1970, Ergebnisse der Albanien-Expedition 1961 des Deutschen Entomologischen Institutes. 82. Beitrag. Heteroptera. *Beiträge zur Entomologie*, 20(7/8): 825–956.
- Josifov, M. [as Josifov, M. V.], 1981, Fauna Bulgarica 12. Heteroptera, Pentatomoidea [in Bulgarian]. *Bulgarian Academy of Sciences*, Sofia, 205 pp.
- Josifov, M., 1986, Verzeichnis der von der Balkanhalbinsel bekannten Heteropterenarten (Insecta, Heteroptera). *Faunistische Abhandlungen. Staatliches Museum für Tierkunde in Dresden*, 14: 61–93.
- Kerzhner, I. M., 1994, Comments on the proposed conservation of the specific name of *Notonecta obliqua* Thunberg, 1787 (Insecta, Heteroptera) (case 2829). *Bulletin of the Zoological Nomenclature*, 51: 41–43.

- Kerzhner, I. M., 1995, Infraorder Dipsocoromorpha, pp. 6–12. In Aukema, B., Rieger, C. (eds), Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic Region, Volume 1, Enicocephalomorpha, Dipsocoromorpha, Nepomorpha, Gerromorpha and Leptopodomorpha. *The Netherlands Entomological Society*, Amsterdam, 222 pp.
- Kerzhner, I. M., 1996, Family Nabidae A. Costa, 1853 – damsel bugs, pp. 84–107. In Aukema, B. Rieger, C. (eds), Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic Region, Volume 2, Cimicomorpha I. *The Netherlands Entomological Society*, Amsterdam, 361 pp.
- Kerzhner, I. M., Josifov, M., 1999, Miridae Hahn, 1883, pp. 1–576. In Aukema, B. and Rieger, C. (eds), Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic Region, Volume 3, Cimicomorpha II. *The Netherlands Entomological Society*, Amsterdam, 576 pp.
- Kirkaldy, G. W., 1897, Revision of Notonectidae. I. Introduction and systematic revision of the genus *Notonecta*. *Transactions of the Entomological Society of London*, 1897: 393–426.
- Kment, P., Baňář, P., 2010, On the taxonomy and distribution of the genus *Maccevethus* (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Rhopalidae). *Acta Musei Moraviae, Scientiae biologicae (Brno)*, 95 (1): 15–47.
- Kment, P., Bryja, J., Jindra, Z., 2005, New records of true bugs (Heteroptera) of the Balkan peninsula. *Acta Entomologica Slovenica*, 13: 9–20.
- Lack, H. W., Barina, Z., 2020, The early botanical exploration of Albania (1839–1945). *Willdenowia*, 50: 519–558. Appendix 5, electronic supplement, <https://doi.org/10.3372/wi.50.50304> (last accessed 01 February 2024).
- Lindskog, P., 1995, Infraorder Leptopodomorpha, pp. 115–141. In Aukema, B. Rieger, C. (eds), Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic regions, Vol. 1, Enicocephalomorpha, Dipsocoromorpha, Nepomorpha, Gerromorpha, and Leptopodomorpha. *The Netherlands Entomological Society*, Amsterdam, 222 pp.
- Linnavuori, R. E., 2008, Studies on the Acanthosomatidae, Scutelleridae and Pentatomidae (Heteroptera) of Gilan and the adjacent provinces in northern Iran. *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae*, 48: 1–21.
- Lis, J. A., 2006, Family Cydnidae Billberg, 1820 - burrowing bugs (burrower bugs), pp. 119–147. In Aukema, B., Rieger, C. (eds), Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic regions, Vol. 5, Pentatomorpha II. *The Netherlands Entomological Society*, Amsterdam, 550 pp.
- Lupoli, R., 2017, *Graphosoma lineatum* (L., 1758) et *G. italicum* (O.F. Müller, 1766), deux espèces valides et distinctes, probablement issues de la transgression zanzibienne méditerranéenne (Hemiptera Pentatomidae). *L'Entomologiste*, 73: 19–33.
- Lupoli, R., F., Dusoulier, A., Cruaud, A., Cros-Arteil, S., Streito, J.-C., 2013, Morphological, biogeographical and molecular evidence of *Carpocoris mediterraneus* as a valid species (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae). *Zootaxa*, 3609(4): 392–410.
- Lupoli, R., van der Heyden, T., Dioli, P., 2021, Confirmation of *Erthesina fullo* (Thunberg, 1783) (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae) in Albania and its host plants. *Heteroptera Poloniae - Acta Faunistica*, 14: 101–102.
- Mancini, C., 1953, Contributo alla conoscenza degli Emitteri Etteroteri dell' Albania. *Annalen des Naturhistorischen Museums in Wien*, 59: 176–196.
- Misja, K., 1970, Të dhëna paraprake mbi inventarizimin e Hemipterëve (Hemiptera). *Buletini i Shkencave të Natyrore*, 1970(4): 85–94.
- Misja, K., 1973, Rezultate të studimit të gjysëmkrähëfortëve Hemipterëve të vëndit tonë. *Buletini Shkencave të Natyrës*, 1–2: 131–151.
- Perez Goodwyn, P. J., 2006, Taxonomic revision of the subfamily Lethocerinae Lauck & Menke (Heteroptera: Belostomatidae). *Stuttgarter Beiträge zur Naturkunde. Serie A (Biologie)*, 695: 1–71.

- Péricart, J., 1972, Hémiptères Anthocoridae, Cimicidae et Microphysidae de l'ouest palaéarctique. *Faune de l'Europe et du Bassin méditerranéen* 7. Masson et Cie, Paris, 402 pp.
- Péricart, J., 1981, Révision systématique des Tingidae Ouest-paléarctiques. 8. Contribution à l'étude du genre *Tingis* Fabricius (Hemiptera). *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France (N.S.)*, 17: 87–95.
- Péricart, J., 1983, Hémiptères Tingidae Euro-Méditerranéens. *Faune de France. France et Régions Limitrophes* 69. *Fédération française des Sociétés des Sciences naturelles*, Paris, 618 pp.
- Péricart, J., 1984, Hémiptères Berytidae Euro-Méditerranéens. *Faune de France. France et Régions Limitrophes* 70. *Fédération française des Sociétés des Sciences naturelles*, Paris, 171 pp.
- Péricart, J., 1990, Hémiptères Saldidae et Leptopodidae d'Europe occidentale et du Maghreb. *Faune de France. France et Régions Limitrophes* 77. *Fédération française des Sociétés des Sciences naturelles*, Paris. 238 pp.
- Péricart, J., 1996a, Family Anthocoridae Fieber, 1836 – flower bugs, minute pirate bugs, pp. 108–140. In Aukema, B., Rieger, C. (eds), Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic regions, Vol. 2, Cimicomorpha I. *The Netherlands Entomological Society*, Amsterdam, 361 pp.
- Péricart, J., 1996b, Family Cimicidae Latreille, 1802 – bed bugs, pp. 141–144. In Aukema, B., Rieger, C. (eds), Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic regions, Vol. 2, Cimicomorpha I. *The Netherlands Entomological Society*, Amsterdam, 361 pp.
- Péricart, J., 1998a, Hémiptères Lygaeidae Euro-Méditerranéens, Vol. 1. *Faune de France. France et Régions Limitrophes* 84a. *Fédération française des Sociétés des Sciences naturelles*, Paris, 468 pp.
- Péricart, J., 1998b, Hémiptères Lygaeidae Euro-Méditerranéens, Vol. 2. *Faune de France. France et Régions Limitrophes* 84b. *Fédération française des Sociétés des Sciences naturelles*, Paris, 453 pp.
- Péricart, J., 1998c, Hémiptères Lygaeidae Euro-Méditerranéens, Vol. 3. *Faune de France. France et Régions Limitrophes* 84c. *Fédération française des Sociétés des Sciences naturelles*, Paris, 487 pp.
- Péricart, J., 2001a, Family Lygaeidae Schilling, 1929 - Seed-bugs, pp. 35–229. In Aukema, B., Rieger, C. (eds), Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic Region, Volume 4, Pentatomomorpha I. *The Netherlands Entomological Society*, Amsterdam, 346 pp.
- Péricart, J., 2001b, Family Berytidae Fieber, 1851 - Stilt-bugs, pp. 230–242. In Aukema, B., Rieger, C. (eds), Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic Region, Volume 4, Pentatomomorpha I. *The Netherlands Entomological Society*, Amsterdam, 346 pp.
- Péricart, J., 2010, Hémiptères Pentatomoidea Euro-Méditerranéens, Vol. 3, Podopinae et Asopinae. *Faune de France. France et Régions Limitrophes* 93. *Fédération française des Sociétés des Sciences naturelles*, Paris. 290 pp.
- Péricart, J., Golub, V. B., 1996, Superfamily Tingoidea Laporte, 1832, pp. 3–78. In Aukema, B., Rieger, C. (eds), Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic regions, Vol. 2, Cimicomorpha I. *The Netherlands Entomological Society*, Amsterdam, 361 pp.
- Polhemus, J. T., 1995, Family Notonectidae Latreille, 1802 – backswimmers, pp. 63–73. In Aukema, B., Rieger, C. (eds), Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic regions, Vol. 1, Enicocephalomorpha, Dipsocoromorpha, Nepomorpha, Gerromorpha and Leptopodomorpha. *The Netherlands Entomological Society*, Amsterdam, 222 pp.
- Protić, L., 2002, Species of the genus *Dicyphus* (Heteroptera: Miridae) in Serbia. *Acta Entomologica Slovenica*, 10: 103–114.
- Protić, L., 2004a, Additions and corrections to the Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palae-

- arctic Region: Tingidae of the Balkan Peninsula. *Acta Entomologica Slovenica*, 12: 229–238.
- Protić, L., 2004b, Species of the family Tingidae in Serbia and adjacent Balkan countries. *Third European Hemiptera Congress, Abstracts*, St. Petersburg, June 8–11, 2004: 63 (not seen, quoting from Protić, 2004a).
- Protić, L., 2007, Family Cydnidae (Insecta: Heteroptera) in the Natural History Museum in Belgrade. *Polish Journal of Entomology*, 76: 143–159.
- Putshkov, P. V., Moulet, P., 2009, Hémiptères Reduviidae de l'Europe occidentale. *Faune de France. France et Régions Limitrophes* 92. *Fédération française des Sociétés des Sciences naturelles*, Paris. 668 pp.
- Rabitsch, W., 2018, Snapshot of the terrestrial true bug fauna of the Pocem floodplains (Insecta: Hemiptera: Heteroptera). *Acta ZooBot Austria*, 155: 251–256.
- Ramsay, A. J., 2014, *Graphosoma melanoxanthum* (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) new to Europe from Albania, with notes on its ecology and distribution. (První evropský nález kněžice *Graphosoma melanoxanthum* (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) z Albánie s poznámkami k její ekologii a rozšíření). *Klapalekiana*, 49: 85–88. <https://researchnet/publication/268074072>.
- Reuter, O. M., 1891, Griechische Heteroptera gesammelt von E. v. Oertzen und J. Emge. *Berliner Entomologische Zeitschrift*, 36: 17–34.
- Ribes, J., D., Gapon, A., Pagola-Carte, S., 2007, On some species of *Carpocoris* Kolenati, 1846: new synonymies (Heteroptera: Pentatomidae, Pentatominae). In Renker, K. (ed.), Festschrift zum 70. Geburtstag von Hannes Günther. *Mainzer Naturwissenschaftliches Archiv*, Beiheft 31: 187–198.
- Rider, D. A., 2006, Family Pentatomidae Leach, 1815, pp. 223–402. In Aukema, B., Rieger, C. (eds), Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic Regions, Vol. 5, Pentatomorpha II. *The Netherlands Entomological Society*, Amsterdam, 550 pp.
- Roubal, J., 1959, *Lamprodema maurum* (F. 1803) et *L. brevicolle* Fieb. 1861 (Het. Lygaeid.). Note rectificative. *Bulletin de la Société entomologique de Mulhouse*, 1959: 53–55 (not seen, quoting from Péricart, 1998c).
- Roubal, J., 1965, *Chiragra*-Komplex unter der Lygaeiden-Gattung *Megalonotus* Fieber 1860 aus dem Europäischen Festland. Ein Versuch um die Taxonomische Lösung. *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae*, 36: 555–588.
- Royer, M., 1922, Travaux scientifiques de l'Armée d'Orient (1916–1918). Hémiptères Hétéroptères (Première note). *Bulletin du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle*, Paris 28: 517–522.
- Royer, M., 1923, Travaux scientifiques de l'Armée d'Orient (1916–1918). Hémiptères Hétéroptères (Deuxième note). *Bulletin du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle*, Paris 29: 245–251.
- Royer, M., 1924a, Travaux scientifiques de l'Armée d'Orient (1916–1918). Hémiptères Hétéroptères (Troisième note). *Bulletin du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle*, Paris 30: 193–200.
- Royer, M., 1924b, Travaux scientifiques de l'Armée d'Orient (1916–1918). Hémiptères Hétéroptères (Quatrième et dernière note). *Bulletin du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle*, Paris 30: 483–489.
- Schumacher, F., 1914, Hemipteren aus Albanien und Epirus. *Sitzungsberichte der Gesellschaft Naturforschender Freunde zu Berlin*, 1914: 116–127.
- Schumacher, F., 1917, *Belostoma (Lethocerus) cordofanum* Mayr, ein riesenhaftes tropisches Wasserinsekt und seine Verbreitung auf der Balkanhalbinsel. *Sitzungsberichte der Gesellschaft Naturforschender Freunde zu Berlin*, 1917: 516–519.
- Slater, J. A., O'Donnell, J. E., 1995, A Catalogue of the Lygaeidae of the World (1960–1994). *New York Entomological Society*, New York, 410 pp.

- Stichel, W., 1938, Illustrierte Bestimmungstabellen der deutschen Wanzen (Hemiptera-Heteroptera). Geographische Verbreitung. II. Lieferung 14. *Wolfgang Stichel-Eigenverlag*, Berlin - Hermsdorf, pp. 363–426.
- Stichel, W., 1955–1962, Illustrierte Bestimmungstabellen der Wanzen. II. Europa. (Hemiptera-Heteroptera Europae). Vol. 1 (1955): 1–160, (1956): 161–168; Vol. 2 (1956): 169–480, (1957): 481–704, (1958a): 705–907; Vol. 3 (1958): 1–32, (1959): 33–192, (1960): 193–428; Vol. 4 (1957): 1–96, (1958): 97–224, (1959): 225–384, (1960a): 385–544, (1961): 545–768, (1962a): 769–838; General-Index (1962b): 1–111. *Wolfgang Stichel-Eigenverlag*, Berlin - Hermsdorf.
- Tamanini, L., 1947, Contributo ad una revisione del genere *Velia* Latr. e descrizione di alcune specie nuove (Hemiptera Heteroptera: Veliidae). *Memorie della Società Entomologica Italiana*, 26: 17–74.
- van der Heyden, T., 2017a, First records of *Lygaeus creticus* Lucas, 1854 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Lygaeidae: Lygaeinae) for Albania and France. *Arquivos entomológicos*, 18: 65–66. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319777664> (last accessed 22 September 2024).
- van der Heyden, T., 2017b, First records of *Gonocerus insidiator* (Fabricius, 1787) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Coreidae: Coreinae: Gonocerini) for Albania. *Arquivos entomológicos*, 18: 131–132. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320288358> (last accessed 22 September 2024).
- van der Heyden, T., 2017c, Notes on *Plinachtus imitator* (Reuter, 1891), including the first records for Albania (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Coreidae: Coreinae: Gonocerini). *BV news Publicaciones Científicas*, Hamburg, 6(77): 68–73. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318984249> (last accessed 22 September 2024).
- van der Heyden, T., 2017d, The first record of *Thaumastocoris peregrinus* Carpintero & Dellapé, 2006 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Thaumastocoridae) for Albania. *Revista gaditana de Entomología*, 8(2): 133–135. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319276315> (last accessed 22 September 2024).
- van der Heyden, T., 2017e, First record of *Trygonotylus* [sic] *caelestialium* (Kirkaldy, 1902) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Miridae: Mirinae: Stenodemini) for Albania. *Arquivos entomológicos*, 18: 231–232. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321319685> (last accessed 22 September 2024).
- van der Heyden, T., 2017f, First records of *Zelus renardii* (Kolenati, 1856) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Harpactorinae) for Albania. *Arquivos entomológicos*, 18: 49–50. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319630229> (last accessed 22 September 2024).
- van der Heyden, T., 2018a, First record of *Aphanus rolandri* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Albania (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Rhyparochromidae: Rhyparochrominae: Gonianotini). *Heteropteron*, 51: 32–33. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323638807> (last accessed 22 September 2024).
- van der Heyden, T., 2018b, First record of *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann (Heteroptera: Coreidae: Coreinae: Anisoscelini) in Albania. *Revista Chilena de Entomología*, 44 (3): 355–356. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327792869> (last accessed 01 February 2024).
- van der Heyden, T., 2019, First records of *Dryadocoris apicalis* (Herrich-Schäffer) (Heteroptera: Pentatomidae: Pentatominae: Antestiini) for Albania. *Revista Chilena de Entomología*, 45(3): 331–333. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334362885> (last accessed 01 February 2024).
- van der Heyden, T., 2024, First record of *Oxycarenus lavatae* (Fabricius, 1787) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Oxycarenidae) for Albania. *Heteroptera Poloniae – Acta Faunistica*, 18: 5–6. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12628755> (last accessed 03 March 2025).
- van der Heyden, T., Dhelhemmes T. & Dioli, P., 2024. First records of *Gonocerus juniperi* Herrich-Schäffer, 1839 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Coreidae) for Albania and its new host

- plant. *Heteroptera Poloniae* – *Acta Faunistica* 18: 5-6. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14559531> (last accessed 03 March 2025).
- van der Heyden, T., Dioli, P., 2019, First records of *Lygaeus simulans* Deckert, 1985 for Albania (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Lygaeidae: Lygaeinae). *Natural History Sciences. Atti della Società italiana di scienze naturali e del Museo civico di storia naturale di Milano*, 6(1): 33–36. <https://doi.org/10.4081/nhs.2019.395> (last accessed 01 February 2024).
- Wagner, E., 1951, Über die Variationen bei *Eurygaster*-Arten (Hemipt. Het. Scutelleridae). *Commentationes Biologicae*, 12(11): 1–43.
- Wagner, E., 1953, Beitrag zur Systematik der Gattung *Geotomus* Muls.-Rey (Hemiptera Heteroptera: Cydnidae). *Bulletin de la Société Fouad 1er d'Entomologie*, 37: 459–476.
- Wagner, E., 1970/71, Die Miridae Hahn, 1831, des Mittelmeerraumes und der Makaronesischen Inseln (Hemiptera, Heteroptera), Teil 1. *Entomologische Abhandlungen*, 37 Suppl., Staatliches Museum für Naturkunde in Dresden, 484 pp.
- Walker, J. J., 1875, Notes on Mediterranean Hemiptera-Heteroptera. *The Entomologist's Monthly Magazine*, 12: 79–81.

Table 1. Locations of Heteroptera records from Albania. The current names of the localities are followed by their geographical coordinates (Lat° Long° WGS84). Variant spellings or spellings in other languages are given as used in the cited literature. Municipality unit (Lnjësi administrative), municipality (Bashkia, Komunë), and county (Qark) are given in both indefinite and definite form. Number, circle or capital letter in parentheses following the county refer to the geographical marking of the locality in Figure 1.

Alipostivan , Alipostivani (village): Teqeja e Baba Aliut	N 40.3150 E 20.2987. Landscape: Mali i Tomorrit. Municipality unit: Qendër Piskovë. Municipality: Përmet, Përmeti. County: Gjirokastrë, Gjirokastra (2).
Apollonia (archeological site)	N 40.72163 E19.47245. Variant form: Sop. Landscape: Illyria. Municipality unit: Dërmenas, Dërmenasi (Pojan, Pojani). Municipality: Fier, Fieri. County: Fier, Fieri (12).
Ardenica , Manastiri i Ardenices (village and monastery)	N 40.81864 E19.59273. Landscape: Myzeqe, Myzeqeja. Municipality: Lushnjë, Lushnja. County: Fier, Fieri (6).
Bardhor , Bardhori (village)	N 41.13986 E19.46625. Variant form: Bardhore. Municipality unit: Synej, Syneji. Municipality: Kavajë, Kavaja. County: Tiranë, Tirana (22).
Berat , Berati (city, municipality)	N 40.70583 E 19.95222. Municipality: Berat, Berati. County: Berat, Berati (○).
Bicaj , Bicaji (village, municipality unit)	N 41.07167, 19.80639. Variant form: Biçaj. Municipality unit: Bicaj, Bicaji. Municipality: Kukës, Kukesi. County: Kukës, Kukësi (14).
Bizë , Biza (village)	N 41.34083, 20.19806. Municipality unit: Shëngjergj (San Giorgio). Municipality: Tiranë, Tirana. County: Tiranë, Tirana (12).
Bogë , Boga (village)	N 42.40074, 19.63294. Municipality unit: Shkrel, Shkrelë. Municipality: Malësi e Madha, Malësia e Madhe. County: Shkodër, Shkodra (7).
Borsh , Borshi (village)	N 40.06175, 19.85746. Municipality unit: Lukovë, Lukova. Municipality: Himarë, Himara. County: Vlorë, Vlora (15).
Bradashesh , Bradasheshi (village, municipality unit)	N 41.105 E 20.0225. Municipality unit: Bradashesh, Bradasheshi. Municipality: Elbasan, Elbasani. County: Elbasan, Elbasani (9).
Buçimas , Buçimasi (village, municipality unit)	N 40.891667 E 20.680556. Variant form: Starova (Macedonian). Municipality unit: Buçimas, Buçimasi. Municipality: Pogradec, Pogradeci. County: Korçë, Korça (1).
Butrint , Butrinti (archeological site)	N 39.74613 E 20.02121. Variant form: Butrinto. Landscape: Chaonia. Municipality: Sarandë, Saranda. County: Vlorë, Vlora (20).
Byshek , Bysheku (village)	N 41.10046 E 20.12433. Municipality unit: Elbasan, Elbasani. Municipality: Elbasan, Elbasani. County: Elbasan, Elbasani (10).
Çermë e Poshtme , Çermë Shkumbin (village)	N 41.04948 E 19.57912. Variant form: Cermë, Cerme. Municipality unit: Rogozhinë, Rogozhina. Municipality: Lushnjë, Lushnja. County: Fier, Fieri (1).
Dardhë , Dardha (village)	N 40.51861 E 20.82694. Municipality unit: Drenovë, Drenova. Municipality: Korçë, Korça. County: Korçë, Korça (8).
Darëzezë e Re , Darëzeza e Re (village)	N 40.71694 E 19.38. Variant form: Darzezë. Municipality unit: Dërmenas, Dërmenasi. Municipality: Fier, Fieri. County: Fier, Fieri (11).
Divjakë , Divjaka (town, municipality)	N 40.95716 E 19.52364. Municipality: Divjakë, Divjaka. County: Fier, Fieri (3).
Dukat , Dukati (village)	N 40.25056 E 19.56722. Municipality unit: Orikum, Orikumi. Municipality: Vlorë, Vlora. County: Vlorë, Vlora (9).
Durrës , Durrësi (city, municipality)	N 41.32355 E 19.45469. Variant form: Durazzo, Durrec. Municipality: Durrës, Durrësi. County: Durrës, Durrësi (○).
Elbasan , Elbasani (city, municipality)	N 41.1125 E 20.08222. Variant form: Elbassan. Municipality: Elbasan, Elbasani. County: Elbasan, Elbasani (○).
Farkë , Farka (city district of Tirana, municipality unit)	N 41.28333 E 19.86667. Municipality unit: Farkë, Farka. Municipality: Tiranë, Tirana. County: Tiranë, Tirana (3).
Fier , Fieri (city, municipality)	N 40.72389 E 19.55611. Municipality: Fier, Fieri. County: Fier, Fieri (○).
Fusha e Rudnicës (high mountain valley)	N 42.4708 E 19.7836. Variant form: Fusa Rudnices. Landscape: Alpet Shqiptare (Prokletije). County: Shkodër, Shkodra (2).
Fushë Lurë , Fushë Lura (village, municipality unit)	N 41.80611 E 20.23194. Variant forms: Luria, Lurja, Lan Lura. Landscape: Lura (Vargmalet e Lurës, Malësia e Lurës). Municipality unit: Fushë Lurë, Fushë Lura. Municipality: Dibër, Dibra. County: Dibër, Dibra (2).
Fushë-Krujë , Fushë-Kruja (city, municipality unit)	N 41.47833 E 19.71778. Municipality unit: Fushë-Krujë, Fushë-Kruja. Municipality: Krujë, Kruja. County: Durrës, Durrësi (5).

Table 1. Continued

Gërmenj , Gërmenj (village)	N 40.45556 E 20.29639. Municipality unit: Potom, Potomi. Municipality: Skrapar, Skrapari. County: Berat, Berati (9).
Gërmenj , Gërmenj (village)	N 40.22472 E 20.67515. Municipality unit: Barmash, Barmashi. Municipality: Kolonjë, Kolonja. County: Korçë, Korça (12).
Giri i Lalzit (bay of Lalëz)	N 41.53194 E 19.56806. Variant form: Gj. Lalzit. Municipality: Durrës, Durrësi. County: Durrës, Durrësi (4).
Gjiri i Kakomesë (bay)	N 39.91667 E 19.93333. Variant form: Kokome. Landscape: Adriatic bay. Municipality: Sarandë, Saranda. County: Vlorë, Vloa (17).
Gllavë , Gllava (village)	N 40.49083 E 19.96417. Municipality unit: Buz, Buzi. Municipality: Tepelenë, Tepelena. County: Gjirokastrë, Gjirokastra (1).
Golem , Golemi (village, municipality unit)	N 41.24583 E 19.53472. Municipality unit: Golem, Golemi. Municipality: Kavajë, Kavaja. County: Tiranë, Tirana (20).
Gostilë , Gostila (village)	N 42.0525 E 20.42028. Variant form: Kōstil, Kōsztil. Municipality unit: Kukës, Kukesi. Municipality: Kukës, Kukesi. County: Kukës, Kukësi (10).
Hamallaj (village)	N 41.47389 E 19.54917. Municipality unit: Sukth, Sukthi. Municipality: Durrës, Durrësi. County: Durrës, Durrësi (6).
Han i Grabomit (guesthouse in the Cemi Valley)	N 42.0172 E 19.3731. Variant form: Hani Grabon. Landscape: Alpet Shqiptare (Prokletije). Municipality unit: Tamarë, Tamara. Municipality: Malësi e Madha, Malësia e Madhe. County: Shkodër, Shkodra (14).
Han i Hotit (small village at a border crossing point between Albania and Montenegro)	N 42.33667 E 19.43417. Variant form: Han Hotit. Landscape: Alpet Shqiptare (Prokletije). Municipality: Malësi e Madha, Malësia e Madhe. County: Shkodër, Shkodra (8).
Himarë , Himara (town, municipality)	N 40.10167 E 19.74472. Municipality: Himarë, Himara. County: Vlorë, Vloa (13).
Hoçisht , Hoçishti (village, municipality unit)	N 40.6106 E 20.9155. Municipality unit: Hoçisht, Hoçishti. Municipality: Devoll, Devolli. County: Korçë, Korça (6).
Hotolisht , Hotolishti (village, municipality unit)	N 41.14668 E 20.37996. Municipality: Librazhd, Librazhdi. County: Elbasan, Elbasani (5).
Ibë , Iba (village)	N 41.23333 E 19.93333. Municipality unit: Bërzhitë, Bërzhita. Municipality: Tiranë, Tirana. County: Tiranë, Tirana (18).
Illjas , Illjasi (village)	N 40.14295 E 19.67031. Variant forms: Lias, vallone di Gjper. Landscape: Kanioni i Gjipesë (canyon between Dhërmi and Vuno). Municipality unit: Himarë, Himara. Municipality: Himarë, Himara. County: Vlorë, Vloa (11).
Jah Salih , Jaho Salih (village)	N 42.35672 E 20.10294. Variant forms: Cernicë (B. Curri), Çernicë (B. Curr). Municipality unit: Llugaj, Llugaj. Municipality: Tropojë, Tropoja. County: Kukës, Kukësi (5).
Jonufër , Jonufra (village)	N 40.4014 E 19.47996. Municipality: Vlorë, Vloa. County: Vlorë, Vloa (6).
Kaninë , Kanina (village)	N 40.44055 E 19.52056. Landscape: Mali i Kanalit (Ceraunian Mountains). Municipality unit: Qendër Vlorë. Municipality: Vlorë, Vloa. County: Vlorë, Vloa (4).
Kavajë , Kavaja (city, municipality)	N 41.18556 E 19.55694. Municipality: Kavajë, Kavaja. County: Tiranë, Tirana (21).
Këlcyrë , Këlcyra (town, municipality)	N 40.36196 E 20.16476. Municipality: Këlcyrë, Këlcyra. County: Gjirokastrë, Gjirokastra (3).
Kepi i Rodonit (cape)	N 41.58417 E 19.44972. Variant form: K. Rodonit. Landscape: rocky cape on the Adriatic Sea. Municipality: Durrës, Durrësi. County: Durrës, Durrësi (1).
Kodrat e Krastës (wooded hills north-west of the city of Elbasan)	N 41.10350 E 20.10982; N 41.12534 E 20.05943. Variant form: K. Krastës. Municipality: Elbasan, Elbasani. County: Elbasan, Elbasani (7).
Kodrat e Krujës (hills near Kruja)	N 41.50917 E 19.79278. Variant form: K. Krujës. Municipality: Krujë, Kruja. County: Durrës, Durrësi (3).
Kodrat Shurit , Gryka e Shurit (mountain)	N 41.22862 E 19.92261. Variant form: Shurija. Municipality unit: Bërzhitë, Bërzhita. Municipality: Tiranë, Tirana. County: Tiranë, Tirana (17).
Kolonjë , Kolonja (town, municipality unit)	N 40.82417 E 19.60389. Municipality unit: Kolonjë, Kolonja. Municipality: Lushnjë, Lushnja. County: Fier, Fieri (7).
Konjat , Konjati (village)	N 41.00741, 19.66387. Variant form: Konja. Municipality: Lushnjë, Lushnja. County: Fier, Fieri (2).

Table 1. Continued

Koplik , Kopliku (town, municipality unit)	N 42.21361 E 19.43639. Landscape: Alpet Shqiptare (Prokletije). Municipality unit: Koplik, Kopliku. Municipality: Malësi e Madha, Malësia e Madhe. County: Shkodër, Shkodra (9).
Korçë , Korça (city, municipality)	N 40.61861 E 20.78083. Variant forms: Koritza, Koriç?. Municipality: Korçë, Korça. County: Korçë, Korça (○).
Krrabë , Krraba (town, municipality unit)	N 41.21556 E 19.97139. Variant form: Kërrabë. Landscape: Kodrat e Krrabës. Municipality unit: Krrabë, Krraba. Municipality: Tiranë, Tirana. County: Tiranë, Tirana (19).
Krrabë e Vogël , Krraba e Vogël (village)	N 41.19280 E 19.9979. Municipality unit: Funarë, Funara. Municipality: Elbasan, Elbasani. County: Elbasan, Elbasani (2).
Krumë , Kruma (town, municipality unit)	N 42.19694 E 20.41333. Landscape: Bjeshka e Krumes. Municipality unit: Krumë, Kruma. Municipality: Has, Hasi. County: Kukës, Kukësi (7).
Kukës , Kukësi (city, municipality)	N 42.07694 E 20.42194. Municipality: Kukës, Kukësi. County: Kukës, Kukësi (○).
Kulla e Lumës (Luma bridge near Kukës)	N 42.10038 E 20.41988. Variant forms: K. Lumës, Kula e Lumës, Kula Ljums. Municipality: Kukës, Kukësi. County: Kukës, Kukësi (8).
Kunë , Kuna (nature reserve)	N 41.75 E 19.56498. Variant form: Kune. Landscape: Rezervati Kunë-Vain-Tale (nature reserve). Municipality: Lezhë, Lezha. County: Lezhë, Lezha (4).
Kunora e Lunës (mountain)	N 41.78906 E 20.17888. Variant form: Knora e Lurës. Landscape: Parku Kombëtar Lurë-Mali i Dejës (national park). Municipality: Dibër, Dibra. County: Dibër, Dibra (4).
Kutë , Kuta (village, municipality unit)	N 40.47333 E 19.76639. Landscape: Vjosë, Vjosa (Aoös) (River). Municipality unit: Kutë, Kuta. Municipality: Mallakastër, Mallakastër. County: Fier, Fieri (16).
Labinot-Fushë (village, municipality unit)	N 41.14056 E 20.14611. Variant forms: F. Labinot, L. Fushë. Municipality unit: Labinot-Fushë. Municipality: Elbasan, Elbasani. County: Elbasan, Elbasani (6).
Laguna e Nartës (lagoon), Kripora e Skrofotinës (salines)	N 40.54671 E 19.45426. Variant form: Vjose-Narte salines near Vlore. Landscape: Peisazh i Mbrojtur Vjosë-Nartë (protected landscape). Municipality unit: Qendër Vlorë. Municipality: Vlorë, Vlora. County: Vlorë, Vlora (1).
Lapardhë 1 , Lapardha 1 (village)	N 40.75520, E 19.94851. Municipality unit: Otlak, Otlaki. Municipality: Berat, Berati. County: Berat, Berati (2).
Lavdar , Lavdari (Shkëmb, Shkëmbi)? (village)	N 40.4975 E 20.10472. Variant form: Shkamb. Municipality unit: Vendreshë, Vendresha. Municipality: Skrapar, Skrapari. County: Berat, Berati (A?).
Lezhë , Lezha (city, municipality)	N 41.78361 E 19.64361. Variant form: Lezhe. Municipality: Lezhë, Lezha. County: Lezhë, Lezha (○).
Librazhd , Librazhdi (town, municipality)	N 41.17944 E 20.315. Variant form: Libraz. Municipality: Librazhd, Librazhdi. County: Elbasan, Elbasani (3).
Liçani i Madh i Buni Jezercës (high mountains lake)	N 42.46081 E 19.80523. Variant form: Buna Jersece. Landscape: Alpet Shqiptare (Prokletije). County: Shkodër, Shkodra (3).
Llixhat e Elbasanit (thermal source)	N 41.03862 E 20.07111. Variant form: Llixha. Municipality unit: Tregan, Tregani. Municipality: Elbasan, Elbasani. County: Elbasan, Elbasani (14).
Llogara (national park)	N 40.21362 E 19.58459. Landscape: Parku Kombëtar i Llogarasëm. Municipality unit: Orikum, Orikumi. Municipality: Vlorë, Vlora. County: Vlorë, Vlora (10).
Lukovë , Lukova (village, municipality unit)	N 39.99152 E 19.91443. Municipality unit: Lukovë, Lukova. Municipality: Himarë, Himara. County: Vlorë, Vlora (16).
Lumi i Selitës (stream)	N 41.38333 E 19.93333. Variant form: L. Selitës. Municipality unit: Dajt, Dajti. Municipality: Tiranë, Tirana. County: Tiranë, Tirana (6).
Lushnjë , Lushnja (city, municipality)	N 40.94194 E 19.705. Variant forms: Lusnia, Lushnje. Municipality: Lushnjë, Lushnja. County: Fier, Fieri (4).
Lybeshë , Lybeshja (village)	N 40.66361 E 20.11583. Municipality unit: Vërtop, Vërtopi. Municipality: Poliçan, Poliçani. County: Berat, Berati (6).
Maja e Korabit (mountain range)	N 41.79056 E 20.54667. Variant forms: Korab, Montes Korab. Municipality: Dibrë, Dibra. County: Dibër, Dibra (3).
Maja e Koret , Maja e Koretës (mountain)	N 40.38333 E 19.36667. Variant form: Kjore. Landscape: Gadishulli i Karaburunit (Karaburuni Peninsula). County: Vlorë, Vlora (5).
Maja e Madhe (peak)	N 41.70694 E 20.24806. Municipality unit: Fushe-Çidhën, Fushe-Çidhëni. Municipality: Dibër, Dibra. County: Dibër, Dibra (5).

Table 1. Continued

Malësi e Madha , Malësia e Madhe (municipality)	N 42.41683 E 19.62. Variant forms: Malçija, Malçija. Landscape: Alpet Shqiptare (Prokletije). Municipality: Malësi e Madha, Malësia e Madhe. County: Shkodër, Shkodra (4).
Mali i Çajupit (mountain)	N 40.2 E 20.18333. Variant form: Çajup. Municipality: Libohovë, Libohova. County: Gjirokastër, Gjirokastra (5).
Mali i Corajt (mountain)	N 40.11667 E 19.85. Municipality: Himarë, Himara. County: Vlorë, Vlora (12).
Mali i Cukalit (mountain range)	N 42.13917 E 19.78. Variant forms: Cukali, Cukaligebirge. Landscape: Alpet Shqiptare (Prokletije). County: Shkodër, Shkodra (10).
Mali i Dajtit (mountain)	N 41.35444 E 19.93611. Variant forms: Dajt, Dajti, Mali Daiti. Landscape: Vargmalet e Skënderbeut (Skanderbeg Mountains). Municipality: Tiranë, Tirana. County: Tiranë, Tirana (5).
Mali i Gjalicës (mountain peak)	N 42.01583 E 20.47167. Variant forms: Djalica Ljums, Montes Djalic Ljums. Landscape: Mali i Korabit (Korab Mountains). County: Kukës, Kukësi (12).
Mali i Robit , Kodra i Robit (hill near Golem)	N 41.23194 E 19.52556. Variant form: M. Robit. Municipality unit: Golem, Golemi. Municipality: Kavajë, Kavaja. County: Tiranë, Tirana (17).
Mali i Shkëlzenit (mountain)	N 42.46073 E 20.1123. Variant forms: Montes Skolsen, Montes Skölsen. Landscape: Alpet Shqiptare (Prokletije). Municipality: Tropojë, Tropoja. County: Kukës, Kukësi (1).
Mali i Sogorit? (mountain)	N 40.75 E 20.36667. Variant form: Suha-Gora. Municipality unit: Lenie. Municipality: Gramsh, Gramshi. County: Elbasan, Elbasani (B?).
Mali i Thatë? (mountain)	N 40.88189 E 20.83398. Variant form: Suha-Gora. Municipality: Pogradec, Pogradeci. County: Korçë, Korça (B?).
Mali me Gropë , Mali me Gropa (mountain)	N 41.39583 E 20.035. Landscape: Vargmalet e Skënderbeut (Skanderbeg Mountains), Mali me Gropa-Bizë-Martanesh (nature reserve). Municipality unit: Farkë, Farka. Municipality: Tiranë, Tirana. County: Tiranë, Tirana (2).
Maliq , Maliqi (town, municipality)	N 40.70583 E 20.69972. Municipality: Maliq, Maliqi. County: Korçë, Korça (4).
Maminas , Maminasi (village, municipality unit)	N 41.37917 E 19.6075. Municipality unit: Maminas, Maminasi. Municipality: Shijak, Shijaku. County: Durrës, Durrësi (8).
Mamurras , Mamurrasi (town, municipality unit)	N 41.5775 E 19.69222. Variant form: Mamuras. Municipality unit: Mamurras, Mamurrasi. Municipality: Kurbin, Kurbini. County: Lezhë, Lezha (6).
Marikaj (village)	N 41.37222 E 19.63222. Municipality unit: Vorë, Vora. Municipality: Vorë, Vora. County: Tiranë, Tirana (8).
Markaj (village)	N 42.35297 E 20.05427. Variant form: Markaj (B. Curri). Municipality unit: Bajram Curr, Bajram Curri. Municipality: Tropojë, Tropoja. County: Kukës, Kukësi (4).
Martanesh , Martaneshi (geographic region, municipality unit)	N 41.41667 E 20.16667. Municipality unit: Martanesh, Martaneshi. Municipality: Bulqizë, Bulqiza. County: Dibër, Dibra (7).
Mes , Mesi (village)	N 42.10528 E 19.57083. Variant form: Skutari Mesi. Municipality unit: Shkodër, Shkodra. Municipality: Shkodër, Shkodra. County: Shkodër, Shkodra (11).
Milot , Miloti (town, municipality unit)	N 41.68389 E 19.71556. Municipality unit: Milot, Miloti. Municipality: Kurbin, Kurbini. County: Lezhë, Lezha (5).
Mirakë , Miraka (village)	N 41.16889 E 20.22444. Municipality unit: Polis, Polisi. Municipality: Librazhd, Librazhdi. County: Elbasan, Elbasani (4).
Mirditë , Mirdita (municipality)	N 41.91667 E 20.08333. Variant form: Merdita. Municipality: Mirditë, Mirdita. County: Lezhë, Lezha (1).
Nangë , Nanga (small village)	N 42.01167 E 20.41639. Variant form: Nangat. Municipality unit: Bicaj, Bicaj. Municipality: Kukës, Kukësi. County: Kukës, Kukësi (13).
Ndroq , Ndroqi (village, municipality unit)	N 41.26389 E 19.65583. Municipality unit: Ndroq, Ndroqi. Municipality: Tiranë, Tirana. County: Tiranë, Tirana (15).
Okol , Okoli (settlement in Theth area)	N 42.41639 E 19.75667. Landscape: Alpet Shqiptare (Prokletije), Shala (river valley). Municipality: Shkodër, Shkodra. County: Shkodër, Shkodra (5).
Orenjë , Orenja (village, municipality unit)	N 41.28472 E 20.21194. Variant form: Oranie. Municipality unit: Orenjë, Orenja. Municipality: Librazhd, Librazhdi. County: Elbasan, Elbasani (1).
Orikum , Orikumi (town, municipality unit)	N 40.32528 E 19.47139. Variant form: Pshaliman. Municipality unit: Orikum, Orikumi. Municipality: Vlorë, Vlora. County: Vlorë, Vlora (7).

Table 1. Continued

Orosh , Oroshi (village, municipality unit)	N 41.85571 E 20.08435. Municipality unit: Orosh, Oroshi. Municipality: Mirditë, Mirdita. County: Lezhë, Lezha (2).
Papaj Ballaban (village)	N 42.43222 E 20.16417. Variant form: Ballabanovë. Municipality unit: Bucaj, Bucaji. Municipality: Kukës, Kukesi. County: Kukës, Kukesi (2).
Papër , Papëri (village, municipality unit)	N 41.05167 E 19.96083. Municipality unit: Papër, Papëri. Municipality: Elbasan, Elbasani. County: Elbasan, Elbasani (12).
Parku Kombëtar Divjakë-Karavasta (national park)	N 40.93056 E 19.49689. Variant form: Karavasta National Park. Municipality: Divjakë, Divjaka. County: Fier, Fieri (5).
Parku Kombëtar i Luginës së Valbonës (national park)	N 42.45334 E 19.88777. Variant form: Valbona National Park. Municipality: Tropojë, Tropoja. County: Kukës, Kukësi (A).
Parku Kombëtar i Qafshitamës	N 41.52076 E 19.89218. Variant forms: Qafë Shamtë, Qafë-Shamtë. Municipality: Krujë, Kruja. County: Durrës, Durrësi (2).
Pashtrikë , Pashtriku (mountain located on their mutual border of Kosovo and Albania)	N 42.21548 E 20.51713. Variant form: Pashtrik. Landscape: Malësia e Hasit (mountain range). Municipality: Has, Hasi. County: Kukës, Kukësi (6).
Patos , Patosi (town, municipality)	N 40.68333 E 19.61944. Municipality: Patos, Patosi. County: Fier, Fieri (13).
Pëllumbas , Pëllumbasi (village)	N 41.233605 E 19.964944. Municipality unit: Bërzhitë, Bërzhita. Municipality: Tiranë, Tirana. County: Tiranë, Tirana (19).
Peqin , Peqini (town, municipality)	N 41.04611 E 19.75111. Municipality: Peqin, Peqini. County: Elbasan, Elbasani (13).
Peshkopi , Peshkopia (town, municipality unit)	N 41.685 E 20.42889. Variant forms: Piskopeja, Pescopic. Municipality unit: Peshkopi, Peshkopia. Municipality: Dibër, Dibra. County: Dibër, Dibra (6).
Peshtan , Peshtani (village)	N 40.66417, E 20.06333. Municipality unit: Vërtop, Vërtopi. Municipality: Poliçan, Poliçani. County: Berat, Berati (5).
Petrelë , Petrela (village, municipality unit)	N 41.25306 E 19.85306. Municipality unit: Petrelë, Petrela. Municipality: Tiranë, Tirana. County: Tiranë, Tirana (16).
Pishë-Poro (village)	N 40.64924 E 19.40819. Variant form: Pish-Poro. Landscape: Vjosë, Vjosa (Aoös) (river). Municipality unit: Levan, Levani. Municipality: Fier, Fieri. County: Fier, Fieri (14).
Ploshtan , Ploshtani (village)	N 41.84472 E 20.45528. Variant forms: Plostan, Ploştan. Landscape: Kalaja e Dodës (Korabi National Park). Municipality unit: Kalaja e Dodës. Municipality: Dibër, Dibra. County: Dibër, Dibra (1).
Poçem , Poçemi (village)	N 40.50278 E 19.72972. Landscape: Vjosë, Vjosa (Aoös) (river). Municipality unit: Kutë, Kuta. Municipality: Mallakastër, Mallakastra. County: Fier, Fieri (15).
Pojan , Pojani (village, municipality unit)	N 40.72583 E 20.8375. Municipality unit: Pojan, Pojani. Municipality: Maliq, Maliqi. County: Korçë, Korça (3).
Poliçan , Poliçani (city, municipality)	N 40.61222 E 20.09806. Municipality: Poliçan, Poliçani. County: Berat, Berati (8).
Porto Palermo (bay)	N 40.07347, 19.77819. Municipality: Himarë, Himara. County: Vlorë, Vlora (14).
Porto Romano (archeological site)	N 41.36616 E 19.42212. Variant forms: Portes, Porter. Municipality: Durrës, Durrësi. County: Durrës, Durrësi (9).
Poshnjë , Poshnja (village)	N 40.78027, E 19.84416. Municipality unit: Urë Vajgurore, Ura Vajgurore. Municipality: Dimal, Dimali. County: Berat, Berati (1).
Prenisht , Prenishti (village)	N 40.82528 E 20.62694. Variant forms: Prënisti, Preništi. Municipality unit: Dardhas, Dardhasi. Municipality: Pogradec, Pogradeci. County: Korçë, Korça (2).
Priskë e Madhe (village)	N 41.31917 E 19.92917. Variant form: Priskë. Municipality unit: Dajt, Dajti. Municipality: Tiranë, Tirana. County: Tiranë, Tirana (10).
Prroj Dunavec , Përroi i Dunavecit, Lumi i Dunavecit (stream near Korça)	N 40.7 E 20.75. Variant form: Dunavec prës Koritza. Municipality: Korçë, Korça. County: Korçë, Korça (5).
Pukë , Puka (town, municipality)	N 42.04444 E 19.89972. Municipality: Pukë, Puka. County: Shkodër, Shkodra (13).
Pulaj (village)	N 41.87722 E 19.38417. Municipality unit: Velipojë, Velipoja. Municipality: Shkodër, Shkodra. County: Shkodër, Shkodra (15).
Qukës , Qukësi (village, municipality unit)	N 41.09333 E 20.44778. Variant form: Qukes. Municipality: Përrenjas, Përrenjasi. County: Elbasan, Elbasani (11).

Table 1. Continued

Qytezë , Qyteza – Sinicë , Sinica (road between the two villages)	N 40.503 E 20.884. Municipality unit: Miras, Mirasi. Municipality: Devoll, Devolli. County: Korçë, Korça (9).
Roskovec , Roskoveci (town, municipality)	N 40.7375 E 19.70222. Municipality: Roskovec, Roskoveci. County: Fier, Fieri (9).
Rrapshë , Rrapsha (village)	N 42.38556 E 19.49278. Variant form: Rapsa. Municipality unit: Kastrat, Kastrati. Municipality: Malësi e Madha, Malësia e Madhe. County: Shkodër, Shkodra (6).
Rrashbull , Rrashbulli (village, municipality unit)	N 41.32278 E 19.51028. Variant form: Rashtbul. Municipality unit: Rrashbull, Rrashbulli. Municipality: Durrës, Durrësi. County: Durrës, Durrësi (12).
Rrogozhinë , Rrogozhina (town, municipality)	N 41.07639 E 19.66528. Municipality: Rrogozhinë, Rrogozhina. County: Tiranë, Tirana (25).
Rubjekë , Rubjeka (village)	N 41.39278 E 19.59944. Variant forms: Rezej, Rezhej. Municipality unit: Maminas, Maminasi. Municipality: Shijak, Shijaku. County: Durrës, Durrësi (7).
Sanjollas , Sanjollasi (village)	N 40.25895 E 20.59826. Municipality unit: Barmash, Barmashi. Municipality: Kolonjë, Kolonja. County: Korçë, Korça (11).
Sarandë , Saranda (city, municipality)	N 39.87534 E 20.00477. Municipality: Sarandë, Saranda. County: Vlorë, Vloa (18).
Shalës , Shalësi (village)	N 40.24726 E 20.64786. Municipality unit: Barmash, Barmashi. Municipality: Kolonjë, Kolonja. County: Korçë, Korça (10).
Sauk , Sauku (village)	N 41.3 E 19.83333. Variant form: Saukë. Municipality unit: Farkë, Farka. Municipality: Tiranë, Tirana. County: Tiranë, Tirana (14).
Selitë , Selita (village)	N 41.39650 E 20.03517. Variant forms: Mali me Gropë, Livadhet e Selitës (grassland area near Selitë). Landscape: Vargmalet e Skënderbeut (Skanderbeg Mountains), Mali me Gropa-Bizë-Martanesh (nature reserve). Municipality unit: Farkë, Farka. Municipality: Tiranë, Tirana. County: Tiranë, Tirana (7).
Seman , Semani (village)	N 40.79113 E 19.45514. Municipality: Lushnjë, Lushnja. County: Fier, Fieri (8).
Shën Thanas (church)	N 40.58852 E 20.682457. Variant form: Shen Thanas. Municipality unit: Voskopojë, Voskopoja. Municipality: Korçë, Korça. County: Korçë, Korça (7).
Shëngjin , Shëngjini (town, municipality unit)	N 41.81361 E 19.59389. Variant forms: Shen Gjini, San Giovanni di Medua, Medua. Municipality unit: Shëngjin, Shëngjini. Municipality: Lezhë, Lezha. County: Lezhë, Lezha (3).
Sherishtë , Sherishta (village)	N 40.46101 E 19.54279. Variant form: Kishbarda. Municipality unit: Qendër Vlorë. Municipality: Vlorë, Vloa. County: Vlorë, Vloa (3).
Shesh , Sheshi (village)	N 41.29972 E 19.66639. Variant form: Sesh. Municipality unit: Ndroq, Ndroqi. Municipality: Tiranë, Tirana. County: Tiranë, Tirana (13).
Shijak , Shijaku (town, municipality)	N 41.34556 E 19.56722. Variant form: Bazar Shiak. Municipality: Shijak, Shijaku. County: Durrës, Durrësi (11).
Shijon , Shijoni (village)	N 41.11667 E 20.01667. Variant form: Shingjonas. Municipality unit: Bradashesh, Bradasheshi. Municipality: Elbasan, Elbasani. County: Elbasan, Elbasani (8).
Shkalla e Priskës (landscape north-east of the Qafa e Priskë pass)	N 41.32806 E 19.95833. Variant form: Sh. Priskë. Landscape: Vargmalet e Skënderbeut (Skanderbeg Mountains). Municipality unit: Dajt, Dajti. Municipality: Tiranë, Tirana. County: Tiranë, Tirana (11).
Shkallë , Shkalla (village)	N 41.33333 E 19.96667. Variant form: Dajti: Shkall Prisk. Landscape: Vargmalet e Skënderbeut (Skanderbeg Mountains). Municipality unit: Dajt, Dajti. Municipality: Tiranë, Tirana. County: Tiranë, Tirana (9).
Shkëmb , Shkëmbi? (village, municipality unit)	N 40.93444, 20.02639. Variant form: Shkamb. Municipality unit: Shkëmb, Shkëmbi. Municipality: Cërrik, Cërriki. County: Elbasan, Elbasani (A?).
Shkodër , Shkodra (city, municipality)	N 42.06828 E 19.51258. Variant forms: Skodra, Scutari, Skutari. Municipality: Shkodër, Shkodra. County: Shkodër, Shkodra (○).
Shkozë , Shkozeti (village)	N 41.10056 E 19.57306. Municipality unit: Lekaj, Lekaji. Municipality: Rrogozhinë, Rrogozhina. County: Tiranë, Tirana (23).
Shtiçën , Shtiçëni (village, municipality unit)	N 42.04056 E 20.43417. Variant forms: Stiçen (in radices Montibus Djalicæ Ljums), Sticen. Municipality unit: Shtiçën, Shtiçëni. Municipality: Kukës, Kukësi. County: Kukës, Kukësi (11).
Shtuf , Shtufi (settlement)	N 42.02222 E 19.38227. Municipality unit: Ana e Malit. Municipality: Shkodër, Shkodra. County: Shkodër, Shkodra (14).

Table 1. Continued

Spille , Spilleja (village)	N 41.09547 E 19.46751. Municipality unit: Kryevidh, Kryevidhi. Municipality: Rrogozhinë, Rrogozhina. County: Tiranë, Tirana (24).
Sukth , Sukthi (village)	N 41.52639 E 19.62306. Municipality unit: Sukth, Sukthi. Municipality: Durrës, Durrësi. County: Durrës, Durrësi (10).
Tarabosh , Taraboshi, Mali i Taraboshit (mountain)	N 42.04639 E 19.44917. Variant form: Farabosk (misspelling). Municipality: Shkodër, Shkodra. County: Shkodër, Shkodra (12).
Theth , Thethi (village)	N 42.39583 E 19.77444. Landscape: Alpet Shqiptare (Prokletije), Shala (river valley). Municipality: Shkodër, Shkodra. County: Shkodër, Shkodra (5).
Tiranë , Tirana (city, municipality, capital)	N 41.3275 E 19.81889. Municipality: Tiranë, Tirana. County: Tiranë, Tirana (c).
Tomorr , Tomorri (mountain range): Tyrbja e Abaz Aliut (shrine)	N 40.63333 E 20.16667. Variant forms: Tomor, M. Tomori, Kloster Abbas Ali. Landscape: Parku Kombëtar i Malit të Tomorrit (Tomorr National Park). Municipality: Skrapar, Skrapari. County: Berat, Berati (7).
Tragjas , Tragjasi (village)	N 40.32669, E 19.51301. Municipality unit: Orikum, Orikumi. Municipality: Vlorë, Vlora. County: Vlorë, Vlora (7).
Tropojë , Tropoja (town, municipality)	N 42.35973 E 20.06977. Municipality: Tropojë, Tropoja. County: Kukës, Kukësi (3).
Uji i Ftohtë Tepelenë (mineral water source, tourist centre in the city of Tepelena)	N 40.25044 E 20.06487. Variant form: Uji Ftohte. Municipality unit: Tepelenë, Tepelena. Municipality: Tepelenë, Tepelena. County: Gjirokastrë, Gjirokastra (4).
Ura i Vezirit (formerly a bridge across the Drin River, submerged by the construction of the Fierza dam)	N 42.1068 E 20.3151. Variant forms: Vezir çupr., Vezir çuprija ad fluvium Drini barz. Landscape: Liqeni i Fierzës (Fierza reservoir). Municipality unit: Kukës, Kukësi. Municipality: Kukës, Kukësi. County: Kukës, Kukësi (9).
Ura Lapaj , Ura e Lapavës (bridge across the river Drin i zi)	N 41.89517 E 20.41681. Variant form: Lušna: Ura i Lopez (Lušna refers to the village of Lusën, County Kukes, not to Lushnjë, County Fier). Municipality unit: Bushtricë, Bushtrica. Municipality: Kukës, Kukësi. County: Kukës, Kukësi (15).
Uznovë , Uznova (urban district)	N 40.69722, E 19.98027. Municipality: Berat, Berati. County: Berat, Berati (3).
Velipojë , Velipoja (village, municipality unit)	N 41.87833 E 19.40556. Municipality unit: Velipojë, Velipoja. Municipality: Shkodër, Shkodra. County: Shkodër, Shkodra (16).
Vermosh , Vermoshi (village)	N 42.58993 E 19.69082. Variant form: Vermosa. Municipality unit: Kelmend, Kelmende. Municipality: Malësi e Madha, Malësia e Madhe. County: Shkodër, Shkodra (1).
Vlorë , Vlora (city, municipality)	N 40.4686 E 19.48318. Variant forms: Avlona, Valona, Vlonë. Municipality: Vlorë, Vlora. County: Vlorë, Vlora (c).
Vodicë , Vodica (village)	N 40.67666, E 20.00861. Municipality unit: Vertop, Vertopi. Municipality: Poliçan, Poliçani. County: Berat, Berati (4).
Vorë , Vora (town, municipality)	N 41.39804 E 19.67703. Variant form: Vorra. Municipality: Vorë, Vora. County: Tiranë, Tirana (1).
Vurg , Vurgu (plain, region)	N 39.83333 E 20.08333. Landscape: Vurg, Vurgu. Municipality: Sarandë, Saranda. County: Vlorë, Vlora (19).
Zall-Bastar (village, municipality unit): Shkalla e Tujanit (canyon)	N 41.39172 E 19.89070. Landscape: Mali i Dajtit. Municipality unit: Zall-Bastar. Municipality: Tiranë, Tirana. County: Tiranë, Tirana (4).
Zharrëz , Zharrëzi (village, municipality unit)	N 40.70917 E 19.64972. Variant form: Zharëza. Municipality unit: Zharrëz, Zharrëzi. Municipality: Patos, Patosi. County: Fier, Fieri (10).
Zvernëc , Zvernëci (village)	N 40.5028 E 19.4269; N 40.5133 E 19.4080. Municipality unit: Qendër Vlorë. Municipality: Vlorë, Vlora. County: Vlorë, Vlora (2).

Table 2. Locations of Heteroptera recordings from ‘Albania’ that are mystifying or ambiguous. Spelling of locations as used in the cited literature. The geographical coordinates are given in Lat° Long° WGS84.

Bresh	Reference: Mancini, 1953. ‘Bresh’ possibly refers to Prezë, Preza (village) (formerly also known as Bresa, Breša), Vorë, County: Tiranë (N 41.4213 E 19.6780).
Kopfstein, Süd-Albanien	Reference: Péricart, 1998b (leg. Apfelbeck, HNHM!). Viktor Apfelbeck, curator of the Sarajevo Museum from 1890, collected many insects in the Balkans (Schumacher, 1914). However, we have been unable to find a site in southern Albania that could be associated with the German-sounding name ‘Kopfstein’. The one entry for ‘Kopfstein’ provided by GeoNames refers to a mountain in Bavaria, GERMANY (N 49.73601 E 12.38477).
Korita	References: Csiki, 1940; Misja, 1973 (quoting from Csiki, 1940). ‘Korita’ refers either to the Albanian localities Koritë, Korita (village), Qendër Skrapar, Skrapar, County: Berat (N 40.54778 E 20.265) or Bregas, Bregasi (Koritë, Korita; village), Maliq, Vreshtas, County: Korçë (N 40.78194 E 20.81444) or to one of the many other entries in GeoNames for MONTENEGRO, NORTH MACEDONIA, BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA, SERBIA, SLOVENIA, CROATIA, and other countries.
Kosovo	Reference: Mancini, 1953. ‘Kosovo’ may refer to the Albanian locations of Kosovë, Kosova (village); Përmet, County: Gjirokastër (N 40.30389 E 20.39444) or Kosovë, Kosova (village), Fierzë, Belsh, County: Elbasan (N 40.89944 E 19.81611).
Ruskuli, Rushkull, or Rrushkull	References: Mancini, 1953; Josifov, 1970 (quoting from Mancini, 1953); Misja, 1970; Heiss, 2006. This place may refer to the Albanian locations of Rrushkull, Rrushkulli (village); Mirditë, County: Lezhë (N 41.42944 E 19.5125) or Rrushkull, Rrushkulli (village), County: Durrës (N 41.42944 E 19.5125) or Rrushkull, Rrushkulli (village), Dajç, County: Shkodër (N 41.97972 E 19.39806).
Rustany	References: Mancini, 1953; Josifov, 1970 (quoting from Mancini, 1953). According to Friese (1967), ‘Rustany’ refers to a place called ‘Rustanej’, 4 km east-northeast of Shijak, which we were unable to locate. The original description rather refers to a settlement called Bodniak, Bodniaku near Maminas, Shijak, County: Durrës (N 41.31844 E 19.61719).
Rusterj	References: Mancini, 1953; Josifov, 1970 (quoting from Mancini, 1953). The location of this record remains unclear.
Shkamb	References: Mancini, 1953; Josifov, 1970 (quoting from Mancini, 1953). ‘Shkamb’ may refer to the Albanian locations of Shkëmb, Shkëmbi (village), Cërrik, County: Elbasan (N 40.93444 E 20.02639) or Lavdar, Lavdari (Shkëmb, Shkëmbi; village); Vëndreshë, Skrapar, County: Berat (N 40.4975 E 20.10472).
Suha-Gora	Reference: Misja, 1970. ‘Suha-Gora’ may refer to the Albanian mountains Mali i Thatë; Pogradec, County: Korçë (N 40.88189 E 20.83398) or Mali i Sogorit; Lenie, Gramsh, County: Elbasan (N 40.75 E 20.36667).

Table 3. Locations of Heteroptera recordings originally attributed to ‘Albania’ but currently located in other countries. Spelling of locations as used in the cited literature. The geographical coordinates are given in Lat°, Long° WGS84.

Banica (prope Ipek)	Reference: Misja, 1973 (quoting from Csiki, 1940). Current name: Banjica, Peć, Komuna e Istogut, KOSOVO (N 42.71667 E 20.38917).
Durmitor	Reference: Mancini, 1953. Current name: Durmitor (mountain), MONTENEGRO (N 43.12792 E 19.03411) or Durmitor (hill), SERBIA (N 43.696 E 20.14002).
Ferijovic	Reference: Mancini, 1953. Current name: Ferizaj, Komuna e Ferizajt, KOSOVO (N 42.37056 E 21.15528).
Hodzha.	References: Mancini, 1953; Josifov, 1970 (quoting from Mancini, 1953). Current name: Hoça e Qytetit, Prizren, KOSOVO (N 42.17472 E 20.69139).
Ipek, Ipak, Ipek (in fauce Plavensi), Ipek: Mons Peklen	References: Misja, 1973 (quoting from Csiki, 1940); Péricart, 1993. Current name: Pejë, Peja; Peć, Komuna e Pejës, KOSOVO (N 42.65913 E 20.28828).
Janina	References: Schumacher, 1914; Josifov, 1970 (quoting from Schumacher, 1914). Current name: Ioannina, Epirus, GREECE (N 39.66486 E 20.85189).
Kavac	Reference: Mancini, 1953; Josifov, 1970 (quoting from Mancini, 1953). Current name: Kavač, Kotor, MONTENEGRO (N 42.41222 E 18.74472).
Lapad	References: Mancini, 1953; Josifov, 1970 (quoting from Mancini, 1953). Current name: Dubrovačko-Neretvanska (Dubrovnik city district), CROATIA (N 42.65396 E 18.07792).
Mitrovica	Reference: Misja, 1973 (quoting from Csiki, 1940). Current name: Mitrovićë, Mitrovica (city), KOSOVO (N 42.88333 E 20.86667).
Mons Peklen, Kosovo polje: Mitrovica	Reference: Csiki, 1940. Current name: Peklëna (ridge), KOSOVO (N 42.685 E 20.24472).
Ohret	Reference: Mancini, 1953. Current name: Ohrid (city), NORTH MACEDONIA (N 41.11722 E 20.80194).
Pecurici	References: Mancini, 1953; Josifov, 1970 (quoting from Mancini, 1953). Current name: Pecurice (town), MONTENEGRO (N 42.03028 E 19.17306).
Peristeri	References: Schumacher, 1914; Josifov, 1970 (quoting from Schumacher, 1914). Current name: Baba, Pelister (mountains), NORTH MACEDONIA (N 41.00334 E 21.18425).
Poljana	Reference: Schumacher, 1914. Current name: Poljana, MONTENEGRO (N 43.26611 E 19.08028 and N 43.27444 E 19.51806) or Poljana, Kochani, NORTH MACEDONIA (N 41.96472 E 22.36389) or Poljana, KOSOVO (N 42.19556 E 20.95639). Numerous further entries in GeoNames, but no entry for Albania.
Prizren	References: Mancini, 1953; Josifov, 1970 (quoting from Mancini, 1953); Péricart, 1998a. Current name: Prizren (city), KOSOVO (N 42.21389 E 20.73972).
Rabic	References: Mancini, 1953; Josifov, 1970 (quoting from Mancini, 1953). Current name: Rabić (hill), Srpska, BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA (N 44.95861 E 17.91722).
Rikavec	Reference: Mancini, 1953. Current name: Rikavec (hill), KOSOVO (N 42.18333 E 20.70139).
Rudnik	Reference: Péricart, 1998c. Current name: Rudnik Raduša (village), Saraj, NORTH MACEDONIA (N 42.08258 E 21.22156). Numerous further entries in GeoNames, but no entry for Albania.
Shar Dagh (Ljuboten)	Reference: Horváth, 1916. Current name: Šar Panina (Šar Dagh, Shar Dagh)-Ljuboten, Mountain range between KOSOVO and NORTH MACEDONIA (N 42.20667 E 21.11944).
Sisevo	References: Mancini, 1953; Josifov, 1970 (quoting from Mancini, 1953). Current name: Šišëvo, Shishovë (village), Grad Skopje, NORTH MACEDONIA (N 41.9756 E 21.30938).
Uskub	References: Mancini, 1953; Josifov, 1970 (quoting from Mancini, 1953). Current name: Skopje (city and capital), Grad Skopje, NORTH MACEDONIA (N 41.99646 E 21.43141).